

Literature & case study review on outcomes in payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programmes

Case studies

This document presents the full case studies received to inform section 4.5.3 in the IPBES values assessment, on protected areas.

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Costa Rica, National Payments for Ecosystem Services (Pagos por Servicios Ambientales)

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1. Background and context

Costa Rica's Payments for Environmental Services (PES; often the Spanish acronym PSA is used to describe Costa Rica's program. Here I'll use "PSA" when referring to Costa Rica's program and "PES" in reference to ecosystem services policy more generally) program was established in 1997. It is a nation-wide program dedicated promoting forest conservation and new tree plantings among private landowners, and within the country's Indigenous reserves. The program is administered by a quasi-state institution, the National Forestry Financing Fund (FONAFIFO), which is part of the Ministry of Environment. FONAFIFO has a governing board that is composed partly by members of the country's forestry industry (hence the quasi-state label). FONAFIFO receives money from a 3.5% gasoline tax, water tariffs, and various multilateral agency loans. Payments from FONAFIFO to landowners are considered to be compensation for four environmental services: carbon sequestration, hydrological services, biodiversity, and scenic beauty. Legally, when FONAFIFO makes a payment to the landowner, the agency is purchasing the rights to these services, which it can then sell to downstream users of these services (in the form of a carbon offset, for example). In practice, FONAFIFO has struggled to make such downstream sales, as the market for carbon offsets that was first envisioned in the 1990s failed to materialize (Fletcher and Breitling 2012).

Biophysical Conditions: Costa Rica is a small, but very ecologically diverse country, encompassing twelve Holdridge life zones. The main population center of the country is in the centrally located, heavily urbanized area of San José. This is a mountainous area with good climatic conditions for growing coffee. The Northwest part of the country (Guanacaste) is a dry forest, and is an area that has been historically dominated by the Latifundia system of land tenure (Edelman 1992) resulting in large levels of land inequality. The Northeast and Eastern part of the country are largely flat largely flat and composed of tropical forest. These areas have seen some of the highest rates of deforestation from the 1960s to the 1980s, and are also some of the highest rates of PES participation in the country (Porrás 2010). The Southeast (Osa Peninsula) is also composed of tropical rain forest with some of the wettest areas in the country.

After starting with three types of payment modes in 1997, the program expanded to include as many as 13 different types of payment modalities in 2013. Currently, there are ten different payment types (FONAFIFO 2020a). These different modalities can be thought of as two types: payments for protecting existing forests and payments for planting new trees. Payment modalities for protecting existing forests historically comprise the vast majority of payments (between 60-80%), and are typically lower (around \$320/ha in 2011) than reforestation payments (\$980/ha in 2011). Payments for reforestation activities comprise around 20% of program contracts, and are generally meant to support commercial wood

harvesting (Lansing 2013). Landowners are compensated in yearly installments over a five year period and, in exchange, they maintain trees on their land for ten to fifteen years (the timing depends on the specific PES modality they are engaged in). Limitations in research and data availability make it difficult to say precisely how many landowners have participated in this program over its history. According to FONAFIFO, the program's payments covered 589,950 hectares since 2010 (FONAFIFO 2020b). This amounts to about 11.5% of the country's land area. In her review of the program's early outcomes, Porras (2010) estimated that, from 1997 to 2008, 100,000 contracts were completed. The actual number of landowners, however, is likely far less because of contract renewals.

Costa Rica's PSA program is one of the first nationwide PES programs in the world. Its first mover status has produced a minor drama with the rollout of REDD+ as a global policy making tool. To briefly summarize: Costa Rica cannot claim many of the reforestation gains it has made in the 1990s and 2000s under the auspices of REDD+. This era of reforestation trends serve as a baseline level for future REDD+ credits, making it difficult for the country to receive very many REDD+ credits. In other words, the country's widespread forest rebound occurred too early for the country to claim significant REDD+ credits. In its REDD Readiness plans, the country has responded by scaling down its analysis and claiming various fronts of deforestation within the country, even as the nationwide reforestation trends are positive (Government of Costa Rica 2010). The country's structure for administering REDD+ is set up to run through FONAFIFO, with some modifications to membership of the governing board. Future REDD+ credits are set up to run through the country's PSA system (Forest Carbon Partnership 2013).

Socio-Economic Conditions: The most important contextual factors to understanding the development and implementation of its PSA program are: 1) the country's history of land inequality and state efforts to address this; 2) the country's high rates of deforestation from 1960 through the 1980s, and 3) the country's period of structural adjustment from 1982 to 1993, along with the outsize influence of U.S foreign aid through the 1980s due to the Contra War.

The country's historical land inequality has produced a legacy of many individuals colonizing land in the country's non-urban periphery, especially in the flat, tropical Eastern part of the country (Vunderink 1990). The result is that areas with the lowest social development tend to be in areas furthest away from the largely urbanized geographic center of the country. It has also resulted in many landowners that have legal ownership to their land, but they often have incomplete title (eg. rights but no official title, or title but no official land survey; see Lansing 2014; Porras et al. 2017).

The country's alarming deforestation trends in the 1970s and 1980s were largely due to the conversion of forest to pasture land (Guess 1979; Sader and Joyce 1988). This was due, in part, to the government's subsidies for cattle ranching. This also led to the country's first forestry subsidies in the 1980s, which are often seen as a precursor to the eventual PSA program in the 1990s. The government eliminated its cattle subsidies under structural adjustment pressure from the World Bank, and the country became more urbanized during this time (Vunderink 1990; Lansing et al. 2014). By the 1990s, much of the nation's deforestation trends had reversed (Sanchez-Azofeifa et al. 2007).

The country's period of structural adjustment ended with the World Bank's third and final structural adjustment loan to the country in 1993. This loan included demands to change the country's forestry laws. The subsequent, landmark 1996 forestry law that established PES was largely a response to this demand. Its passage included both the establishment of its PSA program, but also, a deforestation ban (Matulis 2013; Lansing et al. 2015). It remains possible to legally cut and harvest timber if the landowner has a certified management plan and obtains the proper permits, however, forests cannot fully converted to other land uses.

As Silva (1997) details, this forestry law was widely seen as a political win for the country's forestry industry, and a partial loss for environmentalists and peasant activists, who saw their much more progressive forestry bill defeated. This law institutionalized the forestry industry within the state apparatus through the creation of FONAFIFO, and established a payment system that can be read as a dramatic expansion of previous plantation forestry subsidies (eg. Fletcher and Breitling 2012), even if its policy architects would never describe it that way (Lansing 2014).

Power Relations and Political Influence among Stakeholders: The main stakeholders around PSA in Costa Rica are the following: medium size, capitalist farmers (usually coffee or cattle), the plantation agriculture industry, smallholding peasants, the forestry industry, and the environmental/ecotourism lobby. In general, the relative power of coffee/cattle farmers and peasants have been in decline since the 1980s (Seligson 1980; Edelman 1999) and the relative power of plantation agriculture, the environmental/ecotourism lobby, and the forestry industry has been on the rise since this time (Vunderink 1990; Edelman 1999). This change was largely driven by structural adjustment mandates from the World Bank, which called for the elimination of state subsidies for cattle and coffee and the implementation of state support for "nontraditional" agricultural exports like pineapple. What I am calling the "ecotourism lobby" encompasses a broad group, from grassroots environmental organizations, to international environmental groups, to expatriate hotel operators. It is not necessarily a coherent coalition, but their combined importance to the economy (and relative political power) has surpassed even agriculture as tourism is now Costa Rica's number one industry. The forestry industry has been, and still is, an economically marginal industry, and had very little political organization until the early 1990s, when USAID helped to organize a disparate, and decentralized group of wood processors and tree plantation landowners into a coherent lobby. This more organized lobby was able to help pass the 1996 Forestry Law (mentioned above) that created PSA.

2. Problematization

How was the environmental problem defined?

Costa Rica's PSA program grew out of rising concern around the country's high deforestation rate, which was one of the highest in the world through the 1970s and 1980s (Robalino and Pfaff 2013). For some environmental actors, the country's deforestation trends were a problem because of possible long term ecological damage to the country, and helped inspire some of the early examples of "debt for nature swaps" (Lansing et al. 2015). Other actors, however, viewed deforestation as a problem because it represents a suboptimal use of land, and is a potential drag on export led growth because of the loss of

domestic timber supplies. This view was most prominent among U.S and multilateral aid agencies in the late 1980s and early 1990s. In a 1989 report, for example, USAID suggested increased subsidies to landowners to maintain forest were needed to help maintain a favorable trade balance (Lansing et al. 2015). The World Bank's 1993 forestry policy review of Costa Rica calculated the value of its forests in terms of various ecosystem services (de Camino et al. 2000) . This was one of the first times a monetary value was attached to a forest's environmental services, and was an important institutional step toward PSA becoming included in the country's 1996 forestry law.

How was PES chosen as a solution?

While in 1989 USAID suggested more direct subsidies to stop deforestation, by the early 1990s, the language of ecosystem service payments had come to dominate the policy making agenda. This occurred through two fronts: 1) diffusion of the idea through elite institutions from the global North, and 2) practical implementation of advanced payments for timber through USAID technology transfers.

As mentioned above, the diffusion of ecosystem services concept among state institutions occurred through the World Bank's 1993 forestry policy review for Costa Rica. Here, the idea of a value of various ecosystem services that forests can provide appeared in a key institutional document. During this period USAID also financed a number of studies that purported to show the monetary value of the ecosystem services the country's forests produce (de Camino et al. 2000).

While the top-down diffusion of the ecosystem services concept undoubtedly played a role, local experiments in advanced forestry payments, along with newly acquired GIS technology also helped establish a proof of concept for the idea. Beginning in 1989 USAID created a forestry NGO (first called FORESTA, then FUNDECOR) that used GIS software to identify "irrational" use of land (eg. pasture land where forest use would be more appropriate), and to encourage landowners to see their forests as potential sources of annual income (Gonzalez et al. 1998). FUNDECOR's strategy was to take on the burden of developing the state-mandated sustainable management plans on behalf of landowners as a way to encourage a more "rational" use of their forestry resources (Brockett and Gottfried 2002). FUNDECOR was able to use its newly-acquired GIS and remote sensing capability to develop a sophisticated map to target the best places to help landowners meet sustainable management plans (Obando 1998; de Vos 2007). FUNDECOR's GIS tools were then used to monitor the forest management plan that they helped landowners develop, and predict forest harvests over a ten year period, allowing FUNDECOR to give landowners an advance payment for their forests' timber by selling future timber harvests (Obando 1998; de Vos 2007). Thus, FUNDECOR's use of GIS allowed its original work of smoothing bureaucratic hurdles for landowners to providing such landowners up front payments, and overcoming the long 'time lag' between tree plantings and sale.

FUNDECOR then went even further with their geospatial data by combining it with maps of forest types and tree growth rates in order to estimate the increased rates of carbon fixation its management interventions were encouraging. The resulting maps showed, in a precise and scientific way, how advance payments could be made for ecological services. These maps were initial and influential "proof of concept" for the development of PSa in Costa Rica (De Vos 2007).

In sum, forests were conceived as sources of monetary value, but always subject to “irrational” uses. During the late 1980s and early 1990s, various multilateral aid organizations set about, both discursively and materially, to solve this problem of irrational land use through better planning, institutional capacity building, and the attachment of monetary value to various ecosystem services. This was not a coordinated plan, but something that emerged piecemeal through various institutional efforts to deal with overall problem of deforestation.

What ecosystem services (ES) were prioritized in the initial design? Who was identified as beneficiaries and potential providers of ES, and how?

The initial design of PSA was to compensate landowners for four ecosystem services: carbon sequestration, hydrological services, biodiversity, and scenic beauty. These remains the core idea behind the program today. Initial beneficiaries were to be any landowner that could potentially provide this service, and the program has always operated on a “first come, first serve” basis, though with modifications to this as the program matured. The early years of the program had little outreach, especially in more remote communities. The initial years relied heavily, if not exclusively, on the above-mentioned NGO FUNDECOR as an intermediary to identify landowners and help them with processing the application (Legrand et al. 2011). Specific types of beneficiaries (large landowners, peasants, coffee farmers etc.) were not explicitly identified in the initial program design. As we will see below, however, a certain type of landowner (large and wealthy) did emerge as a beneficiary in the early years due to the institutional structure of the program.

3. Values and value articulation

What value articulation method(s) was/were used in the initial design process (e.g. MCA, ecosystem modeling/targeting, referenda, focus groups, etc.)? How was spatial targeting and prioritization done? How were upstream participants/ES ‘providers’ targeted?

The initial orientation of the PSA program was around identifying the monetary value of the various ecosystem services. As mentioned above, a number of influential studies from the early 1990s were circulating (Tropical Science Center, World Bank) that purported to quantify the economic value of various ecosystem services in the country (De Vos 2007; Lansing et al. 2015). The final payment figures, however, didn’t conform exactly to the amounts in these studies. The main architects of the program have said that it is in fact the price of land rent for pasture that determined the price of their payments for conservation (see Castro et al. 2000; see also de Camino et al. 2000).

Five years into the PSA program, Costa Rica received two rounds of loans from the World Bank that were meant to strengthen and expand the program (colloquially known as Ecomarkets I and II). It is hard to overstate the significance of these loans for the program. These were the first loans to Costa Rica from the World Bank since their politically unpopular structural adjustment loan in 1993. The loans totaled \$80 million and represented a massive expansion of PSA (A 53 fold expansion of its budget (Matulis 2017). Because of the how the financing mechanisms were negotiated with the Costa Rican government, these loans helped establish a permanent base of financial support for PSA from the state. It made the money

available from a 3.5% gas tax a permanent earmark designated only for FONAFIFO rather than a pot of money controlled by the Ministry of Finance (Matulis 2017).

Four key values were articulated in these loans that came to infuse the program in various ways. First, is spatial targeting areas that have high biodiversity. Payments financed from this loan needed to go to areas designated and being “biodiversity gaps”. Second, FONAFIFO was to place a greater emphasis on contracts with women headed households and indigenous peoples. Third, the loan demanded better outreach to rural areas. This led to the creation of more regional offices and the expansion of intermediary institutions.

Finally, this loan contained an approach toward a newly-implemented water tariff that doubled down on the market-based theory of the program. Water tariff fees could only be directed to upstream landowners within the same watershed from which the fees originated. Further, the water fee was paid by water consumers rather than water polluters. According to Matulis (2013) both of these ideas were incorporated so the program could more fully conform to the market-based ideals of end users paying for the ecosystem services they consume. This has also had the result of spreading the costs of the program away from polluters and among the population at large. It has also benefited wealthier watersheds at the expense of poorer regions of the country.

From almost the beginning, the program has been very popular with landowners, with applicants outstripping available funds (as many as 2/3rds of applicants are rejected due to unavailable funds). To determine the recipients of relatively scarce funds, FONAFIFO uses a points system, where landowners meeting certain desired qualifications receive points on their application. Final points are used to determine whether an applicant can receive PSA payments. A landowner’s location with a designated “biodiversity hotspot” will garner significant points.

Early assessments of Costa Rica’s PSA program have shown that the program overwhelmingly benefitted large, wealthy landowners (Zbinden and Lee 2005; Porras 2010). Porras, for example, found that 40-45% of all payments from 1997 to 2008 went to registered corporations. This could include large corporations but also family farms that are registered as a corporation and run as a business. As the program grew, and especially after the World Bank Ecomarkets loans, FONAFIFO has tried to rectify this situation. Applicants are now given points if they come from regions of low “social development” or are smaller landowners (less than 50 hectares). These points, however, are a lot less than the ecological points. For example, an applicant would receive 85 points for being in a biodiversity hotspot, but only 10 points for being in an area of low social development, and 25 points for being a small landowner (see MINANET 2012). In 2003 FONAFIFO instituted an “agroforestry” modality, where landowners are paid per tree, rather than by the hectare. This was meant to allow very small landowners to receive payments for trees planted along the fence lines and between crops (Porras 2010).

Beyond the changing targets based on the application points system, there is also a de facto targeting that has emerged through the program’s reliance on intermediary NGOs to help enroll landowners (Legrand 2011; Bosselman and Lund 2013). In the early years of the program, PES applicants were enrolled almost entirely through the FUNDECOR NGO mentioned above. FONAFIFO eventually opened eight regional

offices for more direct outreach to landowners. Nevertheless, the application process is complicated, and it requires an approved land management plan that is developed by a certified forestry regent. These requirements have meant that a number of forestry NGOs (including FUNDECOR, but others as well) have emerged as intermediaries to help process the paperwork so that landowners may access PES. Typically, the NGO takes an 18% cut in the payment in return for processing the application. Between the intermediary work of NGOs, and the administrative costs of FONAFIFO, Legrand et al. (2011) estimate that up to 40% of payments are consumed by various administrative transaction costs. This places Costa Rica's program as having some of the highest PES transaction costs in the developing world (Wunder 2007; Legrand et al. 2011).

How and why did some values become influential over others in program design and/or implementation?

From the beginning, Costa Rica's PSA program was infused with the idea that there is a monetary value that can be attached to the ecosystem services that forests provide. By "getting the prices right" ecologically irrational uses of land would stop. As far as I can tell, there were no PES-specific alternative values that were ever articulated by program architects. As the program proved popular, FONAFIFO began discussing PSA as a program of social development as well (Lansing 2014). This was around the time the agency began to more explicitly target a broader range of landowners.

PSA itself emerged out of a 1996 forestry law that was something of a political victory for the forestry industry and a partial defeat for peasant and environmental organizations (Silva 1997; Baltodano 1998). To briefly summarize a long story, the 1996 forestry law was enacted over an earlier forestry bill had been slowly making its way through the legislature. This earlier bill prioritized the concerns of a collection of peasantry and environmental groups. Its main component was to provide state support for various grassroots development initiatives around sustainable forestry activities (Silva 1997; Brockett and Gottfried 2002). For example, the original bill provided support for peasant groups engaging in community forestry, mandated that industrial production use a proportion of community forestry products, and provided no support for tree plantations or exotic species. In response, USAID organized the forestry industry into its own trade group, and helped spur the passage of an alternative law, one that included more support for, and deregulation of, the plantation forestry sector. Some support for grassroots forestry groups was still included in this law. As part of this comprehensive forestry law, the PSA program was created. While it was not a complete victory for forest industrialists, the defeat of the previous law was generally seen as a loss for peasantry and environmental groups promoting grassroots development (Silva 1997; Brockett and Gottfried 2002).

Upon passage of Forestry law 7575, the PSA program was criticized by grassroots environmental groups along the following lines. First, it relied too much on a professionalized forestry bureaucracy, requiring expensive assessments and certifications from forestry regents to enroll in the program. This process excludes more marginal land owners. Second, the reforestation modality (which comprises about 20% of the program) was centered entirely around promoting single species tree plantations, rather than natural regeneration (natural regeneration has been a recurring modality in PSA, but a very small one). Third,

there was originally almost no money allocated for outreach, or regional offices, which would lead to only well connected landowners taking advantage of the program. Finally, PES was critiqued as an overall misallocation of funds that could have been directed toward shoring up the chronically underfunded national parks system. Many former landowners within this system are still waiting for their promised monetary compensation from when these parks were created (these critiques are summarized from Baltodano 1998).

In short, some environmental and peasant organizations critiqued the PSA program for being a system that is geared toward more well-connected, larger landowners, and for reforestation payments, geared toward helping the forestry industry, and promoting landscapes of monoculture tree plantations. Subsequent research has largely confirmed many of these critiques, especially with regard to outcomes from the early years of the program (see assessment above). Payments mostly went to large landowners, reforestation payments tended to produce monoculture tree plantations, and the involvement of the forestry regents, along with all of the bureaucratic procedures involved in PES has largely limited the participation of smaller, more economically marginalized, landowners (Porrás 2010; Lansing 2014; Matulis 2016).

Were trade-offs made among multiple objectives, and if so how and by whom?

In response to the demands of the World Bank's "Ecomarkets" loans, and later critiques by peasant organizations, FONAFIFO has been responsive to the needs of smaller producers. In 2003, it introduced the agroforestry modality, where landowners are paid by the tree. This allows smaller landowners to be compensated for trees they plant along fence lines or in between farm plots. In 2004, FONAFIFO began giving emphasis to areas of low social development. In recent years, FONAFIFO has adopted a more inclusive development language and openly talks about how PES can, and should, be a program of social development (Lansing 2014). This shift has resulted in some measured changes in outcomes. The early years of the program were dominated by large landowners, but more recent years have indeed seen more medium-size and some smaller landowners become enrolled in the program. Nevertheless, the key role of the forestry regents, along with the onerous paperwork requirements of the program have excluded the more marginalized landowners, especially those that do not have official land surveys, or those that have received land from the state agrarian development agency (Lansing 2014).

Despite this halting success at becoming more inclusive, the program has also doubled down on some of the more neoliberal ideals of the program as well. This can most clearly be seen in use of the water tariff regulations (mentioned above), where payments are made within the watershed from which the tariff originated, rather than spread more equitably across the country (see Matulis 2013).

4. Distribution of costs and benefits

Distribution of Benefits

The PES program uses monetary payments. Typically landowners are paid over a five year period while they agree to leave their land in conservation for 10 to 15 years (the exact years depends on the specific

modality). Benefits are largely distributed to individual landowners, with a few exceptions. The program has an agreement with the country's Indigenous reserves to make payments to them collectively. This is necessary because, in the eyes of the state, all of the land in an Indigenous reserve is owned by the governing Indigenous council, with individual land ownership a matter of internal concern to Indigenous group (Lansing 2014). At the behest of the World Bank, the early 2000s prioritized areas of biological need, however, due to pressure from peasant organizations, the criteria was altered in 2004 to also give priority to areas of low social development. This does not, however, necessarily mean that an applicant from an area of low SDI is an applicant of high need. Research by Porras (2010) shows that when this geographic equity modality was instituted it did not necessarily result in a shift of more payments to applicants of higher need, but rather, it included wealthier applicants who happened to live in these areas received payments.

There has been very little research on the actual perception of payments by participants. Work by Arriagada et al. (2015), however, show that participant motivations had little to do with the money offered, but instead, were grounded in seeking more secure property rights and contributing to the conservation of forests. Schwartz's (2017) interviews with male and female headed households in the Osa region shows that this conservationist view is true with women headed households that receive payment. Male headed households, however, tended to emphasize the monetary benefits of the program.

Distribution of Costs

There is almost no explicit consideration of the social costs in the literature on PSA. Arriagada et al. (2015) speculate that the high renewal rate of PSA participants in their study site indicates that the overall social and economic costs of PSA are low. In an otherwise positive assessment of the program's impacts, Locatelli et al. (2008) found negative income impacts for small farmers participating in the reforestation modality. They found that the payments were not enough to cover the investments needed for a forest plantation, and that the incomes of smaller farmers suffered in the short term.

There is a monitoring system set up through FONAFIFO and participants can lose their payments if they do not follow the terms of their contract. I am not aware of any research that has assessed the efficacy of FONAFIFO's monitoring program.

5. Outcomes

Participation and Social Outcomes:

It is unclear to what extent FONAFIFO does in-house monitoring of participation, but Porras (2010) conducted an extensive review of participation using FONAFIFO's records. Her main conclusions are that the program has heavily favored large, wealthy landowners in the early years of the program (1997 to 2003), to a shift where more medium and small landowners have begun participating (see also Zbinden and Lee 2005). As mentioned above FONAFIFO has moved to effect this shift by introducing an agroforestry modality and by prioritizing areas of low social development, and expanding its regional offices. FONAFIFO's efforts to enroll the rural poor have had mixed success. This is especially true of their

policy of prioritizing areas of low social development. As Porras (2010) has shown, this geographic targeting has not translated into farmer specific targeting, as it appears many wealthy, often absentee landowners from these regions have received PSA payments. Even smallholders that do enroll in PSA tend to be more wealthy, and older, than non-enrollees of similar size. It appears that many of these smallholders are only marginally engaged in agriculture and are using PSA as a later-in-life retirement strategy (Lansing 2017).

There also remain significant barriers for some of the country's most marginalized landowners to enroll in PSA. These are mostly related to land tenure issues. Because of a separate land tenure law, applicants must have official land title and an official cadastral survey of their land, and the geographic data points on both papers must match exactly. Landowners commonly have to rectify these discrepancies, and the modest cost of doing so is often out of reach for poor farmers (Lansing 2014; Porras et al. 2017). This is a requirement related to a separate program of land regularization and is not something FONAFIFO can change. In addition, landowners that received land from the state agrarian development agency (INDER) that are behind on their payments to this agency (the land is purchased over a 20 year period) also cannot participate. This is also a common situation for INDER recipients and outside of FONAFIFO's control (the policy is set by INDER). This policy effectively excludes many recipients of state agrarian reform lands. Thus, there remain some fairly intractable problems for the country's most marginalized landowners to participate in the program (Lansing 2014).

Beyond simply measuring who has accessed PSA there is sparse research on the actual social and economic impacts of the program. Arriagada et al. (2010) found the payment's impact to be essentially neutral. Payments did not contribute to increased on-farm investments or facilitate moving into off-farm activities, but the costs of the program were not onerous either (as evidenced by the high reenrollment rates of their study subjects). An early analysis of PSA impacts in one watershed indicated a 15% increase in disposable income and increased on-farm investments (Miranda et al. 2003). Locatelli et al. (2008) found mixed impacts, with an overall positive impact, but with some negative income impacts on smaller and more poor farmers. They found that poorer farmers enrolled in the reforestation modality suffered short and medium term income losses. This is because the payment does not cover all of the costs of reforestation. Browenson et al. (2020) compared the national PSA program to a local, non-state PES program and found the local program was better at targeting smaller, less wealthy landowners. They were, however, unable to detect any real differences in social outcomes between PES and non-PES households.

I am not aware of any systematic effort at FONAFIFO to measure the social impacts of their payments. An internal review of the World Bank's Ecomarket's loans indicated that the program did indeed expand its reach to more women headed households and to more Indigenous groups (Ferraro et al. 2005). There was, however, no effort to gauge the social impacts of this expansion. Finally, work by Schwartz (2017) shows women's motivations for enrolling in PSA are more related to the environmental benefits of the program than men. Women headed households that receive PSA tended to have less decision making control than households that did not receive payments.

Ecological Outcomes

While research on the social impacts of PSA are scant, there are numerous studies on the ecological impacts of Costa Rica's PES program. Collectively, there is not a strong consensus as to whether the program has succeeded in halting the country's deforestation trends. Everyone agrees that Costa Rica's days of rampant deforestation are over, and the country has experienced a forest rebound since the 1990s. The disagreement is over the extent to which the PSA program produced this change (ie. whether PSA payments are additional). The passage of the country 1996 Forestry Law that ushered in PES also included a ban on forest conversion and some studies have pointed to this ban on deforestation as a driver of reforestation trends in the country (e.g. Fagan et al. 2014). Similarly, the elimination of cattle subsidies during the structural adjustment period of 1980s has been noted as a factor in the country's forest rebound (Pfaff et al. (2008). Work by Sierra and Russman (2006), Sanchez-Azofeifa (2007), and Pfaff et al. (2008) have all concluded that PES is not driving reforestation trends (see also Robalino and Pfaff 2013). Studies by Arriagada et al. (2012) and Morse et al. (2009) show that PES payments are in fact additional in the region where FUNDECOR has worked. As Daniels et al. (2010) point out, comparing these studies is difficult because they all use slightly different measurement techniques and scales of analysis. Arriagada et al. (2012) use a rigorous matching technique that takes great pains to control for unobserved bias. They show that payments produce an average additional gain of around 11 ha. per contract. Their work, however, is confined to the region of FUNDECOR's work, an area where PSA has the strongest institutional presence and history.

One social/ecological critique of PES has been that the reforestation modality has almost exclusively promoted single species tree plantations (Lansing 2013), which ultimately serve as inputs for plantation agriculture in the form of wooden pallets for shipping. This was a concern voiced by environmental activists from the program's very beginning (see Baltodano 1998). Due to the forestry industry's relatively weak structural position in the Costa Rican economy, it largely serves as a provider of low grade wood for the production of pallets for fruit exports. PES payments for reforestation have largely gone to support these activities. In this way, this specific modality (which comprise about 20% of payments) essentially serve as an indirect subsidy for plantation agriculture.

6. Methodology and literature:

The literature search for this assessment involved expert judgement of available literature as well as additional searches on google scholar.

The following terms were used (separate searches for "PES" and "PSA"):

1. "PES" ("PSA") "inequality" "Costa Rica"
2. "PES" ("PSA") "Social impacts" "Costa Rica"
3. "PES" ("PSA") "women" "Costa Rica"
4. "PES" "REDD+" "Costa Rica"
5. "PES" ("PSA") "institutions"
6. "PES" ("PSA") "effectiveness" "Costa Rica"

Gray Literature

Porras (2010) is a piece of gray literature, which I have known about for some time. Porras et al. (2017) I found with search terms #2 above. Legrand (2011) I found in the bibliography of Porras et al. (2017).

References

- Arriagada, Rodrigo A., et al. (2012) Do payments for environmental services affect forest cover? A farm-level evaluation from Costa Rica. *Land Economics* 88.2: 382-399.
- Arriagada, R. A., Sills, E. O., Ferraro, P. J., & Pattanayak, S. K. (2015). Do payments pay off? Evidence from participation in Costa Rica's PES program. *PLoS one*, 10(7), e0131544.
- Baltodano, J. (1998). Pago de servicios ambientales para reconstrucción ecosistémica, fortalecimiento de organizaciones locales y desarrollo rural. *Revista de Ciencias Ambientales (Trop J Environ Sci)*. EISSN: 2215-3896. Junio, 2000. Vol 18(1): 21-30.
- Bosselmann, A. S., & Lund, J. F. (2013). Do intermediary institutions promote inclusiveness in PES programs? The case of Costa Rica. *Geoforum*, 49, 50-60.
- Brockett, C. D., & Gottfried, R. R. (2002). State policies and the preservation of forest cover: lessons from contrasting public-policy regimes in Costa Rica. *Latin American Research Review*, 7-40.
- Brownson, K., Anderson, E. P., Ferreira, S., Wenger, S., Fowler, L., & German, L. (2020). Governance of Payments for Ecosystem Services influences social and environmental outcomes in Costa Rica. *Ecological Economics*, 174, 106659.
- Castro, R., Tattenbach, F., Gamez, L., & Olson, N. (2000). The Costa Rican experience with market instruments to mitigate climate change and conserve biodiversity. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*, 61(1), 75-92.
- Daniels, A. E., Bagstad, K., Esposito, V., Moolaert, A., & Rodriguez, C. M. (2010). Understanding the impacts of Costa Rica's PES: Are we asking the right questions?. *Ecological economics*, 69(11), 2116-2126.
- De Camino, R.; Segura, O.; Arias, L.G.; Pérez, I. (2000). *Costa Rica Forest Strategy and the Evolution of Land Use: Evaluation Country Case Study Series*. The World Bank. Washington, DC. 128 p.
- de Vos, H.J. 2007. Organisational culture: institutionalization of GIS for forest monitoring in Costa Rica. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design* 34(2): 355–368.
- Edelman, M. (1992). *The logic of the latifundio: the large estates of northwestern Costa Rica since the late nineteenth century*. Stanford University Press.
- Edelman, M. (1999). *Peasants against globalization: rural social movements in Costa Rica*. Stanford University Press.

- Fagan, M. E., DeFries, R. S., Sesnie, S. E., Arroyo, J. P., Walker, W., Soto, C., ... & Sanchun, A. (2013). Land cover dynamics following a deforestation ban in northern Costa Rica. *Environmental Research Letters*, 8(3), 034017.
- Ferraro, P., Spergel, B., & Sills, E. (2005). Evaluation of the World Bank–GEF Ecomarkets Project in Costa Rica.
- Fletcher, R., & Breitling, J. (2012). Market mechanism or subsidy in disguise? Governing payment for environmental services in Costa Rica. *Geoforum*, 43(3), 402-411.
- FONAFIFO (2020a). Actividades. <https://www.fonafifo.go.cr/es/servicios/actividades-y-sub-actividades/>. Accessed: Aug. 11, 2020.
- FONAFIFO. (2020b). Distribucion de hectareas de PSA. <https://www.fonafifo.go.cr/es/servicios/estadisticas-de-psa/>. Accessed: Aug. 12, 2020.
- Forest Carbon Partnership. 2013. REDD Readiness Progress Factsheet. https://www.forestcarbonpartnership.org/system/files/documents/Costa_Rica_FCPF_REDD_Readiness_Progress_Sheet_June_2013_final%20-%20CLEAN.pdf. Accessed: Aug. 10, 2020.
- Gonzalez Chaverri, P., C. Porras Salazar, and L.A. Aguilar Salas. 1998. La compra de Madera por adelantado: una nueva vision aplicada por Fundecor San Jose, Costa Rica: Fundecor. <http://www.fundecortechnology.org/fundecor/Publicaciones/Publicaciones.html>. Accessed on September 5, 2011.
- Government of Costa Rica. 2010. REDD Readiness Proposal.
- Guess, G. M. (1979). Pasture expansion, forestry, and development contradictions: The case of Costa Rica. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 14(1), 42-55.
- Lansing, D. M. (2013). Understanding linkages between ecosystem service payments, forest plantations, and export agriculture. *Geoforum*, 47, 103-112.
- Lansing, D. M. (2014). Unequal access to payments for ecosystem services: The case of Costa Rica. *Development and Change*, 45(6), 1310-1331.
- Lansing, D. M., Grove, K., & Rice, J. L. (2015). The neutral state: a genealogy of ecosystem service payments in Costa Rica. *Conservation and Society*, 13(2), 200-211.
- Lansing, D. M. (2017). Understanding smallholder participation in payments for ecosystem services: the case of Costa Rica. *Human Ecology*, 45(1), 77-87.
- Legrand, T., Froger, G., & Le Coq, J. F. (2010). The efficiency of the Costa Rican payment for environmental services program under discussion.

- Locatelli, B., Rojas, V., & Salinas, Z. (2008). Impacts of payments for environmental services on local development in northern Costa Rica: a fuzzy multi-criteria analysis. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 10(5), 275-285.
- Matulis, B. S. (2013). The narrowing gap between vision and execution: Neoliberalization of PES in Costa Rica. *Geoforum*, 44, 253-260.
- Matulis, B. S. (2017). Persistent neoliberalisation in PES: Taxes, tariffs, and the World Bank in Costa Rica. *Conservation and Society*, 15(2), 147-156.
- Matulis, B. S. (2016). The coercive laws of competition in a neoliberal era: the case of forestry in Costa Rica. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 23(1), 279-295.
- MINAET. (2012). "Establecen cantidad de hectareas a contratar en el pago por servicios ambientales 2012". La Gaceta No. 36935-MINAET.
- Morse, W. C., Schedlbauer, J. L., Sesnie, S. E., Finegan, B., Harvey, C. A., Hollenhorst, S. J., Kavanagh, K. L., Stoian, D. and Wulfhorst, J. D. (2009), 'Consequences of environmental service payments for forest retention and recruitment in a Costa Rican biological corridor', *Ecology and Society*, 14 (1): 23
- Obando, G. 1998. El uso de computadoras, programmas e instrumentos electronicos en la planificacion del manejo del bosque humedo tropical en Costa Rica Fundecor, San José, Costa Rica. <http://www.fundecor.org/inf-tecnica/documentos>. Accessed on June 5, 2010.
- Pfaff, A., Robalino, J. A., & Sanchez-Azofeifa, G. A. (2008). Payments for environmental services: empirical analysis for Costa Rica. Terry Sanford Institute of Public Policy, Duke University, Durham, NC, USA, 404-424.
- Porras, I. (2010). Fair and green?: social impacts of payments for environmental services in Costa Rica (No. 12). IIED.
- Porras, I., Barton, D. N., Miranda, M., & Chacón-Cascante, A. (2017). *Learning from 20 years of payments for ecosystem services in Costa Rica*. International Institute for Environment and Development.
- Robalino, J., & Pfaff, A. (2013). Ecopayments and deforestation in Costa Rica: A nationwide analysis of PSA's initial years. *Land Economics*, 89(3), 432-448.
- Sader, S. A., & Joyce, A. T. (1988). Deforestation rates and trends in Costa Rica, 1940 to 1983. *Biotropica*, 11-19.
- Sanchez-Azofeifa, G. A., Pfaff, A., Robalino, J. A., & Boomhower, J. P. (2007). Costa Rica's payment for environmental services program: intention, implementation, and impact. *Conservation biology*, 21(5), 1165-1173.

- Schwartz, G. J. (2017). The role of women in payment for environmental services programs in Osa, Costa Rica. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 24(6), 890-910.
- Seligson, M. A. (1980). Peasants of Costa Rica and the development of agrarian capitalism. University of Wisconsin Press.
- Sierra, R., & Russman, E. (2006). On the efficiency of environmental service payments: a forest conservation assessment in the Osa Peninsula, Costa Rica. *Ecological economics*, 59(1), 131-141.
- Silva, E. (1997). The politics of sustainable development: native forest policy in Chile, Venezuela, Costa Rica and Mexico. *Journal of Latin American Studies*, 457-493.
- Vunderink, G. L. (1990). Peasant participation and mobilization during economic crisis: the case of Costa Rica. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 25(4), 3-34.
- Wunder, S. (2007). The efficiency of payments for environmental services in tropical conservation. *Conservation biology*, 21(1), 48-58.
- Zbinden, S., & Lee, D. R. (2005). Paying for environmental services: an analysis of participation in Costa Rica's PSA program. *World development*, 33(2), 255-272.

Mexico, National PES and related programs.

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1) Background and context:

This topic gives an introduction to the program and briefly outlines the contextual factors most relevant to the case study. Recognizing that this cannot be comprehensive, this is a space to outline the necessary background information that may be essential to understanding the case. These factors may also be brought up later in response to specific questions. Factors to consider include:

- a) Brief description of the program (for introductory purposes):
 - i) Geographical extent, ecosystem services (ES) rewarded, approximate level of participation, type of compensation.
 - ii) Relevant global standards/programs/certifications (e.g. REDD+, carbon or ecosystem service certifications, etc.)

This analysis will focus on a series of large-scale PES programs led by the Mexican federal government that were first implemented in 2003. While there are a wide variety of sub-national and even smaller scale PES initiatives throughout Mexico, we focus on these federal programs in order to be able to say something coherent and holistic about the ways in which values and value propositions influenced design, implementation and outcomes. These national PES programs are under the control of the Comisión Nacional Forestal (CONAFOR), the federal agency responsible for supporting, monitoring and creating and enforcing forest-related policy in Mexico. Due to the focus and mandate of this agency, these programs have almost exclusively enrolled forested lands and “presence of forest cover” is used almost exclusively as the metric of production of ecosystem services. There are four primary strands of federal government-funded programs, each with distinct objectives and structure:

National PES Programs

This program, and its many iterations, was first implemented in 2003 and has gone by various acronyms: PSA-H, PSA-CABSA, Pro-Arbol, PRONAFOR. While the focus has always been on avoided deforestation as a proxy for the production of ecosystem services (ES), the ES targeted has changed overtime: hydrological services (the sole focus when the project began and always the largest portion of funding and contracts), biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration and the introduction of new or improvement of existing agroforestry systems. The funding for this program is entirely federal and, for that and other reasons, has been critiqued by some as being one in a long line of rural subsidies (Shapiro-Garza 2020) (see further discussion below).

Special Program for REDD+ Readiness

These programs were first implemented in 2006 and supported the development of the policy, technological and other infrastructure necessary to implement REDD+ as well as a number of subnational

proto-type initiatives. Our analysis deliberately excludes these initiatives, primarily given that they have been relatively small in terms of funding and little researched.

Local Mechanisms for Payments for Ecosystem Services through Matching Funds

This program was first implemented in 2008. Contracts are with intermediary organizations (e.g. NGOs, state governments, water utilities, etc.), are of variable length, with CONAFOR providing only half of the funding for payments which is matched by the organization or another funder. At its start, this program had the dual intention of allowing PES to be adapted to local conditions and contexts and supporting the development of the institutional arrangements and other systems to create direct, market-like PES arrangements between upstream providers of ES and downstream users.

Biodiversity Heritage Fund

This program was started in 2010 with funding from the Global Environment Facility and is relatively small compared to the first two programs. It targets landowners in areas with identified biodiversity of global importance to enact conservation-friendly management practices. Contracts are direct with landowners and are to be paid in perpetuity.

Between 2003-2016 these four programs enrolled 6,510,428 ha, which represents approximately 9.5 percent of forested lands in Mexico (Zamora Martínez, 2016), belonging to 11,114 rural communities and small landholders. In 2018, the programs collectively had 2.55 million hectares of forest land enrolled (CONAFOR 2018).

- b) Contextual factors:
 - i) Biophysical conditions
 - ii) Socio-economic conditions
 - (1) Land tenure
 - (2) Land inequities
 - (3) Structural inequalities and legacies of colonization, disenfranchisement, etc.
 - iii) Political conditions
 - (1) Governance context (relevant institutional framework and policy context, including related policy and legislation)
 - iv) Power relations and political influence among stakeholders

Description of biophysical context of Mexico and perhaps the land preferentially enrolled in PES?

Encompassing a broad range of ecotypes, Mexico is considered a “megadiverse” country, accounting for 12% of the world’s biodiversity (CONABIO 2008; Valdez et al., 2006). About 30% of the country’s area has forest cover, with approximately 55% of forests held communally in what are collectively referred to as *nucleo agrarios* (FAO 2015, Klooster and Masera 2000, Barnes, 2009; Madrid et al. 2009; FAO 2015). Because of the preponderance of communal ownership of forests, and based on preferential targeting of

the program to communal land tenure, low socioeconomic status, and level of indigenous populations, the majority of the land enrolled in these programs is communally held.

Certain portions of the PES funds are designated for the costs associated with implementing the forest management plan and participants are required to submit contractor to support that implementation whose services are paid for by CONAFOR, but decisions about how to distribute the rest of the funds are left to the communities. Various studies have documented those decisions, demonstrating that the majority decide to distribute some portion to community members and the rest to projects of communal benefit (e.g. school or road construction, community celebrations, etc.). Numerous cases studies have demonstrated that, in communities with pre-existing structural inequalities and conflict, enrollment in one of these PES programs can exacerbate intra-community tensions and often lead to decisions to exclude people who live within the community, but who do not have official land or voting rights, from these direct payments (Almeida-Leñero et al. 2017; Corbera et al. 2020).

Governance in Mexico is highly centralized, so, as with most government policies, the design and general oversight of the CONAFOR programs has been top down, although some program modifications have originated through suggestions by state offices or even project intermediary organizations. However, given that monitoring by CONAFOR of outcomes is fairly light (e.g. annual visits to ensure that promised management activities are completed, remote sensing monitoring of forest cover) project intermediaries and participants in the end have quite a strong influence on the ways in which the program is implemented on the ground (Shapiro-Garza 2013; Izquierdo-Tort et al. in progress b).

From its inception the program has been primarily funded through direct allocations by the Mexican congress, aside from two, relatively small loans from the World Bank and a grant from the Global Environment Facility (McAfee and Shapiro 2010). This has meant the program has been relatively insulated from the pressure to conform to external models imposed on other large-scale PES programs by lenders, grantors, etc., but instead has been very susceptible to the national-level politics and political shifts in Mexico.

2) Problematization and framing (defining the problem):

This topic aims to cover the process of defining the environmental problem that the PES program was intended to address. We want to identify how the program was initially designed, while the following topic on Value Articulation will provide the opportunity to describe how this changed over time. We recognize that there may be research gaps in these early stages for many programs.

- a) How was the environmental problem defined? Who was empowered in/excluded from this decision?
- b) How was PES chosen as the solution? Who was empowered in/excluded from this decision?
- c) What ecosystem services (ES) were prioritized in the initial design? Who was identified as beneficiaries and potential providers of ES, and how?

The values that have shaped the design of the national PES programs in Mexico have much to do with who was allowed to participate at various points in the evolution of this highly centralized program, which was in turn mediated by the national-level political trends and shifts in political power (Shapiro-Garza 2020). However, it is also important to recognize that the degree to which policy maker's "values" could influence policy design was tempered by the limitations imposed by the grounded institutional, legal and other pragmatic conditions in Mexico (Shapiro-Garza 2013a). To note, while the rural landowners who were the direct targets and recipients of the PES programs have not been actively consulted or included in the design processes by the central offices of CONAFOR, as is noted in section 4, participants have quite a bit of discretion to express their values into project implementation based on the design feature that allows them to choose from a list the suite of forest management activities they want to engage it to "produce" ecosystem services and to decide how they would like to distribute the largest portion of program payments, combined with fairly minimal oversight and monitoring by CONAFOR.

The original national PES program in Mexico was proposed and designed by a group of economists from the World Bank and a Mexican environmental think tank, then called the Instituto Nacional de Ecología (Muñoz-Piña et al. 2008). These economists were primarily responsible for both proposing PES as a solution and for creating the basic policy infrastructure (Ibid). They chose to focus the initial phases of the program on hydrological ecosystem services, both because of the extreme issues of water scarcity in many parts of the country and because, they state, that there is a strong acceptance in Mexico of the belief that more forest cover results in more water downstream. Responsibility for program design and implementation was turned over to CONAFOR in the early days of the program. That the program has been managed by the forestry service of Mexico has meant that the focus has stayed squarely on conservation of forest-based ecosystems.

The economists who designed the program continued to exert pressures to reimpose the original logics of the economic model of PES, prioritizing what they claimed were the greater efficiencies and effectiveness of market or market-like mechanisms, tying payment rates to market demand and targeting based on supply and demand, in incentivizing the production of ecosystem services (Shapiro-Garza 2020). Even so, due to political pressure to have these programs align with rural federal policy and politics, these early iterations included significant design elements (e.g. targeting, program rules, etc.) intended to promote the dual goals of ecosystem services production and poverty alleviation (McAfee and Shapiro 2010). The newly formed national PES program faced almost immediate contestation, by rural social movements, public intellectuals and environmentalists who disagreed with both the objectives and the structure of the new program (Shapiro-Garza 2013b). We have detailed in the following section some of the primary conceptual tensions related to "values" and how they were manifest in various policy decisions. These tensions played out as the actors and entities with alternative perspectives were either outside or inside the policy design process: street protests, participation in design or oversight committees, leaders of NGOs and think tanks or the director of the PES program for CONAFOR.

3) Values and value articulation

This topic digs more deeply into how values are articulated by various actors throughout the process of PES design and implementation, through environmental valuation methods like multi-criteria analysis (MCA), spatial targeting or ecosystem modeling, or political strategies like referenda, petitions, or protest or sabotage, and what kinds of values were articulated through these processes. We aim to cast a wide net to include strategies that were included in program design as well as those used by actors to contest design or implementation later on. The range of methods/strategies that are relevant here will depend on the case.

- a) What value articulation method(s) was/were used in the initial design process (e.g. MCA, ecosystem modeling/targeting, referenda, focus groups, etc.)? How was spatial targeting and prioritization done? How were upstream participants/ES 'providers' targeted?
 - i) How and by whom were these methods chosen?
 - ii) Who was involved? What roles did they play?
- b) How and why did some values become influential over others in program design and/or implementation?
 - i) What values were reflected/excluded in the design process? What forms of knowledge? What worldviews?
 - ii) Whose values were reflected/excluded? Whose knowledge? Whose worldviews?
 - iii) Was this process contested? If so how? (E.g. other strategies by which marginalized values might be expressed – protest, counter-organizing, sabotage).
- c) Were trade-offs made among multiple objectives, and if so how and by whom?

There were three primary mechanisms within the design of the program in which the values of the policy makers, and the value tensions that existed among them, were manifest:

Payment rates

The setting of payment rates is one obvious area where the values of policy makers, and of the politicians who also set the agenda, are clearly at play. When the national PES program was first implemented in 2003, payment rates were calculated based on the average value from analysis of data in a national study of the opportunity costs of converting forestlands to corn fields (Alix-Garcia et al. 2008) and were set as a standard amount/hectare/year. The intent of this study, to increase the efficiency of these government payments by precisely tailoring payments to just enough over the opportunity costs of conversion in each sub-region to convince landowners to choose forest conservation, was diluted by the aggregation of national data and the setting of standardized, national payment rates (Muñoz-Piña et al. 2008).

From the first implementation of the program, the adherents to the economic model of PES at the Instituto Nacional de Ecología and the World Bank continued to push for increased alignment with market principles. Of particular focus was on differentiating payment rates based on the ability of various ecotypes to “produce” ecosystem services. These measures have been adopted at various stages and degrees throughout the life of these programs. An even more significant change was the formation of the above-mentioned Local Mechanisms for Payments for Ecosystem Services through Matching Funds (Matching Funds) program. The program attempted to create more market-like PES arrangements, with

direct connections between local buyers and local sellers. Although partially funded and regulated through CONAFOR, the program allows intermediary organizations to partially negotiate payment rates and contract terms.

Contract rules regarding strict conservation versus sustainable management and use

Similar to disagreements in global environmental discourse, there has been a consistent tension in the Mexican national PES programs between those who believe that forests can only be producers of ecosystem services through strict conservation versus those who believe that forests, especially those facing environmental and human threats, will only be conserved if they are protected by the people living in them and are allowed to be sustainably managed in support of their cultural reproduction (Shapiro-Garza 2020). In Mexico, and other countries in Latin America, those who hold the latter view refer to PES-like arrangements as “compensation for ecosystem services” (CES) (Rosa et al. 2003). This is based on the meaning of *compensación* in Spanish, which refers to a complex social interaction and recognition of a valuable service rendered, such as serving as sustainable stewards of an ecosystem, versus *pagos*, which refer to purely economic transactions (Shapiro-Garza 2020).

The tension between these viewpoints has manifested through a number of policy disagreements and changes over the lifetime of the program. In the original program design, program contracts specified that no management activities would be allowed in enrolled forest. Detractors argued that providing payments without expectation of management was paternalistic and would lead to the disempowerment of forest communities (Merino-Pérez et al. 2005). They also argued that allowing for sustainable management and use was not only necessary for the cultural reproduction of rural communities, but that these forests, under threat of deforestation, pest and diseases, fires, etc., require active protection and management in order to continue to produce ecosystem services (Ibid). This was the perspective that rural social movement leaders brought to the table when, as the result of massive street protests, they won the right to negotiate over a suite of rural-facing federal policies (Shapiro-Garza 2013b). The result was a second PES program, PSA-CABSA, that included payments for carbon sequestration and biodiversity conservation, but also for actively managed, productive agroforestry systems (McAfee and Shapiro 2010). In 2006, a new president was elected in Mexico and he appointed a number of proponents of the CES model to lead the national PES programs from within CONAFOR. These administrators introduced a number of changes, including the addition of rules in 2006 requiring participants to develop as part of their contract with CONAFOR a Program of Best Management Practices, selecting management activities from a menu those options best suited to their capacities and their desires for their forests. Later iterations of the program have also introduced requirements that a certain percentage of total payments received be reinvested in management activities (as of 2015) and in projects related to sustainable use and income generation of enrolled forests (as of 2017).

Targeting

There has been a consistent tension in the design and implementation of the Mexican federal PES programs between promoting forest conservation versus also employing these policies and sources of

funding as a tool for poverty alleviation. Nowhere is this tension more apparent than in the rules and criteria governing the targeting of the programs. Over time, the targeting rules and priorities have influenced by shifts in national policy priorities and were used to build political capital for those in power.

For the initial program, focused on production of hydrological services, CONFOR identified “eligible zones” based on location in overexploited watersheds and upstream from urban centers, as an indication of “demand” (Sims et al. 2014). Participant selection, which early in the program evolution has been regulated a system that assigned a certain number of points based on various characteristics of the applicant, has also been influenced by shifting priorities. As the programs evolved, there have been a number of criteria introduced, promoted by the original economists who had designed the program, to define eligible zones or select participants in those zone intended to increase the probability that true markets for ecosystem services would form: that the applicant has a pending contract with a buyer or is in a watershed with an existing local PES initiative (Ibid). Along with conservationists in Mexico, they also promoted criteria though to increase the “environmental effectiveness” of the program, including targeting based on risk of deforestation, and the “quality” of the forest for biodiversity conservation and/or the specific ecosystem service. At the same time, selection criteria intended to target the program to marginalized groups, such as areas with majority indigenous population or with a high degree of “marginality” (a designation of the Mexican state) or to female landowners, were also introduced (Ibid). One of the most controversial of the targeting rules, first introduced in 2006, was to give preference to landowners located within protected areas (Ibid). Intended as a means to provide compensation for the limitations imposed on landowners with the introduction of protected areas limitations, this targeting criteria has been highly contested by proponents of both market-oriented PES and of conservationists, claiming that since the forest is already conserved, enrolling these landowners provides no additionality (Shapiro-Garza 2020).

4. Distribution of costs and benefits:

a) Benefits:

- i) Compensation/payments:
 - (1) What kind of compensation is used (in-kind vs. monetary)?
 - (2) How and to whom are benefits distributed (e.g. individual versus communal)
 - (3) How were distribution decisions made (who was involved, what was the nature of their participation)? This may reference material above.
 - (4) Do participants perceive distribution and compensation as just? Why or why not? Were distribution decisions contested, and if so how?
 - (5) What do participants perceive as benefits of the program (i.e. other motivations that might not be represented in compensation; this may include ecological benefits)?

b) Distribution of costs

- i) Whose conduct is impacted by the program? Whose conduct is defined as problematic?

- ii) What land-use or other changes were required of participants? How are these changes enforced (conditionality)?
- iii) How are the costs of participation measured/accounted for (e.g. monetary) iv) What did participants perceive as costs of participation (might show mismatch between compensation and motivations)?

Eligibility to the program is defined by spatial targeting based on a combination of environmental and social criteria which are established by CONAFOR with limited or no input from participants (see Section 3 above). Compensation is entirely monetary and benefits are disbursed directly to participants on a per hectare basis and to technical advisors with tiered payment levels depending on the amount of land surface enrolled. Technical advisors are chosen by participants but are paid for by CONAFOR.

The majority of program contracts involve ejidos and indigenous communities but participants also include landholder groups and individuals. Research shows that payments are distributed internally within communities in combinations of individual cash disbursements for landholders and collective set-asides for services and activities, such as public infrastructure (e.g. schools and clinics) or program management costs (Corbera et al. 2007; García-Amado et al. 2011; Izquierdo-Tort 2020; Izquierdo-Tort & Corbera in progress). Therefore, though by design the program's distributive criterion is primarily based on merit because payments are awarded on a per hectare basis to compensate for the opportunity costs of participation, payment distributions within participating communities reflect local equity and need concerns.

Landholders who receive payments generally perceive distribution and compensation as a just reward or compensation for present and past conservation practices, though concerns have been raised about payment levels being too low to compensate for either opportunity costs (Izquierdo-Tort et al. 2019) or the transaction costs incurred by participants (Alix-Garcia et al. 2012). However, research also shows that payment distributions can be contested within communities, particularly by landless groups who are excluded from participation (Corbera et al. 2020, García-Amado et al. 2011, Izquierdo-Tort & Corbera in progress). Besides receiving payments, there is evidence that participation is associated and/or motivated by other types of economic and non-economic factors (See Section 5).

The program targets holders of forest land surfaces whose activities are associated with deforestation and forest degradation. The main requirement for participation is maintaining forest cover on enrolled surfaces but the program also includes other resource management activities, such as developing firebreaks and patrolling. Conditionality is monitored through a combination of field visits and remote sensing. By program rules, non-compliance implies forced withdrawal and the requirement for participants to reimburse all previously received payments. In practice, however, non-compliance is enforced less strictly. Research shows that CONAFOR enforces conditionality by either removing parcels where forest loss has been detected or by requesting non-compliant landholders to compensate forest loss by enrolling additional surfaces (Izquierdo-Tort et al. 2019).

As described in section 3, the program includes a fixed-price payment per hectare, which over time has been differentiated by the specific ES targeted and deforestation risk (e.g. Muñoz Piña et al. 2008). The

payment level is set based on loose calculations of opportunity costs of participation and ES value, as well as available funding. The program has monitored neither monetary nor non-monetary costs of participation. However, research shows that participation imposes local costs, including: prohibition of agricultural activities on enrolled lands, limited access to timber and non-timber resources commercial and household use (Izquierdo-Tort et al. 2019). Though most participants voluntarily accept these costs as a direct implication of program enrolment, costs are also borne by landless groups in participating communities (Corbera et al. 2009).

5. Outcomes

This topic examines what has been documented in program monitoring and relevant literature on social and ecological outcomes. The volume of evidence available for each case will vary considerably, and there will likely be discrepancies between outcomes at different scales (e.g. local project-level outcomes vs. national program outcomes).

a) Social outcomes (based on program monitoring, where available, and subsequent studies)

- i) Does the program have specific social impact goals? Is there monitoring for these, and how?
- ii) What social impacts have been documented (through program monitoring and in wider literature)?
 - (1) What methods/proxies were used, and at what spatial and temporal scales?
 - (2) What was the direction or magnitude of change?
 - (3) What are participants' perceptions of the program's social impacts?

b) Ecological impacts (based on program monitoring, where available, and subsequent studies)

- i) What ecological outcomes are prioritized, for what beneficiaries, and how are these monitored?
- ii) What changes in ES or other impacts have been documented (in program monitoring and wider literature)? What monitoring protocols were implemented?
 - (1) What methods/proxies were used, and at what spatial and temporal scales?
- iii) How do upstream participants and/or downstream stakeholders perceive ecological impacts? (Might show disconnect between ES monitored and impacts of interest to participants or other stakeholders).

c) Participation:

- i) (How) have participation levels and longevity been assessed? What is the extent of participation in the areas covered by the program?
- ii) What evidence exists in the literature regarding the main factors influencing participation (e.g. non-monetary motivations, barriers, availability of alternative labor markets or livelihood options, etc.)? This may overlap with material above.

d) Other outcomes and research gaps

- i) Effects on land tenure?
- ii) Off-site impacts/leakage?
 - (1) Is there evidence of off-site or indirect social or environmental impacts, including e.g. impacts on other labor markets, social cohesion, cultural practices, or broader environmental impacts due to intensification of agriculture or land conversion elsewhere?
- iv) Is there evidence of 'value crowding,' positive or negative?

Mixed

The program has been considered pro-poor because it targets participants using not only on ecological but also social criteria (Ezzine-de-Blas et al. 2016, Muñoz Piña et al. 2008). These include the targeting of areas based on calculations of ES value and deforestation risk, and of communities with high levels of marginalization and indigenous populations. The program outcomes monitored, nonetheless, are exclusively ecological. The main outcome is forest cover on enrolled surfaces but the program also monitors required resource management activities, such as developing firebreaks and patrolling. Monitoring involves a combination of field visits and remote sensing.

Research on social and ecological outcomes includes national, regional, and local-level analyses. Nationwide counterfactual impact assessments show that the program has significantly reduced deforestation (Alix-Garcia et al. 2012, 2015; Sims et al. 2017), reduced forest fragmentation (Ramirez-Reyes et al. 2018), and increased land cover management practices (e.g. patrolling illegal activities, building firebreaks) (Alix-Garcia et al. 2018). However, analyses also show that the program has had moderate economic impacts (e.g. consumption, investment and poverty reduction) (Alix-Garcia et al. 2015; Sims et al. 2017) and has displaced deforestation (leakage) (Alix-Garcia et al. 2012). Nationwide studies so far have mostly examined short-term outcomes and have used forest cover as a proxy for ES provision.

In turn, studies at the regional and local level provide contrasting results in program impacts, particularly regarding social outcomes. Studies of ecological impacts include counterfactual impact assessments (e.g. Costedoat et al. 2015, Le Velly et al. 2017), mixed-methods approaches (e.g. Garcia-Amado et al. 2011, Izquierdo-Tort et al. 2019, Scullion et al. 2011), and qualitative perception-based analyses (e.g. Rodriguez-Robayo et al. 2019). Overall, these studies document positive ecological outcomes but with significant regional variations. For instance, Costedoat et al. (2015) document high program impact on avoided deforestation in Chiapas despite evidence of lack of compliance; in turn, Le Velly et al. (2017) document low avoided deforestation in Yucatán and also found evidence of leakage and lack of permanence when contracts ended. More research is needed but variations in program impact seem to reflect contextual differences in pressures for land conversion, with programs being more effective on sites with higher deforestation rates. Also, despite a few exceptions (e.g. Mokondoko et al. 2016), studies so far have used forest cover as a proxy for ES provision.

Studies of program social impacts have been mostly based on qualitative or mixed-methods and have focused on poverty and equity. Documented impacts on poverty reduction have been positive but generally low (Arriagada et al. 2018, Scullion et al. 2011) but there are exceptions where impacts on income have been positive and significant (Izquierdo-Tort 2020). Studies focused on equity outcomes document negative effects and of participation triggering social conflict, which often have to do with more powerful or wealthier social groups having better access to program benefits and information, as well as vulnerable groups bearing some of the costs of participation (Corbera et al. 2007, 2020; Garcia-Amado et al. 2011; Jones et al. 2018). However, other case studies show that program participation has helped improve social organisation and relations through the allocation of program benefits on collective goods and services, and the improvement of forest conservation and resource management practices and agreements (Almeida-Leñero et al. 2017, Izquierdo-Tort 2020, Izquierdo-Tort & Corbera in progress, Izquierdo-Tort et al. in progress b). Overall, outcome variations across contexts seem to depend on a combination of factors to do with exogenous conditions (e.g. influence of markets and urban centres, economic history), actors' attributes (e.g. livelihoods, income, motivations), and local governance features (e.g. land tenure, rules for management and use, existence of local intermediaries) (Rodriguez-Robayo et al. 2019).

From the beginning, interest in participation has greatly exceeded program funding and thus rejection rates have always been high (Munoz et al. 2008). Research shows participation is motivated primarily by receiving a payment, which is often driven by low opportunity costs or lack of resources for forest conversion (Rico Garcia Amado et al. 2013, Izquierdo-Tort et al. 2019). Yet, other monetary and non-monetary factors have driven interest in program involvement, especially in the context of communities, including: improved income stability and financial planning within the household (Izquierdo-Tort 2020); pre-existing interests in forest conservation and access to training (Figueroa et al. 2016); personal attributes, such as age and gender (Mendez-Lopez et al. 2018); prosocial motivations, such as the existence of community sanctions and land governance (Jones et al. 2019); design and implementation factors, such as specific rule features and communication with intermediaries (Kosoy et al. 2008).

Despite these advances, there is still scant information to do with how the program impacts actual ES provision beyond forest cover (see e.g. Mokondoko et al. 2016), how PES interacts with other environmental and non-environmental policies (see e.g. Ezzine-de-Blas et al. 2016, Izquierdo-Tort 2020), whether participation crowds-in or crowds-out intrinsic conservation motivations (see e.g. Arriagada et al. 2018), and how program design changes and how participants adapt to such change over the long-term (see e.g. Izquierdo-Tort et al. in progress b), and whether program impacts are maintained when contracts end (Le Velly et al. 2017). Also, due to the difficulties of conducting research in some regions of Mexico because of the presence of illegal activities and violence related to the drug trade and illegal logging there is little data from the Central and North areas and some other states.

6. Methodology and literature

a) Please describe, in a few words/lines, your method of literature search (e.g. expert judgment, snowball, systematic, etc.).

b) Please provide any search criteria, search terms used, or databases consulted.

c) Have you included gray literature? If so, please provide any relevant details on how you located it.

The literature search was conducted as part of a systematic review of the existing literature on the National PES programs of Mexico developed by Izquierdo-Tort (in progress a). The systematic review process first consisted of online searches of peer-reviewed publications with keywords related to PES programs in Mexico in English and Spanish in several internationally recognized databases as suggested by previous PES reviews (e.g. Calvet-Mir et al., 2015; Ezzine de Blas et al., 2016; Salzman et al., 2018; Sattler and Matzdorf, 2013; Schomers and Matzdorf, 2013) and other related literature reviews (e.g. Martinez-Harms et al., 2015; Perevochtchikova et al., 2019; Sattler et al., 2018). Specifically, searches were conducted in three internationally recognized databases:

Scopus: international database of peer-reviewed academic publications worldwide;

Scielo: international database of peer-reviewed academic publications, mainly from Latin America, Ibero-America, and South Africa;

Redalyc: international database of peer-reviewed academic publications from Latin America, Caribbean, Spain, and Portugal.

Additionally, given specific interest in PES literature based in Mexico, Izquierdo-Tort et al. (in progress a) also conducted online searches of publications on nationally recognized Mexican journals. The analysis focused on peer-reviewed journals with indexation by Mexico's Science and Technology Journal Classification System (CRMCYT) as of May 2020. From a list of 94 CRMCYT indexed journals from 7 thematic areas, some were first filtered based on relevance of thematic area (57 journals from 5 thematic areas), and others were subsequently filtered based on relevance of journal title (21 journals). From a list of 21 relevant journals from Mexico, 15 were excluded as they already appeared in Scopus, Scielo and Redalyc. Thus, additional searches were conducted in 6 individual Mexican journals:

Botanical Sciences; Estudios Sociológicos de El Colegio de México; Norteamérica; Política y Gobierno; Revista Chapingo Serie Ciencias Forestales y del Ambiente; Tropical and Subtropical Agroecosystems

From these sources, search elements related to PES in Mexico were sought specifically in the title, abstract and keywords for Scopus and Scielo, and in the full text of the publications for Redalyc and the 6 individual Mexican journals described below. The syntax used included a wide array of combinations of the following terms:

Mexico/Mexican AND payment/programme/scheme + ecosystem/environmental/hydrological/biodiversity/carbon service.

In total, 757 records were obtained and downloaded in a single Excel spreadsheet on the 5th of May 2020 (139 from Scopus, 28 from Scielo, 496 from Redalyc, 94 from relevant Mexican journals). Duplicate records (117) were identified and thus the final publication database included a total 640 different records (Fig 1).

The following step consisted of identifying the set of records related to PES programmes in Mexico from the publication database, and thus relevant for analysis. Therefore, each record was coded according to two dimensions:

PES focus: publication related to actual existing PES programmes and/or provides insights related to their application;

Mexico focus: publication based entirely or partially in Mexico.

For each dimension, the coding process consisted of two main steps: 1) search for keywords in the title related to PES or Mexico; 2) reading of abstract to confirm PES or Mexico focus. Whenever the publication's classification was unclear after steps 1) and 2), the body of the publication was further scanned. This codification was developed by the main author of the study (Izquierdo-Tort) but was validated by the team of coauthors to ensure its accuracy.

Once all records were coded, only those publications that combined a focus on PES and Mexico were selected for analysis. In total, 119 articles met this requirement and formed the empirical basis for analysis.

Figure 1. Methodology and search criteria based on PRISMA guidelines. The inclusion criteria are: PES = related to existing PES programmes and/or provides insights related to their application, MEXICO = based entirely or partially in Mexico. Notes: 1) searches in Redalyc and relevant Mexican journals indexed under CRMCYT include results for keyword searches in all data fields (i.e. document full text) because the search engines do not include options for refining search criteria (e.g. to title, abstract and keywords). Source: Izquierdo-Tort et al. (in progress a). Figure retrieved with permission by the authors.

Besides these above-mentioned peer-reviewed publications, we included some of CONAFOR's yearly reports, a few external reports by Mexican scholars assessing program outcomes and non-peer reviewed books on this topic. We have also included some references that we will cite in providing context (e.g. status of land tenure in Mexico, forest cover, etc.).

References

- Barnes, G. 2009. The evolution and resilience of community-based land tenure in rural Mexico. *Land Use Policy* 26, 393–400.
- CONABIO 2008. *Capital natural de México, vol. I : Conocimiento actual de la biodiversidad*. Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad, México.
- CONAFOR. (2018). Programa Institucional de la Comisión Nacional Forestal 2014-2018. Avance y Resultados 2018. Comisión Nacional Forestal (CONAFOR). https://www.conafor.gob.mx/transparencia/docs/Avances_y_Resultados_2018_PIC.PDF
- Calvet-Mir, L., Corbera, E., Martin, A., Fisher, J., & Gross-Camp, N. (2015). Payments for ecosystem services in the tropics: A closer look at effectiveness and equity. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 14, 150–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.06.001>
- Ezzine de Blas, D., J. Le Coq and A. Guevara Sangines (eds.) (2017), *Los pagos por servicios ambientales en America Latina: gobernanza, impactos y perspectivas*, Mexico City, Universidad Iberoamericana (IBERO).
- Ezzine-de-Blas, D., Wunder, S., Ruiz-Pérez, M., & Moreno-Sanchez, R. del P. (2016). Global Patterns in the Implementation of Payments for Environmental Services. *PLOS ONE*, 11(3), e0149847. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0149847>
- FAO. 2015. *Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015*. Rome, Italy: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).
- Izquierdo-Tort, S., Corbera, E. (in progress). Multiple fairness principles influence benefit distribution in conservation payments: evidence from Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) in Selva Lacandona, Mexico.
- Izquierdo-Tort, S., Corbera, E., Shapiro-Garza, E., Borgomeo, E., Carabias Lillo, J., Dupras, J., Kolinjivadi, V., Nuñez, J.M., Perevochtchikova, M., Rodriguez, L.A., Rodriguez-Robayo, K.J.,
- Izquierdo-Tort, S., Corbera, E., Barceinas-Cruz, A., Carabias Lillo, J., Castro-Tovar, E., Naime, J., Ortiz Rosas, F., Rubio, N., Torres-Knoop, L., Vázquez-Cisneros, P.A., Dupras, J. (in progress b). Collective adaptations: long-term participation in payments for ecosystem services in Chiapas, Mexico.

- Klooster, D., Masera, O. 2000. Community forest management in Mexico: carbon mitigation and biodiversity conservation through rural development. *Glob. Environ. Change* 10, 259–272.
- Madrid, L., Núñez, J.M., Quiroz, G., Rodríguez, Y. 2009. Propiedad social forestal Mexico. *Investigaciones Ambientales* 1, 179–196.
- Martinez-Harms, M. J., Bryan, B. A., Balvanera, P., Law, E. A., Rhodes, J. R., Possingham, H. P., & Wilson, K. A. (2015). Making decisions for managing ecosystem services. *Biological Conservation*, 184, 229–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2015.01.024>
- Merino-Pérez, L., J. Rodríguez, G. Oritz and A. García (2008) 'Estudio Estratégico sobre el Sector Forestal Mexicano' ['Strategic Study of the Mexican Forestry Sector']. Mexico City, DF: Universidad Autónoma de México.
- Merino Pérez, L. et al. (2005) 'El Programa de Pago por Servicios Ambientales Hidrológicos: Revisión Crítica y Propuestas de Modificación' ['The Programme for Payments for Hydrological Environmental Services: Critical Review and Proposals for Modification']. Mexico City, DF: Consejo Civil Mexicano para la Silvicultura Sostenible. www.ccmss.org.mx/acervo/
- [programa-pago-por-servicios-ambientales-hidrologicos-revision-critica-y-propuestas-demodificacion/](http://www.ccmss.org.mx/acervo/programa-pago-por-servicios-ambientales-hidrologicos-revision-critica-y-propuestas-demodificacion/) (accessed 9 September 2018).
- Perevochtchikova M. (coord.) 2014. Pago por servicios ambientales en México. Un acercamiento para su estudio. El Colegio de México, México. ISBN: 978-607-462-657-5.
- Perevochtchikova M. (ed.) (2016). ESTUDIO DE LOS EFECTOS DEL PROGRAMA DE PAGO POR SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES. EXPERIENCIA EN AJUSCO, MÉXICO. El Colegio de México, México. ISBN: 978-607-628-112-3.
- Perevochtchikova, M., De la Mora-De la Mora, G., Hernández Flores, J. Á., Marín, W., Langle Flores, A., Ramos Bueno, A., & Rojo Negrete, I. A. (2019). Systematic review of integrated studies on functional and thematic ecosystem services in Latin America, 1992–2017. *Ecosystem Services*, 36, 100900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100900>
- Rosa, H., S. Kandel, L. Dimas, N. Cúellar and E. Méndez (2003) 'Compensation for Environmental Services and Rural Communities: Lessons from the Americas and Key Issues for Strengthening Community Strategies'. San Salvador: Salvadoran Research Program on Development and Environment (PRISMA).
- Salzman, J., Bennett, G., Carroll, N., Goldstein, A., & Jenkins, M. (2018). The global status and trends of Payments for Ecosystem Services. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(3), 136–144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0033-0>

- Sattler, C., Loft, L., Mann, C., & Meyer, C. (2018). Methods in ecosystem services governance analysis: An introduction. *Ecosystem Services*, 34, 155–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.11.007>
- Sattler, C., Trampnau, S., Schomers, S., Meyer, C., & Matzdorf, B. (2013). Multi-classification of payments for ecosystem services: How do classification characteristics relate to overall PES success? *Ecosystem Services*, 6, 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.09.007>
- Schomers, S., & Matzdorf, B. (2013). Payments for ecosystem services: A review and comparison of developing and industrialized countries. *Ecosystem Services*, 6, 16–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.01.002>
- Sims, K.R.E., Van Hecken, G., Hidalgo-Garcia, L., Oropeza Calderon, D., Vazquez-Cisneros, P.A. (in progress a). How effective and equitable are Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) in Mexico? A review and meta-analysis.
- Valdez, R., Guzmán-Aranda, J.C., Abarca, F.J., Tarango-Arámbula, L.A., Sánchez, F.C. 2006. Wildlife Conservation and Management in Mexico. *Wildlife Society Bulletin (1973-2006)* 34, 270–282.
- Zamora Martínez, M.C. (2016) ‘Superficie Forestal Actual’ [Current Forest Cover]. *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Forestales* 7(35).

Reference list from systematic review by Izquierdo-Tort et al. (in progress)

- Aguilar-Gómez, C. R., Franco-Maass, S., & Arteaga-Reyes, T. T. (2018). Differentiated payments for environmental services schemes: A methodology proposal. *Journal of Mountain Science*, 15(8), 1693–1710. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11629-017-4800-6>
- Alix-Garcia, J., De Janvry, A., & Sadoulet, E. (2008). The role of deforestation risk and calibrated compensation in designing payments for environmental services. *Environment and Development Economics*, 13(3), 375–394. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355770X08004336>
- Alix-Garcia, J. M., Shapiro, E. N., & Sims, K. R. E. (2012). Forest Conservation and Slippage: Evidence from Mexico’s National Payments for Ecosystem Services Program. *Land Economics*, 88(4), 613–638. <https://doi.org/10.3368/le.88.4.613>
- Alix-Garcia, Jennifer M., Sims, K. R. E., Orozco-Olvera, V. H., Costica, L. E., Fernández Medina, J. D., & Romo Monroy, S. (2018). Payments for environmental services supported social capital while increasing land management. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(27), 7016–7021. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1720873115>
- Alix-Garcia, Jennifer M., Sims, K. R. E., & Phaneuf, D. J. (2019). Using referenda to improve targeting and decrease costs of conditional cash transfers. *Journal of Public Economics*, 176, 179–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2019.06.001>

- Alix-Garcia, Jennifer M., Sims, K. R. E., & Yañez-Pagans, P. (2015). Only One Tree from Each Seed? Environmental Effectiveness and Poverty Alleviation in Mexico's Payments for Ecosystem Services Program. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 7(4), 1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1257/pol.20130139>
- Almeida-Leñero, L., Revollo-Fernández, D., Caro-Borrero, A., Ruiz-Mallén, I., Corbera, E., Mazari-Hiriart, M., & Figueroa, F. (2017). Not the same for everyone: Community views of Mexico's payment for environmental services programmes. *Environmental Conservation*, 44(3), 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892916000564>
- Almendarez-Hernández, M. A., Jaramillo-Mosqueira, L. A., Avilés-Polanco, G., Beltrán-Morales, L. F., Hernández-Trejo, V., & Ortega-Rubio, A. (2013). Economic valuation of water in a natural protected area of an emerging economy: Recommendations for el Vizcaino Biosphere reserve, Mexico. *Interciencia*, 38(4), 245–252.
- Arriagada, R., Villaseñor, A., Rubiano, E., Cotacachi, D., & Morrison, J. (2018). Analysing the impacts of PES programmes beyond economic rationale: Perceptions of ecosystem services provision associated to the Mexican case. *Ecosystem Services*, 29, 116–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.12.007>
- Asbjornsen, H., Manson, R. H., Scullion, J. J., Holwerda, F., Muñoz-Villers, L. E., Alvarado-Barrientos, M. S., Geissert, D., Dawson, T. E., McDonnell, J. J., & Bruijnzeel, L. A. (2017). Interactions between payments for hydrologic services, landowner decisions, and ecohydrological consequences: Synergies and disconnection in the cloud forest zone of central Veracruz, Mexico. *Ecology and Society*, 22(2), art25. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-09144-220225>
- Balderas Torres, A., MacMillan, D. C., Skutsch, M., & Lovett, J. C. (2013). Payments for ecosystem services and rural development: Landowners' preferences and potential participation in western Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 6, 72–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.03.002>
- Balderas Torres, A., MacMillan, D. C., Skutsch, M., & Lovett, J. C. (2015). 'Yes-in-my-backyard': Spatial differences in the valuation of forest services and local co-benefits for carbon markets in México. *Ecological Economics*, 109, 130–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.11.008>
- Baró, J. E., & Expósito, J. L. (2008). Pago por servicio ambiental hídrico para la implementación de perímetros de protección de fuentes de agua destinadas al consumo humano. *Ciencia Ergo Sum*, 15(003), 311–316.
- Barr, R. F., & Mourato, S. (2009). Investigating the potential for marine resource protection through environmental service markets: An exploratory study from La Paz, Mexico. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 52(11), 568–577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2009.08.010>
- Bee, B. A. (2019). Gendered spaces of payment for environmental services: A critical look. *Geographical Review*, 109(1), 87–107. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gere.12292>

- Borrego, A., & Skutsch, M. (2014). Estimating the opportunity costs of activities that cause degradation in tropical dry forest: Implications for REDD+. *Ecological Economics*, 101, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.02.005>
- Brunett, E., Baró, J. E., & Cadena, E. (2010). Pago por servicios ambientales hidrológicos: Caso de estudio Parque Nacional del Nevado de Toluca, México. *Ciencia Ergo Sum*, 17(3), 286–294.
- Caro-Borrero, A., Corbera, E., Neitzel, K. C., & Almeida-Leñero, L. (2015). “We are the city lungs”: Payments for ecosystem services in the outskirts of Mexico City. *Land Use Policy*, 43, 138–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2014.11.008>
- Chagoya Fuentes, J. L., Mallén Rivera, C., McDonald, M. A., Jiménez Otarola, F., Akbar Ibrahim, M., Velázquez Fragoso, L., & Becerra Luna, F. (2018). Información hidrológica, primer paso para diseñar una política local de pago por servicios ambientales. *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Forestales*, 6(29), 24–43. <https://doi.org/10.29298/rmcf.v6i29.214>
- Chávez-Cortés, M. M., & Mancilla-Hernández, K. E. (2014). Esquema de cobro del servicio hidrológico que provee la cuenca alta del Pixquiac. 17.
- Corbera, E. (2010). Mexico’s PES-carbon programme: A preliminary assessment and impacts on rural livelihoods. In L. Tacconi, S. Mahanty, & H. Suich (Eds.), *Payments for Environmental Services, Forest Conservation and Climate Change* (pp. 54–81). Edward Elgar.
- Corbera, E., Costedoat, S., Ezzine-de-Blas, D., & Van Hecken, G. (2020). Troubled Encounters: Payments for Ecosystem Services in Chiapas, Mexico. *Development and Change*, 51(1), 167–195. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12540>
- Corbera, E., Kosoy, N., & Martínez Tuna, M. (2007). Equity implications of marketing ecosystem services in protected areas and rural communities: Case studies from Meso-America. *Global Environmental Change*, 17(3–4), 365–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2006.12.005>
- Corbera, E., Soberanis, C. G., & Brown, K. (2009). Institutional dimensions of Payments for Ecosystem Services: An analysis of Mexico’s carbon forestry programme. *Ecological Economics*, 68(3), 743–761. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2008.06.008>
- Costedoat, S., Corbera, E., Ezzine-de-Blas, D., Honey-Rosés, J., Baylis, K., & Castillo-Santiago, M. A. (2015). How Effective Are Biodiversity Conservation Payments in Mexico? *PLOS ONE*, 10(3), e0119881. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0119881>
- Costedoat, S., Koetse, M., Corbera, E., & Ezzine-de-Blas, D. (2016). Cash only? Unveiling preferences for a PES contract through a choice experiment in Chiapas, Mexico. *Land Use Policy*, 58, 302–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.07.023>

- De la Mora-De la Mora, G. (2019). Aproximación sociopolítica para el análisis de políticas de conservación en contextos urbanos: Entre servicios ambientales y áreas naturales protegidas. *Perfiles Latinoamericanos*, 27(53). <https://doi.org/10.18504/pl2753-003-2019>
- del Ángel Pérez, A. L., Rebolledo Martínez, A., Villagómez Cortés, J. A., & Zetina Lezama, R. (2009). Valoración del servicio ambiental hidrológico en el sector doméstico de San Andrés Tuxtla, Veracruz, México. *Estudios sociales (Hermosillo, Son.)*, 17(33), 225–257.
- del Ángel Pérez, A. L., Villagómez Cortés, J. A., Mendoza Briceño, M. A., & Rebolledo Martínez, A. (2016). Valoración de recursos naturales y ganadería en la zona centro de Veracruz, México. *Madera y Bosques*, 12(2), 29–48. <https://doi.org/10.21829/myb.2006.1221241>
- del Ángel Pérez, A. L. del, Villagómez Cortés, J. A., & Díaz Padilla, G. (2019). VALORACIÓN SOCIOECONÓMICA DEL PAGO POR SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES HIDROLÓGICOS EN VERACRUZ (COATEPEC Y SAN ANDRES TUXTLA). *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Forestales*, 2(6), 95–112. <https://doi.org/10.29298/rmcf.v2i6.577>
- Denham, D. (2017). Community Forest Owners Evaluate a Decade of Payments for Ecosystem Services in the Mexican Cloud Forest: The Importance of Attention to Indigenous Sovereignty in Conservation. *Society & Natural Resources*, 30(9), 1064–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2017.1295495>
- Dyer, G. A., & Nijnik, M. (2014). Implications of carbon forestry for local livelihoods and leakage. *Annals of Forest Science*, 71(2), 227–237. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-013-0293-9>
- Ezzine-de-Blas, D., Dutilly, C., Lara-Pulido, J.-A., Le Velly, G., & Guevara-Sanginés, A. (2016). Payments for Environmental Services in a Policymix: Spatial and Temporal Articulation in Mexico. *PLOS ONE*, 11(4), e0152514. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0152514>
- Figueroa, F., Caro-Borrero, Á., Revollo-Fernández, D., Merino, L., Almeida-Leñero, L., Paré, L., Espinosa, D., & Mazari-Hiriart, M. (2016). “I like to conserve the forest, but I also like the cash”. Socioeconomic factors influencing the motivation to be engaged in the Mexican Payment for Environmental Services Programme. *Journal of Forest Economics*, 22, 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfe.2015.11.002>
- Flores Aguilar, A., Aguilar Robledo, M., Reyes Hernández, H., & Guzmán Chávez, M. G. (2018). Gobernanza ambiental y pagos por servicios ambientales en América Latina. *Sociedad y Ambiente*, 16, 7–31. <https://doi.org/10.31840/sya.v0i16.1811>
- Franco-Maass, S., Nava-Bernal, G., Endara-Agramont, A., & González-Esquivel, C. (2008). Payments for Environmental Services: An Alternative for Sustainable Rural Development: The Case of a National Park in the Central Highlands of Mexico. *Mountain Research and Development*, 28(1), 23–25. <https://doi.org/10.1659/mrd.0971>

- Fuentes-George, K. (2013). Neoliberalism, Environmental Justice, and the Convention on Biological Diversity: How Problematizing the Commodification of Nature Affects Regime Effectiveness. *Global Environmental Politics*, 13(4), 144–163. https://doi.org/10.1162/GLEP_a_00202
- García López, T., & Gudiño Anaya, M. L. (2019). PROPUESTA Y BASES JURÍDICAS PARA LA ELABORACIÓN DE UN PROGRAMA DE PAGO POR SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES PARA LA LAGUNA DE SONTECOMAPAN, MÉXICO. *Veredas Do Direito: Direito Ambiental e Desenvolvimento Sustentável*, 16(35), 37. <https://doi.org/10.18623/rvd.v16i35.1558>
- García-Amado, L. R., Pérez, M. R., Escutia, F. R., García, S. B., & Mejía, E. C. (2011). Efficiency of Payments for Environmental Services: Equity and additionality in a case study from a Biosphere Reserve in Chiapas, Mexico. *Ecological Economics*, 70(12), 2361–2368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.07.016>
- García-Barrios, L., García-Barrios, R., Cruz-Morales, J., & Smith, J. A. (2015). When death approaches: Reverting or exploiting emergent inequity in a complex land-use table-board game. *Ecology and Society*, 20(2), art13. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07372-200213>
- Gómez Bonilla, A. (2017). Los programas de pago por servicios en Milpa Alta. Un análisis desde la ecología política feminista. *Sociedad y Ambiente*, 15, 93–116. <https://doi.org/10.31840/sya.v0i15.1788>
- Green, K. M., DeWan, A., Arias, A. B., & Hayden, D. (2013). Driving adoption of payments for ecosystem services through social marketing, Veracruz, Mexico. 5.
- Guerrero-García-Rojas, H., Gómez-Sántiz, F., & Rodríguez-Velázquez, J. R. (2015). Water Pricing in Mexico: Pricing Structures and Implications. In A. Dinar, V. Pochat, & J. Albiac-Murillo (Eds.), *Water Pricing Experiences and Innovations* (pp. 231–247). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16465-6_12
- Honey-Rosés, J., Baylis, K., & Ramírez, M. I. (2011). A Spatially Explicit Estimate of Avoided Forest Loss: Spatial Estimate of Avoided Forest Loss. *Conservation Biology*, 25(5), 1032–1043. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2011.01729.x>
- Honey-Rosés, J., López-García, J., Rendón-Salinas, E., Peralta-Higuera, A., & Galindo-Leal, C. (2009). To pay or not to pay? Monitoring performance and enforcing conditionality when paying for forest conservation in Mexico. *Environmental Conservation*, 36(2), 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892909990063>
- Ibarra, J. T., Barreau, A., Campo, C. D., Camacho, C. I., Martin, G. J., & Mccandless, S. R. (2011). When formal and market-based conservation mechanisms disrupt food sovereignty: Impacts of community conservation and payments for environmental services on an indigenous community of Oaxaca, Mexico. *International Forestry Review*, 13(3), 318–337. <https://doi.org/10.1505/146554811798293935>

- Illescas, J., & Montiel, S. (2018). Los nidos artificiales asociados al pago por servicios ambientales en una comunidad maya de Campeche: Características y atributos sociales para su implementación. *ACTA ZOOLOGICA MEXICANA (N.S.)*, 34(1). <https://doi.org/10.21829/azm.2018.3411187>
- Izquierdo-Tort, S. (2020). Payments for ecosystem services and conditional cash transfers in a policy mix: Microlevel interactions in Selva Lacandona, Mexico. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 30(1), 29–45. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1876>
- Izquierdo-Tort, S., Ortiz-Rosas, F., & Vázquez-Cisneros, P. A. (2019). ‘Partial’ participation in Payments for Environmental Services (PES): Land enrolment and forest loss in the Mexican Lacandona Rainforest. *Land Use Policy*, 87, 103950. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.04.011>
- Jones, K. W., Avila Foucat, S., Pischke, E. C., Salcone, J., Torrez, D., Selfa, T., & Halvorsen, K. E. (2019). Exploring the connections between participation in and benefits from payments for hydrological services programs in Veracruz State, Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 35, 32–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.11.004>
- Jones, K. W., Muñoz Brenes, C. L., Shinbrot, X. A., López-Báez, W., & Rivera-Castañeda, A. (2018). The influence of cash and technical assistance on household-level outcomes in payments for hydrological services programs in Chiapas, Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 31, 208–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.04.008>
- Jurjonas, M., & Seekamp, E. (2019). Balancing carbon dioxide: A case study of forest preservation, out-migration, and afforestation in the Pueblos Mancomunados of Oaxaca, Mexico. *Journal of Sustainable Forestry*, 38(7), 697–714. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10549811.2019.1602058>
- Kaczan, D., Pfaff, A., Rodriguez, L., & Shapiro-Garza, E. (2017). Increasing the impact of collective incentives in payments for ecosystem services. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 86, 48–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2017.06.007>
- Karsenty, A., Aubert, S., Brimont, L., Dutilly, C., Desbureaux, S., Ezzine de Blas, D., & Le Velly, G. (2017). The Economic and Legal Sides of Additionality in Payments for Environmental Services: The Economic and Legal Sides of Additionality in Payments for Environmental Services. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 27(5), 422–435. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1770>
- Kerr, J., Vardhan, M., & Jindal, R. (2012). Prosocial behavior and incentives: Evidence from field experiments in rural Mexico and Tanzania. *Ecological Economics*, 73, 220–227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2011.10.031>
- Kerr, J., Vardhan, M., & Jindal, R. (2014). Incentives, conditionality and collective action in payment for environmental services. *International Journal of the Commons*, 8(2), 595–616. <https://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.438>

- Koff, H., & Maganda, C. (2019). Saving the baby while discarding the bathwater: The application of policy coherence for development analysis to payment for watershed services. *Madera y Bosques*, 25(3). <https://doi.org/10.21829/myb.2019.2531760>
- Kosoy, N., Corbera, E., & Brown, K. (2008). Participation in payments for ecosystem services: Case studies from the Lacandon rainforest, Mexico. *Geoforum*, 39(6), 2073–2083. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2008.08.007>
- Le Velly, G., Sauquet, A., & Cortina-Villar, S. (2017). PES Impact and Leakages over Several Cohorts: The Case of the PSA-H in Yucatan, Mexico. *Land Economics*, 93(2), 230–257. <https://doi.org/10.3368/le.93.2.230>
- López Paniagua, C., González Guillén, M. de J., Valdez Lazalde, J. R., & De los Santos Posadas, H. M. (2016). Demanda, disponibilidad de pago y costo de oportunidad hídrica en la Cuenca Tapalpa, Jalisco. *Madera y Bosques*, 13(1), 3–23. <https://doi.org/10.21829/myb.2007.1311232>
- Manson, R. H. (2016). Los servicios hidrológicos y la conservación de los bosques de México. *Madera y Bosques*, 10(1), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.21829/myb.2004.1011276>
- Manzo-Delgado, L., López-García, J., & Alcántara-Ayala, I. (2014). Role of forest conservation in lessening land degradation in a temperate region: The Monarch Butterfly Biosphere Reserve, Mexico. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 138, 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.11.017>
- Martínez-Cruz, D. A., Bustamante-González, Á., Luis, J., Silva-Gómez, S. E., Tornero, M. A., & Vargas-López, S. (2010). DISPOSICIÓN DE LOS PRODUCTORES FORESTALES DE LA REGIÓN IZTA-POPO A ACEPTAR PAGOS POR MANTENER LOS SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES HIDROLÓGICOS. 8.
- McAfee, K., & Shapiro, E. N. (2010). Payments for Ecosystem Services in Mexico: Nature, Neoliberalism, Social Movements, and the State. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 100(3), 579–599. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00045601003794833>
- McDermott, C. L., & Ituarte-Lima, C. (2016). Safeguarding what and for whom? The role of institutional fit in shaping REDD+ in Mexico. *Ecology and Society*, 21(1), art9. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08088-210109>
- Méndez-López, M. E., García-Frapolli, E., Pritchard, D. J., Sánchez González, M. C., Ruiz-Mallén, I., Porter-Bolland, L., & Reyes-García, V. (2014). Local participation in biodiversity conservation initiatives: A comparative analysis of different models in South East Mexico. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 145, 321–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2014.06.028>
- Méndez-López, M. E., García-Frapolli, E., Ruiz-Mallén, I., Porter-Bolland, L., & Reyes-García, V. (2015). From Paper to Forest: Local Motives for Participation in Different Conservation Initiatives. Case

- Studies in Southeastern Mexico. *Environmental Management*, 56(3), 695–708. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-015-0522-0>
- Méndez-López, M. E., García-Frapolli, E., Ruíz-Mallén, I., Porter-Bolland, L., Sánchez-González, M. C., & Reyes-García, V. (2019). Who participates in conservation initiatives? Case studies in six rural communities of Mexico. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 62(6), 1045–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2018.1462152>
- Min-Venditti, A. A., Moore, G. W., & Fleischman, F. (2017). What policies improve forest cover? A systematic review of research from Mesoamerica. *Global Environmental Change*, 47, 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.08.010>
- Mokondoko, P., Manson, R. H., & Pérez-Maqueo, O. (2016). Assessing the service of water quality regulation by quantifying the effects of land use on water quality and public health in central Veracruz, Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 22, 161–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.09.001>
- Mokondoko, P., Manson, R. H., Ricketts, T. H., & Geissert, D. (2018). Spatial analysis of ecosystem service relationships to improve targeting of payments for hydrological services. *PLOS ONE*, 13(2), e0192560. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192560>
- Mora Carvajal, M. J., Bustamante González, A., Cajuste Bontemps, L., Vargas López, S., Cruz Bello, G. M., & Ramírez Juárez, J. (2019). Pago por servicios ambientales hidrológicos y dinámica de la cobertura arbórea en la región Iztaccíhuatl-Popocatepetl, Puebla, México. *Acta Agronómica*, 68(2), 84–91. <https://doi.org/10.15446/acag.v68n2.66291>
- Muñoz-Piña, C., Guevara, A., Torres, J. M., & Braña, J. (2008). Paying for the hydrological services of Mexico's forests: Analysis, negotiations and results. *Ecological Economics*, 65(4), 725–736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.07.031>
- Nava-López, M., Selfa, T. L., Cordoba, D., Pischke, E. C., Torrez, D., Ávila-Foucat, S., Halvorsen, K. E., & Maganda, C. (2018). Decentralizing Payments for Hydrological Services Programs in Veracruz, Mexico: Challenges and Implications for Long-term Sustainability. *Society & Natural Resources*, 31(12), 1389–1399. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2018.1463420>
- Neitzel, K. C., Caro-Borrero, A. P., Revollo-Fernandez, D., Aguilar-Ibarra, A., Ramos, A., & Almeida-Leñero, L. (2014). Paying for environmental services: Determining recognized participation under common property in a peri-urban context. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 38, 46–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2013.04.002>
- Newsham, A., Pulido, M. T., Ulrichs, M., Cruz, R. M., Ocón, X. C., Shankland, A., & Cannon, T. (2018). Ecosystems-based adaptation: Are we being conned? Evidence from Mexico. *Global Environmental Change*, 49, 14–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.01.001>

- Nieratkaa, L., Bray, D., & Mozumder, P. (2015). Can Payments for Environmental Services Strengthen Social Capital, Encourage Distributional Equity, and Reduce Poverty? *Conservation and Society*, 13(4), 345. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-4923.179880>
- Osborne, T., & Shapiro-Garza, E. (2018). Embedding Carbon Markets: Complicating Commodification of Ecosystem Services in Mexico's Forests. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 108(1), 88–105. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2017.1343657>
- Otto, J. (2016). Participation constrained: Generating buy-in and rationalizing carbon forestry labor through participatory mapping in Southern Mexico. *Geoforum*, 76, 28–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2016.08.009>
- Otto, J. (2019). Precarious Participation: Assessing Inequality and Risk in the Carbon Credit Commodity Chain. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 109(1), 187–201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2018.1490167>
- Perevochtchikova, Maria. (2012). The Federal Program of Payment for Hydrological Environmental Services as an Alternative Instrument for Integrated Water Resources Management in Mexico City. *The Open Geography Journal*, 5(1), 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874923201205010026>
- Perevochtchikova, María, & Colorado, V. M. T. (2014). Análisis comparativo de dos instrumentos de conservación ambiental aplicados en el Suelo de Conservación del Distrito Federal. *Sociedad y Ambiente*, 3, 3–25. <https://doi.org/10.31840/sya.v0i3.994>
- Perevochtchikova, María, & Ochoa Tamayo, A. M. (2019). AVANCES Y LIMITANTES DEL PROGRAMA DE PAGO POR SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES HIDROLÓGICOS EN MÉXICO, 2003—2009. *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Forestales*, 3(10), 89–112. <https://doi.org/10.29298/rmcf.v3i10.522>
- Perevochtchikova, Maria, & Oggioni, J. (2015). Global and Mexican analytical review of the state of the art on Ecosystem and Environmental services: A geographical approach. *Investigaciones Geográficas*, 0(85). <https://doi.org/10.14350/rig.41239>
- Perevochtchikova, Maria, & Rojo Negrete, I. A. (2015). The perceptions about payment schemes for ecosystem services: Study case of the San Miguel and Santo Tomás Ajusco community, Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 14, 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.04.002>
- Pérez García, N., Rueda González, M., Rojo Martínez, G. E., Martínez Ruiz, R., Ramírez Valverde, B., & Juárez Sánchez, J. P. (2009). El bambú (*Bambusa* spp.) como sistema agroforestal: Una alternativa de desarrollo mediante el pago por servicios ambientales en la sierra nororiental del Estado de Puebla. *Ra Ximhai*, 335–346. <https://doi.org/10.35197/rx.05.03.2009.08.np>
- Pfaff, A., Rodriguez, L. A., & Shapiro-Garza, E. (2019). Collective Local Payments for ecosystem services: New local PES between groups, sanctions, and prior watershed trust in Mexico. *Water Resources and Economics*, 28, 100136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wre.2019.01.002>

- Pischke, E. C., Berry, Z. C., Kolka, R. K., Salcone, J., Córdoba, D., Shinbrot, X., López Ramirez, S. M., Jones, K. W., Congalton, R. G., Manson, R. H., Von Thaden Ugalde, J. J., Selfa, T., Avila Foucat, V. S., & Asbjornsen, H. (2019). Lessons Learned About Collaborating Across Coupled Natural-Human Systems Research on Mexico's Payments for Hydrological Services Program. In S. G. Perz (Ed.), *Collaboration Across Boundaries for Social-Ecological Systems Science: Experiences Around the World* (pp. 35–77). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13827-1_2
- Ponette-González, A. G., & Fry, M. (2014). Enduring footprint of historical land tenure on modern land cover in eastern Mexico: Implications for environmental services programmes: Enduring footprint of historical land tenure on modern land cover. *Area*, 46(4), 398–409. <https://doi.org/10.1111/area.12125>
- Quijas, S., Boit, A., Thonicke, K., Murray-Tortarolo, G., Mwampamba, T., Skutsch, M., Simoes, M., Ascarrunz, N., Peña-Claros, M., Jones, L., Arets, E., Jaramillo, V. J., Lazos, E., Toledo, M., Martorano, L. G., Ferraz, R., & Balvanera, P. (2019). Modelling carbon stock and carbon sequestration ecosystem services for policy design: A comprehensive approach using a dynamic vegetation model. *Ecosystems and People*, 15(1), 42–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395908.2018.1542413>
- Ramírez-Reyes, C., Sims, K. R. E., Potapov, P., & Radeloff, V. C. (2018). Payments for ecosystem services in Mexico reduce forest fragmentation. *Ecological Applications*, 28(8), 1982–1997. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1753>
- Rico García-Amado, L., Ruiz Pérez, M., & Barrasa García, S. (2013). Motivation for conservation: Assessing integrated conservation and development projects and payments for environmental services in La Sepultura Biosphere Reserve, Chiapas, Mexico. *Ecological Economics*, 89, 92–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.02.002>
- Rodríguez R., K. J., & Ávila Foucat, S. (2013). Instrumentos económicos voluntarios para la conservación: Una mirada a su surgimiento y evolución en México: An Outlook on their Emergence and Evolution in Mexico. *Sociedad y Economía*, 25, 75–105.
- Rodríguez-Robayo, Karla J., & Merino-Pérez, L. (2018). Preserve and produce: Experience in implementing payments for environmental services in two indigenous communities in the Northern and Southern ranges of Oaxaca, Mexico. *Journal of Sustainable Forestry*, 37(5), 504–524. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10549811.2018.1432363>
- Rodríguez-Robayo, Karla Juliana, Ávila-Foucat, V. S., & Maldonado, J. H. (2016). Indigenous communities' perception regarding payments for environmental services programme in Oaxaca Mexico. *Ecosystem Services*, 17, 163–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.11.013>

- Rodríguez-Robayo, Karla Juliana, & Merino-Perez, L. (2017). Contextualizing context in the analysis of payment for ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services*, 23, 259–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.12.006>
- Rodríguez-Robayo, Karla Juliana, Perevochtchikova, M., Ávila-Foucat, S., & De la Mora De la Mora, G. (2020). Influence of local context variables on the outcomes of payments for ecosystem services. Evidence from San Antonio del Barrio, Oaxaca, Mexico. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 22(4), 2839–2860. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-019-00321-8>
- Rojas-López, O., González-Guillen, M. D. J., Gómez- Guerrero, A., & Romo-Lozano, J. L. (2019). RENTA DE LA TIERRA Y PAGO DE SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES EN LA SIERRA NORTE DE PUEBLA. *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Forestales*, 3(11), 41–56. <https://doi.org/10.29298/rmcf.v3i11.516>
- Rojo, I. A., Castro, B., & Perevochtchikova, M. (2018). Análisis de disfuncionalidad institucional de programas de política pública ambiental en la Ciudad de México, 2000-2012. *Gestión y Política Pública*, 27.
- Rolón Sánchez, J. E., Boucher, I. S., & Cortés, I. I. (2012). The Mexican PES Programme: Targeting for Higher Efficiency in Environmental Protection and Poverty Alleviation. In B. Rapidel, F. DeClerck, J.-F. Le Coq, & J. Beer (Eds.), *Ecosystem Services from Agriculture and Agroforestry* (pp. 323–338). Routledge.
- Romero, H. G. (2012). Payments for Environmental Services: Can They Work? *Field Actions Science Reports*, 7.
- Ruiz-Jiménez, M., Valtierra-Pacheco, E., Ruiz-Jiménez, M., & Valtierra-Pacheco, E. (2017). Impacto del pago por servicios ambientales hidrológicos en los bosques de tres ejidos de Texcoco, México. *Agricultura, sociedad y desarrollo*, 14(4), 511–531.
- Saavedra Díaz, Z. M., & Perevochtchikova, M. (2017). Evaluación ambiental integrada de áreas inscritas en el programa federal de Pago por Servicios Ambientales Hidrológicos. Caso de estudio: Ajusco, México. *Investigaciones Geográficas*. <https://doi.org/10.14350/rig.56437>
- Sánchez Brito, I. (2013). Valor de existencia del servicio ecosistémico hidrológico en la Reserva de la Biosfera Sierra La Laguna, Baja California Sur, México. 25, 34.
- Scullion, J., Thomas, C. W., Vogt, K. A., Pérez-Maqueo, O., & Logsdon, M. G. (2011). Evaluating the environmental impact of payments for ecosystem services in Coatepec (Mexico) using remote sensing and on-site interviews. *Environmental Conservation*, 38(4), 426–434. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S037689291100052X>
- Shapiro-Garza, E. (2013a). Contesting the market-based nature of Mexico's national payments for ecosystem services programs: Four sites of articulation and hybridization. *Geoforum*, 46, 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2012.11.018>

- Shapiro-Garza, E. (2013b). Contesting market-based conservation: Payments for ecosystem services as a surface of engagement for rural social movements in Mexico. *Human Geography* 6(1): 134-150.
- Shapiro-Garza, E. (2020). An Alternative Theorization of Payments for Ecosystem Services from Mexico: Origins and Influence. *Development and Change*, 51(1), 196–223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12552>
- Silva-Flores, R., Pérez-Verdín, G., & Návar-Cháidez, J. de J. (2016). Valoración económica de los servicios ambientales hidrológicos en El Salto, Pueblo Nuevo, Durango. *Madera y Bosques*, 16(1), 31–49. <https://doi.org/10.21829/myb.2010.1611178>
- Sims, K. R. E., & Alix-García, J. M. (2017). Parks versus PES: Evaluating direct and incentive-based land conservation in Mexico. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 86, 8–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2016.11.010>
- Sims, K. R. E., Alix-García, J. M., Shapiro-Garza, E., Fine, L. R., Radloff, V. C., Aronson, G., Castillo, S., Ramírez-Reyes, C., & Yañez-Pagans, P. (2014). Improving Environmental and Social Targeting through Adaptive Management in Mexico's Payments for Hydrological Services Program: Adaptive Management and Payment for Ecosystem Services. *Conservation Biology*, 28(5), 1151–1159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12318>
- Skutsch, M., Simon, C., Velázquez, A., & Fernández, J. C. (2013). Rights to carbon and payments for services rendered under REDD+: Options for the case of Mexico. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(4), 813–825. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.02.015>
- Southgate, D., & Wunder, S. (2009). Paying for Watershed Services in Latin America: A Review of Current Initiatives. *Journal of Sustainable Forestry*, 28(3–5), 497–524. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10549810902794493>
- Tolentino, O., García-Frapolli, E., Porter-Bolland, L., Ruíz-Mallén, I., Reyes-García, V., Sánchez-González, M.-C., & López-Méndez, M.-E. (2015). Triggering Community Conservation Through the Trade of Carbon Offsets: The Case of the Ejido Felipe Carrillo Puerto, Mexico. *The Journal of Environment & Development*, 24(2), 187–210. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1070496514565460>
- Villavicencio, Á. A. (2009). PROPUESTA METODOLÓGICA PARA UN SISTEMA DE PAGO POR SERVICIOS AMBIENTALES EN EL ESTADO DE MÉXICO. *Cuadernos Geográficos*, 44, 29–49.
- Von Thaden, J., Manson, R. H., Congalton, R. G., López-Barrera, F., & Salcone, J. (2019). A regional evaluation of the effectiveness of Mexico's payments for hydrological services. *Regional Environmental Change*, 19(6), 1751–1764. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-019-01518-3>
- Wells, G., Fisher, J. A., Porras, I., Staddon, S., & Ryan, C. (2017). Rethinking Monitoring in Smallholder Carbon Payments for Ecosystem Service Schemes: Devolve Monitoring, Understand Accuracy and

Identify Co-benefits. Ecological Economics, 139, 115–127.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.04.012>

Witt, B. (2019). Evaluating the Effects of a Minimalist Deliberative Framework on the Willingness to Participate in a Payment for Ecosystem Services Program. *Resources*, 8(2), 112.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/resources8020112>

Zamora Saenz, I., Cabestany Ruiz, G., Lucio Hernández, M., García Cuevas, L. M., & Vargas Pérez, E. (2016). Percepción social sobre el Pago por Servicios Ambientales Hidrológicos en los bienes comunales de San Pedro y San Felipe Chichila, Taxco, Guerrero. *Sociedad y Ambiente*, 10, 57–77.
<https://doi.org/10.31840/sya.v0i10.1652>

Zúñiga Vásquez, J. M., López, E. A. M., Gallardo, N., & Mejía, B. C. (2018). Análisis ecológico de un área de pago por servicios ambientales hidrológicos en el ejido La Ciudad, Pueblo Nuevo, Durango, México. *Investigación y Ciencia*, 26(73), 27–36.

Sloping Land Conservation Program in China

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1. Background and context & Problematization and framing

In 1998, devastating floods swept through the Yangtze Basin and attracted national attention to the environmental degradation in the river's upper watersheds. Apart from deforestation, it is commonly believed that the cultivation of mountainous land coupled with uneven rainfall caused major soil erosion and the failure of the ecosystem's water regulating functions, ultimately leading to human-induced natural disasters (Xu et al., 2004; Xu et al., 2006; Wang, 2008). Poverty was identified as a factor associated with the extension of cultivation to steeper slopes, the clearance of forest for agricultural purposes, and the subsequent overgrazing of pastures that led to unsustainable land conditions upstream (SFA, 2002).

In response to the devastating flooding in the Yangtze Basin, the Chinese government initiated the SLCP for ecological restoration in 1999. Pilot studies were initiated in three provinces (Sichuan, Shangxi and Gansu), and this was expanded to 17 provinces in 2000. Currently, the SLCP is being implemented in 25 provinces. The initial goal of the SLCP was to increase forest cover and prevent soil erosion on sloping croplands by converting the marginal agricultural land into forest. As it was implemented in remote and poor mountainous regions, the program also sought to restructure the rural economy and improve the livelihoods of poor communities by providing subsidies and off-farm opportunities. This was to ensure that participating farmers could gradually shift into more environmentally and economically sustainable land-use activities (SFA, 2002).

Under the first round of the SLCP, the State Forestry Administration planned to convert around 14.67 million hectares of fragile croplands to forest by 2010 (SFA, 2002). The program targeted marginal cropland on slopes of 15° or greater in northwestern China and 25° or greater elsewhere. Apart from its integration of environmental goals with those of agricultural resource sustainability and poverty reduction, the program directly involves millions of rural households as core agents of its implementation. This was partly in recognition of local priorities and partly to fulfill the need for greater local input into forest management. It also has been a landmark program in promoting the principle of volunteerism for decentralized, grassroots participation in forest sector projects, as policy attempts to enable local decision-making in all process from planning and implementation (Bennett, 2008; Weyerhaeuser et al., 2005; He, 2014). However, He (2014) showed limited participatory governance and little volunteerism in a comparative study of implementation in two villages, with a majority of respondents stating they had no autonomy in determining interventions. In these instances, community meetings were primarily for distributing already-drafted plans to participants. Other studies have also shown administration of the program to be top-down in practice (Weyerhaeuser et al., 2005; Xu et al. 2004; Bennett 2008).

The SLCP is also known as Grain for Green, as its innovative payment approach subsidizes farmers with grain in exchange for ecological restoration to cover their agricultural losses. Under the program, the government compensated farmers with 2250 and 1500 kg of grain per ha of converted cropland per year in the upper reaches of the Yangtze River Basin, and the upper and middle reaches of the Yellow River Basin, respectively, calculated to offset opportunity cost and accounting for differences in regional average yields. This compensation scheme was motivated by large agricultural surpluses in grain supplies. In addition, annual cash subsidies of 300CNY/ha/year for miscellaneous expenses and a one-off subsidy of 750 CNY/ha for seeds or seedlings are also provided to farmers. The duration of the grain and cash subsidies depends on the cropland conversion: it continues for eight years if ecological forest is planted and for five or two years if economic forest or grasses are planted, respectively. In 2004, the grain subsidies were replaced with the equivalent value in cash, at CNY 1.4 per kg of grain. This was in response to the rapid decline in stored domestic grain, the international food security crisis, and the increasing operational costs of transporting grain.

In 2007, the Chinese government launched a policy called 'Improvement of the SLCP', also known as 'Consolidating SLCP Achievements', to show its commitment to long-term investments in forest restoration. The policy was also a response to questions of the SLCP's sustainability, because the government feared that participating farmers would cut the planted trees (SFA, 2007). This follow-up policy extends the compensation payment period to avoid land reconversion and ensure a positive environmental outcome from the SLCP. Under this revision, after the first round of compensation, farmers receive CNY 1875/ha/year in the Yangtze River Basin and 1350/ha/year in the Yellow River Basin for another 8 or 5 years, respectively, depending on what tree species they have planted. The new payment is half the full compensation of the first round. The Consolidating SLCP policy also recognizes that local economic development is a necessary pathway for long-term conservation, hence it has invested in securing food production, rural energy, and other post-SLCP industry development.

2. Outcomes

There is a rich body of literature examining various perspectives of the SLCP and its outcomes. Many studies have focused on its effectiveness in forest restoration (e.g. Persson et al. 2013; He et al. 2014; Ahrends et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2017) and livelihood impacts (e.g. Uchida, 2007; Liu et al. 2009; Li et al. 2011; Lin et al. 2014), concluding that there are mixed results at both the macro and micro levels. For example, some scholars have undertaken large-scale analyses to document that the SLCP has led to limited forest cover change (e.g. Ahrends et al. 2017). Others have argued that reforestation with compositionally-simple (plantation) forests has negatively impacted bird biodiversity, with limited benefits from the use of mixed forests but far below levels seen in native forests (Hua, et al., 2016). That study concluded that all reforestation modalities negatively impacted bee biodiversity (ibid.). Still other scholars have focused on the impacts on rural incomes and inequality (Li et al. 2011; Uchida 2007). Others have taken a case-study approach to highlight the important local variations and contexts that shape the SLCP outcomes (He, 2014; Zhang et al., 2017 and Zinda, 2018). Existing literature further have attempted to explain the variations in project outcomes based on finer-scale analyses, concluding that customary

institutions (He, 2014), local knowledge and labor (Bennett et al. 2014), local cultures (Woodhouse, 2015) and central-local conflicts of interest (Yu, 2016) would affect the program's outcomes.

While many studies attempt to focus on institutional aspects of the SLCP, most of these analyses are restricted to the institutional arrangements of policy formulation (e.g. Bennett, 2008; Xu et al. 2004; Yin and Yin, 2010; Yeh, 2009; Liu et al. 2008; Weyerhaeuser et al. 2005). Some scholars have had an interest in the program's policy formulations and institutional arrangements, documenting how the top-down implementation of the SLCP has limited both its ecological and socioeconomic outcomes and deviated from the original principles of PES (Bennett 2008; Xu et al. 2004; He and Lang, 2014). Some scholars have examined the gaps between state intentions and actual local outcomes (Zhang et al., 2017), or questioned the program's sustainability (Xu et al. 2006). For instance, participants have modified state-driven interventions that were not suited to local biophysical conditions, livelihoods, or cultural values, sometimes resulting in conflict with authorities (He 2014; Harrell et al. 2016). He (2014) showed in a comparative study that social and environmental outcomes varied significantly based on local institutional context, with greater self-governance and downward accountability associated with increased forest cover and participant satisfaction. However, all of these studies have focused on the analysis of effectiveness and efficiencies by an outcomes-oriented approach, or whether the outcomes of the SLCP have varied from place to place, while only a few studies provide a critical viewpoint of local dynamics and process in SLCP implementation (Zinda et al., 2017; Trac et al., 2013).

He and Sikor (2015) found that a partial overlap in notions of distributive justice held by participants and local state officials in Yunnan Province may have contributed to positive economic and environmental outcomes, even though participants desired more procedural justice in program implementation. They note that "[v]illagers' notions of justice are part of the local political economies that shape the dynamics of implementation, land use, and livelihoods as well as the outcomes of the SLCP and other programs," and that adapting PES design to local notions of justice is as important as considering local ecosystem values (ibid. 215).

The SLCP program is a milestone in Chinese forest policy, which has shifted from a command-and-control approach towards applying financial instruments that provide monetary incentives to farmers for forest restoration, with the aim of enhancing efficiency and improving rural livelihoods (He and Sikor 2015). More innovatively, the program intends to improve local volunteerism and autonomy in the policy's implementation (State Forestry Administration, SFA, 2002; Bennett, 2008). This has attracted international interest and research. Apart from studies focusing on the top-down approach of the program's policy formulation and implementation (Xu et al., 2004; Bennett, 2008; Yin et al., 2013), the literature concentrates on the socioeconomic impacts of the program and particularly on farmers' economic strategies and options after the program (Chen et al., 2009; Ma et al., 2009), and the contribution of off-farm job for improving local economies and shifting from on-farm to off-farm strategy. Others also showed that the SLCP made positive contributions to rural income and increased off-farm opportunities, while inequality increased due to a lack of labor and skills for off-farm employment (Uchida et al., 2007; Li et al., 2011). These studies also show that SLCP interacts in complex ways with urban labor markets and other political economic forces driving rural-to-urban migration, variously considered

positive for economic development (Yan et al. 2016; Uchida et al. 2007). While other studies explore its local impact from a more comprehensive perspective (Weyerhaeuser et al., 2005; Xu et al., 2006), they do not adequately provide a combination of biophysical and socioeconomic evidence for a holistic understanding of the policy's implementation and impacts. Whether the SLCP has been implemented effectively, the extent of its ecological and socioeconomic outcomes, and how its performance can be improved are still not clear.

3. Methodology and literature:

I draw from the insight in section of literature part of five my previous published paper to make the argumentation for this case-studies. Those five published paper are:

1. He, J.* (2020) Situated payment for ecosystem services: local agencies in Sloping Land Conversion Program Implementation in Southwest China. *Development and Change* 51(1): 73-93
2. He, J., and Sikor, T. (2015). Notions of Justice in Payments for Ecosystem Services: Insights from China's Sloping Land Conversion Program in Yunnan Province. *Land Use Policy* 43: 207–216.
3. He, J. (2014). Governing Forest Restoration: Local Case Studies of Sloping Land Conversion Program in Southwest China. *Forest Policy and Economics* 46: 30–38.
4. He, J., Lang, R., Xu, J. (2014) Local Dynamics Driving Forest Transition: Insights from Upland Villages in Southwest China. *Forests* 5 (2): 214-233.
5. He J., R. Lang (2015) Limits of state-led programs of payment for ecosystem services: field evidence from the Sloping Land Conversion Program in Southwest China. *Human Ecology* 43:749-758.

References

- Ahrends, A., Hollingsworth, P. M., Beckschäfer, P., Chen, H., Zomer, R. J., & Zhang, L., et al. (2017). China's fight to halt tree cover loss. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B Biological Sciences*, 284(1854).
- Bennett, M.T.,(2008). China's sloping land conversion program: institutional innovation or business as usual? *Ecological Economics* 65 (4), 699–711.
- Bennett, M. T., Xie, C., Hogarth, N. J., Peng, D., and Putzel, L. (2014). China's Conversion of Cropland to Forest Program for Household Delivery of Ecosystem Services: How Important is a Local Implementation Regime to Survival Rate Outcomes? *Forests* 5(9): 2345–2376.
- Chen, X., F. Lupi, G. He, Z. Ouyang, J. Liu. (2009). Factors affecting land reconversion plans following a payment for ecosystem service program. *Biological Conservation* 142(8): 1740-1747.

- Gutierrez Rodriguez, L., Hogarth, N. J., Zhou, W., Xie, C., Zhang, K., & Putzel, L. (2016). Chinas conversion of cropland to forest program: A systematic review of the environmental and socioeconomic effects. *Environmental Evidence*, 5 doi:<http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.library.ubc.ca/10.1186/s13750-016-0071-x>
- Harrell, S., Yang Qingxia, Viraldo, S. J., Hagmann, R. K., Hinckley, T., & Schmidt, A. H. (2016). Forest is Forest and Meadows are Meadows: Cultural Landscapes and Bureaucratic Landscapes in Jiuzhaigou County, Sichuan. *Archív Orientalní*, 84(3), 595–623.
- He, J. and Sikor, T. (2017). Looking beyond tenure in China's Collective Forest Tenure Reform: insight from Yunnan Province, Southwest China. *International Forestry Review* 19(1):29-41.
- He, J., and Sikor, T. (2015). Notions of Justice in Payments for Ecosystem Services: Insights from China's Sloping Land Conversion Program in Yunnan Province. *Land Use Policy* 43: 207–216.
- He, J. (2014). Governing Forest Restoration: Local Case Studies of Sloping Land Conversion Program in Southwest China. *Forest Policy and Economics* 46: 30–38.
- He, J., Lang, R., Xu, J. (2014) Local Dynamics Driving Forest Transition: Insights from Upland Villages in Southwest China. *Forests* 5 (2): 214-233.
- He J., R. Lang (2015) Limits of state-led programs of payment for ecosystem services: field evidence from the Sloping Land Conversion Program in Southwest China. *Human Ecology* 43:749-758.
- He, J., Zhou, Z., Weyerhaeuser, H., Xu, J. (2009). Participatory technology development for incorporating non-timber forest products into forest restoration in Yunnan, Southwest China. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 257(10), 2010-2016.
- Hua, F. et al. (2016). Opportunities for Biodiversity Gains under the World's Largest Reforestation Programme. *Nature Communications* 7:12717.www.nature.com/articles/ncomms12717.
- Li, J., M. W. Feldman, S Li, G. C. Gaily. (2011). Rural household income and inequality under the Sloping Land Conversion Program in western China. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108(19): 7721-7726.
- Lin Y, Yao S. (2014) Impact of the Sloping Land Conversion Program on rural household income: An integrated estimation. *Land Use Policy*, 40: 56-63.
- Liu, C., Lu, J., & Yin, R. (2010). An Estimation of the Effects of China's Priority Forestry Programs on Farmers' Income. *Environmental Management*, 45(3), 526-540.
- Ma, H., Y. Lu, Y. Xing, G. He, Y. Sun. (2009). Rural Households' Attitude and Economic Strategies toward the Conversion of Cropland to Forest and Grassland Program (CCFG): A Case Study in Qira, China. *Environmental Management* 43(6): 1039-1047.

- SFA (State Forestry Administration) (2002) Improving implementation of the Sloping Land Conservation Program. Policy Document by State Forestry Administration.
- SFA (State Forestry Administration)(2007) Improving the Sloping Land Conservation Program. Policy Document by State Forestry Administration.
- SFA (State Forestry Administration) 2018. 2017 China Forestry Development Report. Beijing: China Forestry Publishing House.
- Trac, C.J., A.H. Schmidt, S. Harrell and T.M. Hinckley. (2013). Environmental Reviews and Case Studies: Is the Returning Farmland to Forest Program a Success? Three Case Studies from Sichuan. *Environmental Practice* 15(3): 350–366.
- Uchida, E.; Xu, J.; Xu, Z.; Rozelle, S. (2007). Are the poor benefiting from China's land conservation program? *Environment Development and Economics*. 12, 593–620.
- Wang, G., J. L. Innes, S.W. Wu, S. Dai. (2008). Towards a New Paradigm: The Development of China's Forestry in the 21st Century. *International Forestry Review* 10(4), 619-631.
- Weyerhaeuser, H., Wilkes, A., Khral, F. (2005). Local impacts and responses to regional forest conservation and rehabilitation programs in China's northwest Yunnan province. *Agric. Syst.* 85 (3), 234–253.
- Woodhouse, E. (2015). Local experiences and contested meanings of the Chinese 'grain for green' land conversion programme in an agro-pastoralist Tibetan community. *Nomadic Peoples*, 19(2), 281-302.
- Xu, Z.G.; Bennett, M.T.; Tao, R.; Xu, J.T. (2004) China's Sloping Land Conversion Programme four years on: Current situation and pending issues. *International Forestry Review* 2004, 6, 317–326.
- Xu, J., Yin, R., Li, Z., & Liu, C. (2006). China's ecological rehabilitation: Unprecedented efforts, dramatic impacts, and requisite policies. *Ecological Economics*, 57(4), 595–607.
- Yan, J., Yang, Z., Li, Z., Li, X., Xin, L., & Sun, L. (2016). Drivers of cropland abandonment in mountainous areas: A household decision model on farming scale in Southwest China. *Land Use Policy*, 57, 459–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.06.014>
- Yeh, E.T. (2009) 'Greening Western China: A Critical View', *Geoforum* 40(5): 884–894.
- Yin, R., Liu, T., Yao, S., Zhao, M. (2013). Designing and implementing payments for ecosystem services programs: lessons learned from China's cropland restoration experience. *For. Policy Econ.* 35, 66–72.
- Yin, R., Yin, G., (2010) China's primary programs of terrestrial ecosystem restoration: initiation, implementation, and challenges. *Environmental Management* 45 (3):429-441.

Yin, R.; Zhao, M.; Yao, S. (2014) Designing and implementing payments for ecosystem services programs: What lessons can be learned from China's experience of restoring degraded cropland? *Environment Science and Technology* 48, 19–20.

Yin, R.K. (2003). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*, 3rd ed. Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.

Yu, X. (2016). Central–local conflicts in China's environmental policy implementation: the case of the sloping land conversion program. *Natural Hazards*, 84(1), 77-96.

Zhang, Z., J.A. Zinda and W. Li. (2017) Forest Transitions in Chinese Villages: Explaining Community-level Variation under the Returning Forest to Farmland Program. *Land Use Policy* 64: 245–257.

Zinda, J. A., Trac, C. J., Zhai, D., & Harrell, S. (2017). Dual-function forests in the returning farmland to forest program and the flexibility of environmental policy in China. *Geoforum* 78: 119-132.

North Australian Indigenous fire management and carbon abatement – the case of savanna burning

Sue Jackson

Background and context

Program description

For the past twenty years, savanna burning has been an important site of innovation in climate change policy. In parts of northern Australia, where colonisation induced a decline or cessation of Indigenous burning practices (Cook et al. 2012; Langton 1998; Yibarbuk et al. 2001), community-based Indigenous natural resource management organisations and others have implemented prescribed burning regimes that are consistent with the Kyoto Protocol. Under a savanna burning program fire regimes that combine Indigenous burning practices, non-Indigenous expertise and new technologies are being applied to areas where funds for land management are scarce. The program provides an economic basis for improved fire management, reductions of Greenhouse Gases (GHG), and a range of other environmental and social outcomes. There are now 78 registered savanna burning projects in northern Australia (Moura et al. 2019), of which one third are administered by Indigenous ranger groups (MacMurray et al.). They cover more than 20% of Australian savannas (Corey et al. 2018) under a broad range of tenures across Queensland, Western Australia and the Northern Territory (see Figure 1) (32 are on Indigenous lands). These projects currently account for 10% of Australian carbon credit issuance, with five projects in Arnhem Land in the Northern Territory making up half that amount (Ansell et al. 2020).

Figure 1. Australia's tropical savannas

Due to their rainfall seasonality, savannas are one of the most fire prone landscapes on earth (Lipsett-Moore et al. 2018). An average of 20 percent of Australia's 1.9 million km² northern savanna region burns annually, mostly in the latter part of the dry season (April–November), when relatively high intensity wildfires sweep through remote areas (Russell-Smith et al. 2013; Anderson et al. 2012). These fires emit methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), affect carbon stocks, and often have deleterious social impacts. Fires in this sparsely populated region contribute 1.5 – 4% of Australia's total annual emissions (Whitehead et al. 2008). Much of the frequently fire-affected land has a history of Indigenous use and management stretching back more than 50 000 years (Clarkson et al. 2017) and is now under forms of Indigenous communal ownership recognised by the state. Native title, for instance, is recognised over as much as 60% of northern Australia (at March 2018) (Heiner et al. 2019).

Savanna burning projects shift the seasonal timing of fire to the early dry season and/or reduce overall fire frequency and extent. Such fires result in lower GHG emissions by reducing biomass consumed within the fire footprint (including dead organic matter such as trees) and by limiting the spread of high intensity fires that will inevitably occur later in the dry season (Corey et al. 2018). The distinction between early and late dry season fires provides the basis for the methodologies upon which prescribed burns reduce GHG emissions. These methodologies provide a means to quantify the effects of changing fire regimes on emissions (Russell-Smith *et al.*, 2013) and trade in carbon offsets.

Managing fire to sequester or avoid the release of GHG is one of a number of 'carbon farming' activities fostered by programs that form part of Australia's response to climate change. This terminology was given official recognition under the Australian Government's Carbon Farming Initiative (CFI), a legislated offset scheme that formed part of the Carbon Pricing Mechanism that existed from 2011 to 2014 (Baumber et al. 2019; Watson and Fitzsimons 2015). The CFI was Australia's first national-scale example of a market in ecosystem services (Russell-Smith et al. 2015). It enabled landholders to earn credits for sequestration on their land under approved methodologies and sell them to entities wishing to offset their emissions. In 2014, the Emissions Reduction Fund (ERF) replaced the Carbon Pricing Mechanism, where the Australian Government acts as a single buyer of emissions reduction credits via an auction mechanism. A number of CFI methodologies relating to vegetation management were incorporated into the ERF in 2015, including savanna burning, after much work by a loose coalition of researchers, land management agencies, Indigenous NGOs, and various government departments. The ERF works on a principle of lowest cost abatement; it places no financial value on social or environmental outcomes that accompany GHG abatement (McMurray et al. 2018).

While the ERF is the dominant source of demand for carbon credits, accounting for over 95% of demand, there is a broader market that involves other buyers including those acting voluntarily to offset their emissions. Such credits can sell at a price premium compared to ERP auction prices (Baumber et al. 2019; MacMurray et al. 2018) and many have recognised the potential for savanna burning to provide additional payments to landholders for providing other 'services' (Jackson and Palmer 2015; Robinson et al. 2016). Australian studies (e.g. Evans 2018) have identified a lack of incentive to monitor and report co-benefits of carbon farming generally, arguing that this has hampered understanding of benefits and the estimation of risks of disbenefits (Baumber et al. 2019), as well as difficulties in tracking changes over time.

Experimentation in landscape fire management in the late 1990s led to a landmark GHG offset agreement in 2006 between American gas company ConocoPhillips, the Northern Territory Government, Northern Land Council, and Traditional Owners and Indigenous land managers in west Arnhem Land (referred to as WALFA – West Arnhem Land Fire Abatement). This ‘globally unique’ project became the landscape-scale model upon which the approved savanna burning method was based (Whitehead et al. 2009 p. 291) and it currently accounts for the highest number of ACCUs issued to a single project across all eligible offsets projects across all methodologies (Ansell et al. 2020). The first project approved under the savanna burning methodology occurred in the same jurisdiction in 2012 at Fish River (O’Donnell 2014; Macdonald 2013; Jackson et al. 2017). The private investment from the WALFA deal helped consolidate earlier initiatives and generated confidence for others to invest both financially and non-financially (Whitehead et al. 2009).

Context

The population of the savannas is relatively small (500 000 in 2011), widely dispersed and 18.7% Indigenous. Average population density of 0.29 persons.km⁻² is low by Australian (2.5 persons.km⁻²) and global standards, and lower still away from major towns (see Figure 1) (Russell-Smith et al. 2009; Russell-Smith et al. 2015). The decentralised Indigenous population is rapidly growing, but economically marginalised, despite having very substantial interests in, and customary responsibilities for, land (Russell-Smith et al. 2009). Low population density and weak infrastructure compromise capacity to manage pervasive threats such as wildfire that require active intervention to manage their impacts (Whitehead 1999).

The major uses of land in the tropical savannas are grazing (under lease), Indigenous customary use and conservation. Only a very small area is used for mining purposes, but such land use constitutes by far the greatest economic return to the regional economy (Russell-Smith et al. 2009). Regulation of the use of fire is a responsibility of state or territory governments under Australia’s system of land management but states and territories have agreed that GHG emissions should be managed nationally (Whitehead et al. 2009).

In this region, many of the Indigenous NRM programs are supported financially by the Australian Government through funding programs like Indigenous Protected Area (IPA) and Indigenous Advancement Strategy (IAS), as well as other sources of income, that include philanthropy (Ansell 2020; Altman and Kerins 2012; Jackson and Palmer 2015). This and other factors led Whitehead et al. (2008) to conclude that opportunities for Indigenous involvement in fire abatement work have arisen under favourable political circumstances. Without strong land rights legislation that granted statutory freehold title to some Aboriginal traditional owners in the Northern Territory (as much as 45% of the jurisdiction) it is unlikely that the program would have taken the shape it has. In addition, the CFI provides Indigenous groups with exclusive possession native title with a carbon right and status as a project proponent, which includes the legal right to carry out a savanna burning project (O’Donnell 2013). There is no requirement of proof of any specific traditional law and custom, specific native title right or interest or concerns about extinguishment concerning a right to carbon.

Problematization and framing (defining the problem)

While most accounts trace the origins of the program to a concern over ‘out of control fires’ and a specific research collaboration in Arnhem Land in the late 1990s (described below), it can be argued that the program emerged from a deeper history of agitation over fire by Indigenous peoples (Jackson and Palmer 2015). The significance of fire and Indigenous firing behaviours and knowledge had been a ‘burning issue’ in this region for some time before the development of a PES program. Scientific controversies had erupted over the efficacy of Indigenous burning with some ecologists blaming Indigenous peoples for extinctions of megafauna or destruction of rainforests (Verran 2002; Langton 1998). As noted by Bowman (1998) the scientific literature was originally characterised by an absence of Indigenous people’s own views about fire. During the 1990s a number of influential Indigenous people responded to misrepresentations and neglect of their firing practices (Langton 1998; Yirbarbuk 1998; 2001) and many more had been agitating for change in their local interactions with management agencies for at least a decade or earlier (see Petty et al.). Yirbarbuk (1998), for instance, drew attention to widespread concern amongst his community in Arnhem Land that knowledge of customary practices and symbolic meanings, as well as adherence to norms of fire use, were at risk because of changes within Indigenous societies and to environmental relations (1998). Yirbarbuk said that ‘fire is not being well looked after’ around settlements and there are large areas that are devoid of people to fire the land (1998 p. 5).

A few papers on savanna burning emphasise the perspective of traditional owners in shaping the program’s direction. Ansell et al. (2020) explain that early discussions between traditional owners and (non-Aboriginal) scientists ‘led to the development of a vision of people living on healthy country, and ultimately to the innovative program of fire management’ (p. 372). In this region, Aboriginal people see fire as both ‘an asset to protect and utilise within the landscape, and as a threat to manage’ (Ansell et al. 2020 p. 375). Petty et al. (2015) describe WALFA as ‘highly collaborative’, coming from ‘extensive discussion and collaboration with Aboriginal residents and particularly senior landowners to understand the geography and sociology of fire’ (p. 155).

Numerous descriptions of the program’s formative years confirm the emergence in the 1990s of a consensus view that late, dry season wildfires were harmful to ‘natural and cultural assets’ (Russell-Smith et al. 2009 p. 14; Perry et al. 2018). Ecological studies conducted at this time provided the ‘technical foundation’ for collaborative efforts made later to reduce GHG (Whitehead et al. 2009; Duff et al. 2009). Russell-Smith et al. (2009) emphasise that the prevailing fire regime was the central problem:

Achieving significant greenhouse gas emissions abatement, and more effective savanna landscape fire management generally, are thus components of the same integral problem – how do we practically and economically reduce the incidence and extent of contemporary late dry season wildfires.

Research on the biophysical role and characteristics of fire built a case for a change in fire management practices and explored practical management models. That effort proceeded to improve understanding through a series of regional fire management case studies in the Top End, many of them relating to the impacts of fire on vegetation dynamics (Whitehead et al. 2009). The focal point at that time was western Arnhem Land, a region of high biodiversity value where Aboriginal land rights were secure and positive

professional relationships between key scientists, land managers and traditional owners (with some overlap of these categories) were conducive to experimentation (Duff et al. 2009; Whitehead et al. 2009). Whitehead et al. (2009) explain that earlier initiatives had built institutions needed for fire management to operate over a large area, a fire control region for Arnhem created in 2004 under the sole control of Indigenous land-owners, and the capability that creation of consolidation of Aboriginal Ranger groups brought to the problem (see Altman and Kerins 2012; Marum 2014).

Whitehead et al. (2009) point to the connection between wildfires and GHG emissions as a crucial moment. Until the Kyoto Protocol lever came into play, it had been difficult to gain support for active fire management. The deleterious effects for biodiversity or the potential livelihood opportunities had not been influential in forming effective policy responses. From 2000, the fire research this group undertook included an emissions inventory to underpin a commercially sustainable GHG abatement programme (Whitehead et al. 2008).

A mix of three environmental governance ideas influenced problem framing and the trajectory that program leaders followed in converting a regional landscape fire project to a land management program based on payments conditional on performance in abating GHG. First, a significant number of environmental scientists agreed that Aboriginal burning was a tool for effectively managing the land (Verran 2002). Under this newly developing paradigm, it was not possible or productive to exclude fire from large areas in the highly seasonal landscapes of the tropical north (Whitehead et al. 2003). In a departure from colonial traditions of scientific practice (Verran 2003; Cook et al. 2012), they sought knowledge from Aboriginal custodians to elucidate the role of Indigenous fire practices in shaping the fundamental character of savanna landscapes (see for example Whitehead et al. 2003; Bowman 1998). Similarly, scientists grew more interested in the ecological consequences of the socially disruptive effects of colonisation, when fires went 'feral' through a depopulated landscape (Russell-Smith et al. 2009; Cook et al. 2012; Whitehead et al. 2008).

Second, NT researchers and land managers were attracted to the international discourse of PES, seeing an opportunity in market-based instruments (such as GHG targets and carbon trading) to improve fire 'management performance' by incentivising land-holders to alter fire regimes. At this point fire started being described as an ecosystem service, as a processes contributing to climate regulation for instance, and Indigenous people were positioned as providers of ES to 'regional, national and international markets' (Russell-Smith et al. 2009 p.15). It was hoped that the new regulatory framework for GHG that imposed costs on emissions and created a 'national carbon budget' (Williams et al. 2005) would make the 'productive use' of fire in the north Australian economy more visible (Whitehead et al. 2009; Whitehead et al. 2008). According to Williams et al. (2005), this international framework could provide an 'alternative or additional land use and valuation of these environments' (p. x). If ecosystem services are valued properly, argued Russell-Smith et al. (2015, p. 13), landholders will 'have stronger incentives to provide them and some segments of society [will] no longer free-ride on the efforts of others to care for environments'.

Third, carbon trading could generate income for Indigenous people (Zander et al. 2013); it could finance alternative approaches to environmental stewardship that would underwrite a 'return to country', some of which had been abandoned for decades (Whitehead et al. 2008; Jackson et al. 2017). Additionally, traditional owners and researchers saw carbon burning and trading as a means to support programs that would enable Indigenous landowners to exercise greater control over fire, autonomy and self-determination in community affairs, as well as valorise Indigenous knowledge and expertise in 'caring for country' (McMurray et al. 2018; Marum 2014; Robinson et al. 2016; Langton 1998).

It is also worth reflecting on how the social context of this program and its various 'social dimensions' are represented in the literature (published almost exclusively in scientific outlets) for it provides an insight into framing. A key source is an edited collection on the 'culture, ecology, and economy' of northern savannah fire management produced by three program 'thought leaders' (Russell-Smith, Whitehead, Cook et al. 2009). In the introduction, they explain that 'in positing options for human intervention to improve outcomes from management of fire, it is essential also to consider the plausibility of the interventions proposed' (p. 15). It seems that those telling the savanna burning story were not pursuing, or did not wish to explicitly commit this program to a normative goal of procedural or distributive justice, for example. Technical knowledge (historical events and trends, demographic trends, patterns of Indigenous life including customary practices etc.) would improve program efficacy and aid in program implementation:

We approach the question of plausibility in several ways. First, we closely examine the social history of northern Australia (especially the Top End) to improve understanding of the way different groups interpreted their actions and influence on patterns of fire and their benefits. Second, informed by this historical analysis, we consider relevant aspects of contemporary northern Australia society to assess options to secure greater engagement of the present population in shared approaches to fire management. Third, and perhaps most importantly, we consider the relationship between the well-being of northern Australia's human population and its use of fire (p.15).

Such a perspective can be contrasted to the sentiment contained in a statement made by Indigenous leaders who lent their support to carbon offset because it represented 'the largest opportunity in history to drive sustainable poverty alleviation in Aboriginal communities (Molitor and Tilmouth 2011 cited in Jackson et al. 2018 p. 874). A similar perspective is found in information on carbon farming provided by the Aboriginal Carbon Foundation (AbCF), a not for profit company:

'The vision of the AbCF is to catalyse life-changing, community prosperity through carbon farming. In doing this, our aim is to build wealth for Traditional Owners and non-Aboriginal carbon farmers implementing carbon projects that demonstrate environmental, social and cultural core-benefits through the ethical trade of carbon credits'.

Savanna burning is widely represented in the scientific literature as a program that, for example, 'sees an unprecedented meeting of interests relating to biodiversity protection, greenhouse gas abatement, and culturally appropriate economic opportunity for historically marginalized communities' (Anderson et al. 2012 p. 633). Some analysts regard its various aims and outcomes as commensurate (e.g. Baumber et al.

2019) and gloss over the significant complexity of Indigenous rationales and motivations for burning. Indigenous peoples burn for many reasons – to fulfil religious obligations and communicate with country, as hunting strategy, to protect valuable plants, and to ‘clean the country’ from overgrown vegetation (Petty et al. 2015). Program leaders like Whitehead et al. (2009) acknowledge this diversity and complexity to its goals is as an important issue, but observe that for the time being, the expectations of the mix of actors involved appear ‘compatible – at least in principle’ (p. 296). Woinarski et al. (2009) see concordance in objectives across interest groups, arguing that in the case of Arnhem Land, ‘reduction in fire frequency is a ‘no regrets’ policy for the plateau that can be achieved in part by supporting Indigenous fire managers to assert greater control’ (Woinarski et al. 2009). They are however cautious about the risks of conflating objectives, arguing that not all conservation goals can be met by restoration of customary fire management, ‘because some species are threatened by factors other than fire, or may benefit from fire regimes that differ from both presently weakly managed fire or reimposed traditional regimes’ (cited in Russell-Smith 2009 p.18).

Ansell et al. (2020) reflect briefly on wider public perceptions of the program, although they rely on one newspaper report only when claiming it is the its income-generating potential that receives the most attention from the Australian public. They point to a misapprehension that ‘the savanna burning method pays people to burn and that, as a result, more country is burnt more often’ (2020 p. 383).

Benefits are conceptualised in the savanna burning discourse in a particular manner with fire regime change portrayed as the primary or major benefit and other outcomes conceived as collateral benefits, or ‘co-benefits’. Evans and Russell-Smith (2020), for example, state that the WALFA landscape-scale fire management project was implemented ‘primarily for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from savanna wildfires’. Numerous other authors frame program outcomes in this way (see Corey et al. for example). Yet as Ansell et al (2020) explain ‘These co-benefits are arguably the reason why Aboriginal people are engaging with the carbon industry and also why the carbon credits they produce are highly valued by the carbon market’.

Scientists, managers and others (e.g. investors) may find this compartmentalised framing of benefits helpful in promoting the value and urgency of the program but it may also generate tensions given ‘it is impossible to ascribe one motive or rationale to Aboriginal fire management’ (Petty et al. 2015 p.147). In other NRM contexts, such as water management (see Jackson 2006), the diverse rights and interests of Indigenous peoples tend to be confined to the ‘culture box’, framed as ‘cultural values’, and omitted from regional economic decisions or mainstream environmental strategies. It is not likely that such a stark narrowing of scope could happen with savanna burning given the history of the program and the degree to which Indigenous peoples are participating, nonetheless it is a risk to watch.

Recognising the centrality of the social outcomes to the program, the Aboriginal Carbon Foundation uses the term ‘core-benefits’ rather than co-benefits, to describe the ‘most ‘meaningful outcomes’ (MacMurray et al. 2018 p. 10). It has also developed an alternative means of assessing or verifying these outcomes according to Indigenous-to-Indigenous Standard of peer-review (Aboriginal Carbon Foundation 2018). This approach ‘sees all verification of core-benefits conducted by a team of trained Aboriginal

experts, including Rangers and Traditional Owners from across the projects' (McMurray et al. 2018). McMurray et al. argue that this safeguard 'balances the role of third party verification with Aboriginal property rights and a requirement for the people with these responsibilities to have strong cultural and project-based knowledge'.

Relative to the large number of papers written by ecologists or natural resource management specialists, there are very few analyses of the savanna burning program by social researchers (see Fache and Moizo 2015; Jackson et al. 2017; Petty et al. 2015). Their contributions attend to issues that tend to be overlooked elsewhere, including asymmetries in power relations, disparities in knowledge traditions, competing views of what 'traditional' fire regimes were and should be, as well as the effects of institutionalisation of burning practices, codification of local knowledge and professionalization of Indigenous expertise. Petty et al. (2015) warn of the risks from state control of fire and technocratic institutions of management that have a tendency to 'replace the complexity and contingency of indigenous fire management with standardized goals' (p. 140). This form of management positions 'indigenous people as workers executing plans developed by others rather than as genuine partners in the design and implementation of management programs' (Petty et al. 2015 p. 140). Their case study from Kakadu National Park, adjacent to the WALFA region, shows how earlier efforts to institutionalise fire management within a conservation framework had changed the character of Aboriginal burning and led to a 'diminution of Aboriginal involvement in fire management from expertise to labour' (p. 149).

Although not writing about burning for carbon abatement, Verran examines collaborative episodes of burning involving scientists and Yolngu in a region of Arnhem Land , arguing that the burning that is prescribed (the scientific form of firing) and the firing that emerges from local relationships with country are different because they 'come to life in disparate epistemic regimes' (Verran 2002). While the parties do not share the same experience when burning, Verran (2002) sees in these collaborations a shared desire to improve both sorts of firing regimes. From her post-colonial perspective, savanna burning might represent a postcolonial moment in which a 'right story of sameness' (Verran 2002 p. 730) could redistribute power, and authority as well as increase the possibilities for co-operation while respecting differences.

Values and value articulation

Few papers describe in detail how the Program's leaders elicited, systematically analysed or prioritised values during the initial design process. There are however, numerous values embedded in the program logic and in the reasoning, justifications and assumptions made by its proponents. Furthermore, the market for carbon credits serves as a means by which savanna burning is valued. From the published literature it appears that PES was chosen as the mechanism to improve fire management because government funded programs were not addressing the problem of out of control, late season fires and that program proponents saw the need for new avenues for financing Indigenous NRM.

There have been no published accounts of opposition or resistance since program inception there are however reports of tensions in at least two participating communities. Fache and Moizo (2015) observed that fire regimes for GHG abatement were in 2009-10 a source of social tensions in one NT community in

Arnhem land. There, differences emerged 'between a fire regime conducted within a social, ceremonial, and symbolic framework and a fire regime implemented for conservation purposes following guidelines that were mainly defined outside the community' (p. 171). Tensions between community members over fire regimes are also reported from Cape York (Perry et al. 2019). Perry et al. (2018) identified an imbalance in access to land under the current arrangements, where the fire program supports rangers but not all traditional owners to travel out to customary estates. They also reported that 'conflicts have arisen when a traditional owner passed away and access [to Rangers] to large areas was restricted until areas were ritually opened up by those with the cultural authority to do so' (p. 29). Elders in that region spoke of 'traditional fire management' as a historical rather than continuing practice. Perry et al. (2018) conclude that 'Aboriginal decision-makers are now required to negotiate the contemporary pressures and responsibilities of contracted land management, but with limited economic support for cultural practices and the transfer of these skills and knowledge to succeeding generations'.

A number of analysts raised the potential for this kind of harm and others should the PES framework crowd out customary norms and ethical motivations (Jackson et al 2018.; Zander et al. 2013), too narrowly and rigidly prescribe management objectives (Whitehead et al. 2008), simplify and diminish Indigenous knowledge and practice (Petty et al. 2015), privilege technical expertise over local knowledge, or produce perverse biodiversity outcomes. Whitehead et al. (2008) point to possibility that commercial objectives may be compromised in the pursuit of multiple objectives (Whitehead et al. 2008) and Zander et al. (2013) suggest that the 'conditionality of rewards is likely to be compromised' because some outcomes are difficult and expensive to assess, especially in very remote regions' (p. 151). Zander et al. (2013) also identify the potential for conflict to arise from a program that has relied so successfully on meeting a number of objectives that may have so far been compatible without resolving differences in motivations. They argue that 'a failure to articulate the differences in motivation carries risks that incompatibilities will be ignored, tensions will fester, disenchantment grows and what remain to be highly promising schemes that may indeed have the potential to satisfy all parties could be abandoned' (p. 150). More is said about these issues in the outcome section.

In 2013, Zander et al. observed that there is little empirical evidence in the published literature that enunciates Indigenous views on the appropriate means of compensating or rewarding Indigenous effort and knowledge. The authors question the assumption in much of the Australian literature that 'indigenous people are willing, and probably enthusiastic, to accept conditional remuneration for activities providing ES. This may not be true. Many indigenous people 'look after country' and thereby provide ES as part of their daily activities without any compensation at all' (p.146). A survey of 60 Indigenous people in a regional town in Arnhem Land found that personal financial reward was not a major motivation for undertaking NRM activities (including being on country, teaching children). In part because ES provision is a communal activity, many respondents wanted monetary compensation only to cover the costs of providing the ES (equipment, vehicles etc). While this study suggests strong contrary motivation to personal gain, it also points to a difference in understanding where respondents equated 'looking after country' with 'being on country', the latter included attendance at ceremonies, including funerals. Zander et al. warn that 'funding agencies may look askance at providing funds that result in greater participation in funeral ceremonies when they had paid for burning.' (2013 p. 151).

In 2020, Ansell et al. affirmed the absence of Indigenous perspectives in the literature on co-benefits but argued that in the Arnhem Land savanna burning projects traditional owner input is widely sought in designing management activities, that authority figures are respected and customary processes are followed. Whereas Fache and Moizo (2015) point to a number of steps in which non-Indigenous actors external to the community of Ngukurr were influential, presumably unduly. For example, at Ngukurr community members did not contribute to the definition of the protocol for data collection, organise or supervise the aerial burns, or participate in the analysis of the data collected and their 'understanding of the process was fragmentary' (2015 p. 176). Working in the same community, McKemey et al. (2020) report that 'many of the Elders interviewed had little understanding of savannah burning for GHG abatement' (p. 7) and confirm many of the 'negative comments' discussed in Fache and Moizo (2015), although they do not cite that paper.

Initially, there was no systematic prioritisation process by which suitable project sites were selected. Rather, the requirement for approval of a major gas development in Darwin presented a serendipitous opportunity to make a 'very lateral connection' to regional fire management problems some 300 km east via a voluntary offset mechanism (Whitehead et al. 2009; Whitehead et al. 2008). There is no published evidence that the traditional owners of the site of the gas development received any carbon related payments. WALFA was initially funded through public subsidies with private funding later channelled through contracts that included a target for an average annual reduction of 100 000 tonnes CO₂-equivalent relative to a 10 year (1995 to 2004) baseline of the region's fire-derived GHG emissions. Over 17 years the developer will pay AU\$1 million per annum (indexed to 2006) for greenhouse-effective fire-management services (Whitehead et al. 2009). It does not purchase tradeable carbon credits from the WALFA project.

In the following years, Indigenous organisations were enrolled by their regional representative organisations (primarily Land Councils and the Northern Australia Indigenous Land and Sea Management Alliance). The loose coalition of actors came to see that with the right policy settings and funding models Indigenous people 'will play a major role in determining and implementing improved fire management for north Australia' (Russell-Smith et al. 2009 p. 15).

The literature demonstrates that an enormous effort went into developing the accounting methodology and proving up the processes by which local organisations could provide well validated credits (e.g. Russell-Smith et al. 2015). GHG emissions from savanna fires are now calculated using a quantitative measure, expressed in t.CO₂-e (Russell-Smith and Sangha 2018). Far less effort has been devoted to metrics or indicators for other outcomes that many anticipated would generate additional income for project proponents through the voluntary carbon market (Robinson et al. 2016). A number of papers report that methods to measure, monitor and account for the 'co-benefits' are still under consideration or development (see Russell-Smith et al. 2018; Ansell et al. 2020; Jackson and Palmer 2015). An early paper by Fitzsimons et al (2012) argued that to be able to refer with any certainty to social 'benefits in these fields, internationally accredited and recognized benchmarking and monitoring programmes are essential' (p. 53). The Aboriginal Carbon Foundation has developed a verification approach that it is currently rolling out in various communities.

Distribution of costs and benefits

Rights to burn vegetation had to be defined in order to clearly identify tradeable entitlements and so considerable effort went into developing supportive legal regimes. Much of the scientific literature is devoted to describing the effort involved in developing the carbon accounting methodology. Dore (2014) notes that navigating the land tenure requirements that had to be met to establish approved carbon projects was 'equally challenging' (p. 389). According to the CFI, any carbon credits earned from projects will not be issued unless the registered native title corporation for the group has set up a special native title registry account under the CFI, and credits are to be held in trust for all native title holders (Hansen 2015). Native title holders can 'transfer' their carbon sequestration right to a third party and allow them to undertake a project in relation to their land through a negotiated agreement process under the *Native Title Act*. Hansen argues that this provision may provide an opportunity for payment to native title holders who cannot otherwise carry out projects themselves. The land titling issues are regarded as a barrier to Indigenous participation in the carbon market (Hansen 2015), for instance current law excludes non-exclusive possession native title holders from participating in the CFI (Hansen 2015). In the Northern Territory, the majority of its native title determinations are non-exclusive determinations over pastoral leases. The needs of those groups will require further negotiation with governments and landholders, particularly graziers (O'Donnell 2013).

Benefits

Compensation/payments

Savanna burning projects currently generate A\$30m per year (Russell-Smith and Sangha 2018). Purchasers of carbon credits from Indigenous lands include petrochemical companies such as Woodside and Caltex, airlines such as Qantas, but also the Australian government, which has bought contracts for roughly AUD\$200 million of carbon credits from savanna burning since 2013 (Neale et al. 2019).

Payments from carbon trades are made to Aboriginal corporations who also receive funding support for land management programs from government agencies and other sources. It appears that the primary form of compensation for the provision of GHG abatement is the provision of salaries for rangers, which succeeded earlier forms of payment for NRM work but at higher rates (Zander et al. 2014). There is little commentary on distributional mechanisms or issues, although in 2008, Whitehead et al. observed that the levels of emissions-related funding within the WALFA project was not sufficient to meet all employment and other costs of the fire work by the Indigenous ranger groups.

Whitehead et al. (2009) comment on the criteria used in the WALFA case, noting a tension between the fee for service model of PES vs the royalty payment system established by the *Aboriginal Land Rights Act 1976*, and the need for decisions about participation and benefit-sharing to be entirely clear as the sector grows:

The Northern Land Council, representing traditional landowners, has a particular obligation to ensure that landowners share incomes derived from management of and use of resources from their lands. But the

prevailing ethos among many participants is that income should be distributed entirely on active contributions to meeting targets in fire mitigation. Indeed, it may be argued that landowners are receiving services that may exceed in value any 'royalties' (rent) that might otherwise be payable for any associated commercial activity on their lands (p. 297).

These authors also call for internal mechanisms for negotiation and resolution of disputes about participation, benefit-sharing, and compensation and point to customary institutions as a place to start. Such work should generate rules to identify activities that can legitimately be treated as contributing to creation of fire-abatement credits, including ritual activity (see also Zander et al. 2013).

Outcomes

Savanna burning methodologies have abated more than 4 million tonnes of Co2 equivalent, principally through the application of low intensity dry season burning (Lynch et al. 2018). The reporting of outcomes is patchy with far more attention given in the published literature to Arnhem Land (NT) than other regions. For instance, Ansell et al. (2020) conclude that the adoption of the savanna burning method has been the direct cause of the recent positive changes in fire management regimes in Arnhem Land, 'delivering outstanding fire management results' (p. 381). Ansell et al. (2020) however describe the systems ranger groups follow in Arnhem Land by which Aboriginal organisations set fire management objectives, explaining that of the nine Aboriginal ranger groups operating the fire projects in Arnhem Land (NT), eight groups are covered by seven detailed operational plans of management. Ansell et al. (2020) note that five of the seven management plans in Arnhem Land have been undertaken using the HCP framework. Ranger groups in this region are using fire for a number of purposes with each fire management strategy relating to several fire management goals (Ansell et al. 2020 p. 375), noting that 'The single strategy that was consistent across all seven plans was that 'Burning is directed by Traditional Owners'. Protecting biodiversity was listed as a goal in 4 of the 7 planning documents and producing a carbon abatement in only 3. The authors argue their results demonstrate that abatement does not 'drive' the fire programs of Rangers.

According to the Aboriginal Carbon Foundation, many corporations are interested in buying ACCUs with 'environmental, social and cultural core-benefits at approximately \$16-\$20 per tonne to meet their UN SDGs, Reconciliation Action Plans and/or Corporate Social Responsibility goals' (McMurray et al. 2018). Co-benefits are marketed to voluntary investors alongside the carbon credits in a manner typical of certified commodity promotion (see Jackson et al. 2018). In the case of Fish River station, the proponent, the Indigenous Land Corporation, undertook a 'well publicised expression of interest process promoting the valuable cultural, social and biodiversity co-benefits associated with the project' (Walton and Fitzsimons 2015). Successful bids were identified based on three key criteria: the price; the organisation's compatibility with Indigenous values; and how the company proposed to market the sale. The first two tranches of credits were sold to Caltex Australia for more than \$22/t, a high price that the authors argue recognised the 'genuine market value of the co-benefits produced by the project' (Walton and Fitzsimons 2015). In that case, all revenue from sale of credits was to be invested in land management activities, including employment and training for traditional owners (Walton and Fitzsimons 2015). Since those

figures were published Fleming et al. (2019) came to the view that expectations that market demand would be sufficient to drive an

increasing price for carbon and catalyse further participation by the land sector in carbon programmes had not been realised. Then the price was fluctuating around \$13 per ACCU.

Social outcomes: Similarly, evaluations of social outcomes are patchy and more difficult to describe precisely in comparison to sales of credits that are publicly reported, or even ecological impacts that receive more systematic scientific attention. Monitoring is undertaken on a project basis to account for funds provided by government and there is now strong interest in verification processes that are run by Aboriginal people (see McMurray et al. 2018). One of the lead Indigenous organisations, NAILSMA had plans to implement a social benchmarking process in 2012 that were supported by The Nature Conservancy (Fitzsimons et al.). A 2012 paper identified the need to benchmark rates of Indigenous ownership and the extent to which customary knowledge is deployed. It identified a need for baseline 'information mapping' to include land use and interest, tenure type /extent, cultural and economic resource values, demography, infrastructure, and cultural and heritage site identification and condition, and to integrate these measures with biodiversity monitoring. The intention was to synthesise a 'range of benchmarking activities focused on social and biodiversity issues across six proposed regional projects'. There are no further published accounts of social impact monitoring from this program (beyond that reported by Ansell et al. 2020). In 2017, the five Arnhem Land projects recorded the employment of 316 Aboriginal people to undertake the actual burning and firefighting work (Ansell et al. 2020). The paper by Ansell et al. notes that 'Even further employment is achieved with many groups investing carbon credit revenue into non-fire related land management employment'. Interestingly, the same paper states that reporting on cultural site protection is out of scope, although it does note that firing resulted in many social events for school age children and elders. For example, in 2016, Mimal Land Management Aboriginal Corporation and Arafura Swamp Rangers Aboriginal Corporation supported the performance of a fire ceremony that had not been performed for more than 40 years (Ansell 2020).

There are clear political co-benefits that remain under appreciated. Jackson and Barber define these as co-benefits that pertain to systems of governance and the exercise of authority (2017). Successful natural and cultural resource management requires a range of skills and generates a range of benefits that relate to resource rights, governance, autonomy, self-empowerment, self-determination, and recognition. Having been so closely involved in program development specialist, peak Indigenous organisations are now highly knowledgeable about GHG abatement methodologies and aspects of carbon governance. They have had a direct impact on shaping the domestic arrangements that seek reductions in GHG from landscape management and are developing expertise in the offset industry (see for example, the Aboriginal Carbon Foundation (McMurray et al. 2018). Yet few have undertaken research to document, or evaluate these improvements or associated dis-benefits. Robinson et al. (2016) surveyed 128 Indigenous agencies and representative bodies that could be involved in carbon offset projects across Australia and found that all 'framed their interest in participating in carbon offset projects in terms of their communities' demands for control over land, management capability and regional development

pathways to address Indigenous disadvantage’ (p. 131). These authors note that co-benefit standards do not currently recognise the diversity of motivations for engaging in carbon offsetting.

Ecological outcomes: Again, published accounts relating to outcomes are skewed towards the Northern Territory, where the scientific effort has been most intense. Reports from Arnhem Land show improvements in fire management on ecological measures (as well as others), where ‘smaller fires have become more numerous and longer unburnt areas appear to be increasing’ (Ansell et al. 2020). Ansell et al. (2020) state that some Aboriginal ranger groups have commenced ambitious research and monitoring projects to examine the biodiversity outcomes (Ansell et al. 2020). Prior to commencement of the project, 75% of Fish River Station (NT) burnt every year. Since the introduction of planned early dry season burning, the total area of the property burnt has reduced to 40% and the proportion of the property burnt in the late dry season has reduced from 36% to 1% (Walton and Fitzsimons 2015).

Methodology and literature

We used two search engines to identify 72 papers, 2 books (*Carbon Accounting and Savanna Fire Management 2015 and Fire Management in North Australian Savannas 2009*) and 2 book chapters relating to Indigenous peoples, livelihoods, multiple benefits, ecosystem services, and PES. We first searched Google Scholar using the terms ‘savanna burning carbon Australia’ for articles published since 2000. This yielded 1060 results. We then manually excluded papers relating only to carbon processes, carbon accounting, fire behaviour, biodiversity benefits, non-Indigenous carbon farming, or the carbon consumption profiles of Indigenous communities (leaving 68 papers, 2 books and two book chapters). We then conducted four Web of Science searches for articles since 2000 finding 4 more:

1. Carbon offsets* Australia* fire* - this generated 9 relevant articles – 6 not identified through the Google Search but not relevant.
2. Carbon offsets* Australia *co-benefits - this generated 2 new papers – one of which was relevant.
3. Indigenous* fire* Australia* carbon* - this generated 31 papers – 15 new. Only two of those were relevant.
4. Payment for ecosystem services* fire* Indigenous* Australia – this generated 8 – 2 new Only one was relevant.

Additional literature was identified through citations in reviewed articles and through personal networks (e.g. 12 papers relating primarily to social and cultural co-benefits and one PhD thesis), as well as ‘grey’ literature such as government reports.

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References

Aboriginal Carbon Foundation 2019. Core Benefits Verification Framework: For the environmental, social and cultural values of Aboriginal carbon farming

Altman, J., and S. Kerins, eds. 2012. *People on country: Vital landscapes, indigenous futures*. Sydney: The Federation Press

Anderson, A., Cook, G and D. Williams. 2012 Commentary, Savanna burning: The ecology and economy of fire in tropical savannas, *Austral Ecology* 37, 633.

Barber, S. and S. Jackson 2017. Identifying and categorizing co-benefits in state-supported Australian indigenous environmental management programs: International research implications. *Ecology and Society* 22 (2):11.

Baumber, A., Metternicht, G. et al. 2019 Promoting co-benefits of carbon farming in Oceania: Applying and adapting approaches and metrics from existing market-based schemes, *Ecosystem Services* 39, 100982.

Bowman, D. 1998 Tansley Review No. 101: The impact of Aboriginal landscape burning on the Australian biota, *New Phytologist* 140, 385-410.

Clarkson C, Jacobs Z, Marwick B, Fullagar R, Wallis L, Smith M, Roberts RG, Hayes E, Lowe K, Carah X, Florin SA, McNeil J, Cox D, Arnold LJ, Hua Q, Huntley J, Brand HEA, Manne T, Fairbairn A, Shulmeister J, Lyle L, Salinas M, Page M, Connell K, Park G, Norman K, Murphy T, Pardoe C (2017) Human occupation of northern Australia by 65,000 years ago. *Nature* **547**, 306–310. doi:10.1038/NATURE22968

Cook, G.D, S. Jackson and R.J. Williams 2012. A revolution in northern Australian fire management: recognition of Indigenous knowledge, practice and management, in Bradstock, R., Gill, A. M. and R. Williams (Eds) *Flammable Australia: Fire Regimes, Biodiversity and Ecosystems in a Changing World*, CSIRO Publishing, Melbourne: 293-306.

Cook GD, Richards AE, Liedloff AC, Levick SR, Meyer CP (Mick). 2020. *Supporting savanna fire management through carbon farming*. CSIRO, Winnellie, NT.

Corey et al. 2018 Better biodiversity accounting is needed to prevent bioperversity and maximize co-benefits from savanna burning

- Conservation Measures Partnership (2018) The open standards for the practice of conservation. Available at <http://cmp-openstandards.org/>.
- Duff, G., Garnett, D. et al. 2009. A collaborative design to adaptively manage for landscape sustainability in north Australia: lessons from a decade of cooperative research, *Landscape Ecology* 24, 1135–1143.
- Evans, J. and J. Russell-Smith 2020. Delivering effective savanna fire management for defined biodiversity conservation outcomes: an Arnhem Land case study, *International Journal of Wildland Fire* 29, 386–400.
- Evans, M., 2018. Effective incentives for reforestation: lessons from Australia’s carbon farming policies. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 32, 38–45.
- Fache, E. and B. Moizo 2015. Do Burning Practices Contribute To Caring For Country? Contemporary Uses of Fire For Conservation Purposes In Indigenous Australia, *Journal of Ethnobiology* 35(1): 163–182.
- Fitzsimons, J. et al. 2012 Insights into the biodiversity and social benchmarking components of the Northern Australian fire management and carbon abatement programmes
- Fleming, A., Stitzlein, C., Jakku, E. and S. Fielke 2019. Missed opportunity? Framing actions around co-benefits for carbon mitigation in Australian agriculture, *Land Use Policy*, 85, 230–238.
- Hansen, L. 2015 Carbon in Country: Legal Pathways and Barriers to Indigenous Participation in Australia’s Carbon Market Through Savanna Fire Management Under the Carbon Farming Initiative. Working Paper No 3, Centre for Resources, Energy and Environmental Law, University of Melbourne
- Heiner, M. et al. 2019 Moving from reactive to proactive development planning to conserve Indigenous community and biodiversity values, *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 74 (2019) 1–13
- Jackson, S., Stoeckl, N., Straton, A. and O. Stanley 2008. The changing value of Australian tropical rivers, *Geographical Research* 46(3): 275-290.
- Jackson, S. and L. Palmer 2015. Reconceptualising ecosystems services: Possibilities for cultivating and valuing the ethics and practices of care. *Progress in Human Geography* 39(2): 122–145.
- Jackson, S., Palmer, L. Macdonald, F. and A. Bumpus 2017. Cultures of carbon and the logic of care: The possibilities of carbon enrichment and its cultural signature. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* 107: 867-882.
- Langton, M. 1998. Burning Issues: Emerging Environmental Issues for Indigenous peoples in Northern Australia, CINCRM, Northern Territory University.

- Lipsett-Moore, G., Wolffe, N. and E. Game 2018 Emissions mitigation opportunities for savannah countries from early dry season fire management, *Nature Communications* 9, 2247.
- Luckert, L., B. Campbell, J. T. Gorman and S. T. Garnett (Eds), *Investing in Indigenous Natural Resources Management*, CDU Press, Darwin: 53-61.
- Lynch, D., Russell-Smith, J, Edwards, A., Evans, J. and C. Yates 2018 Incentivising fire management in Pindan (Acacia shrubland): A proposed fuel type for Australia's Savanna burning greenhouse gas emissions abatement methodology. *Ecological Management & Restoration*.
- Marum, J. 2014 Network Governance in Community Development: Structures and Dynamics in the Northern Territory, Australia, PhD Thesis, Charles Darwin University, Darwin.
- McDonald, F. 2013. The Carbon Farming Initiative (CFI) and indigenous community-based natural and cultural resource management: A case study of the Fish River Savanna Burning Methodology Project. Master's thesis, School of Geography, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Australia.
- McKemeey, M., Ens, E., Yugul Mangi Rangers, Costello, O. and N. Reid 2020. Indigenous knowledge and seasonal calendar inform adaptive savanna burning in Northern Australia, *Sustainability*, 12, 995.
- McMurray L., Foley, R. and C. O'Sullivan 2018. An Indigenous 'right way' environmental, social and cultural core-benefits verification standard. Available at <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/518cb4d9e4b082221e51d3b8/t/5b32ee4ef950b7530a12bd6f/1530064467248/AbCFb+Edinburghhp2018ppaperppublicpMarchp2018.pdf> [Verified 11 August 2020].
- Moura. L., Scariot, A., Schmidt, I., Beatty, R. and J. Russell-Smith 2019. The legacy of colonial fire management policies on traditional livelihoods and ecological sustainability in savannas: Impacts, consequences, new directions. *Journal of Environmental Management* 232, 600–606.
- Neale, T., Zahara, A. and W. Smith 2019. An Eternal Flame: The Elemental Governance of Wildfire's Pasts, Presents and Futures. *Cultural Studies Review*, 25, <https://doi.org/10.5130/csr.v25i2.6886>
- O'Donnell, M. 2013 Native title – a right to burn and fire the land? Savanna burning and the Carbon Fund Initiative in the Northern Territory, *Environment Planning and Law Journal*, 30, 553- 559.
- Perry, J., Sinclair, M., Wikmunea, H, Wolmby, S., Martin, D. and B Martin 2018. The divergence of traditional Aboriginal and contemporary fire management practices on Wik traditional lands, Cape York Peninsula, Northern Australia, *Ecological Management and Restoration*, 19, 24-31.
- Petty, A., de Koninck, V. and B. Orlove 2015. Cleaning, Protecting, or Abating? Making Indigenous Fire Management "Work" in Northern Australia, *Journal of Ethnobiology*, 35(1): 140-162.

- Preece, L., van Oosterzee, P., et al. 2016. Ecosystem service valuation reinforces world class value of Cape York Peninsula's ecosystems but environment and indigenous people lose out, *Ecosystem Services* 18 154–164
- Robinson, C., Renwick, A., May, T., Gerrard, E., Foley, R., Battaglia, M., Possingham, H., Griggs, D. and D. Walker 2016. Indigenous benefits and carbon offset schemes: An Australian case study. *Environmental Science & Policy* 56, 129–134.
- Russell-Smith, J., Whitehead, P. and P. Cooke 2009 Introduction to Culture, Ecology and Economy of Fire Management in North Australian Savannas: Rekindling the Wurrk Tradition, CSIRO, Melbourne.
- Russell-Smith, J., G. Cook, P. Cooke, A. Edwards, M. Lendrum, C. Meyer, and P. Whitehead. 2013. Managing fire regimes in north Australian savannas: Applying Aboriginal approaches to contemporary global problems. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 11 (1): e55–e63.
- Russell-Smith, J., Murphy, B., Edwards, A. and C. Meyer 2015. Carbon Accounting and Savanna Fire Management, CSIRO: Melbourne
- Russell-Smith, J. and K. Sangha 2018. Emerging opportunities for developing a diversified land sector economy in Australia's northern savannas, *The Rangeland Journal*, 2018, 40, 315–330
- Russell-Smith, J., Edwards, A., Sangha, K., Yates, C. and M. Gardener 2020. Challenges for prescribed fire management in Australia's fire-prone rangelands – the example of the Northern Territory, *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, 29, 339–353
- Walton, N. and J. Fitzsimons 2015. Payment for ecosystem services in practice – savanna burning and carbon abatement at Fish River, northern Australia. In Figgis, P., Mackay, B., Fitzsimons, J. Irving, J., Clark P (eds) *Valuing Nature: Protected Areas and Ecosystem Services*. Australian Committee for IUCN, Sydney.
- Whitehead, P., Bowman, D., Preece, N., Fraser, F. and P. Cooke 2003 Customary use of fire by Indigenous peoples in northern Australia: its contemporary role in savannah management, *International Journal of Wildland Fire* 12, 415-425.
- Whitehead, P., Purdon, P., Russell-Smith, J. Cooke, P., S. Sutton 2008. The Management Of Climate Change Through Prescribed Savanna Burning: Emerging Contributions Of Indigenous People In Northern Australia. *Public Administration and Development* 28, 374–385.
- Whitehead, P. et al. 2009. The West Arnhem Land Fire Abatement (WALFA) project: The institutional environment and its implications, In Russell-Smith, J., Whitehead, P. and P. Cooke 2009 Introduction to Culture, Ecology and Economy of Fire Management in North Australian Savannas: Rekindling the Wurrk Tradition, CSIRO, Melbourne: 287-

- Williams, R., Carter, J. et al. 2005. Carbon accounting, land management, science and policy uncertainty in Australian savannah landscapes: Introduction and overview. *Australian Journal of Botany* 53, 583-588.
- Woinarski, J., Mackay, B., Nix, H. and B. Traill 2007. *The nature of northern Australia: Its natural values, ecological processes and future prospects*. ANU E-Press, Canberra.
- Woinarski, J.C.Z., Legge, S., Fitzsimons, J.A., Traill, B.J., Burbidge, A.A., Fisher, A., Firth, R.S.C., Gordon, I.J., Griffiths, A.D., Johnson, C., McKenzie, N.L., Palmer, C., Radford, I., Rankmore, B., Ritchie, E., Ward, S., Ziembicki, M., 2011. The disappearing mammal fauna of northern Australia: context, cause and response. *Conserv. Lett.* 4, 192–201.
- Yirbarbuk, D. 1998. Notes on traditional use of fire on upper Cadell River, In Langton, M. *Burning Issues: Emerging Environmental Issues for Indigenous peoples in Northern Australia*, pp 1-6., CINCRM, Northern Territory University.
- Yibarbuk D, Whitehead PJ, Russell-Smith J, Jackson D, Godjuwa C, Fisher A, Cooke P, Choquenot D, Bowman DMJS (2001) Fire ecology and Aboriginal land management in central Arnhem Land, northern Australia: a tradition of ecosystem management. *Journal of Biogeography* 28, 325–343.
- Zander, K.K., Garnett, S.T., 2011. The economic value of environmental services on Indigenous-held lands in Australia. *PLoS One* 6 (8), e23154.
- Zander, K., Dunnett, D., Brown, C., Campion, O. and S Garnett 2013. Rewards for providing environmental services — Where Indigenous Australians' and western perspectives collide. *Ecological Economics* 87 145–154

Case Study: 'Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action, Mongolia'.

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Background and context

The Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action (PCCA) programme was established at three sites in rural Mongolia from 2015. These sites cover some 78,000ha in total and are home to some 130 herding households (PDD, 2015). The sites are located in mountain, steppe and desert steppe environments respectively, with households belonging to one of three herder groups in these regions (ibid). As a programme located in rangeland, rather than the more typical forested environments, this programme rewards provision of a range of ecosystem services, centred on carbon sequestration in soils through improved land use management, biodiversity conservation and habitat provision. In accordance with the Plan Vivo Standard (2013), under which the project is certified, an important characteristic of PCCA is that it adopts a holistic, tripartite 'carbon+' approach to PES and thus also encompasses livelihood/ wellbeing, and herders' participation in biodiversity governance (Upton, 2020; PDD, 2015). Site-specific management plans and targets were co-developed with herding communities for each site. Within the three herder groups, participation in PCCA represented some 90% of group membership at the time of writing. In accordance with Plan Vivo (PV) Standards and procedures, compensation to ES providers is derived from sales of resultant PV certificates (each equivalent to 1 tonne CO₂ sequestered or avoided carbon emissions, plus co-benefits set out above) in the voluntary carbon market (PV, 2013). Again in accordance with the PV model, a minimum of 60% of funds derived from certificate sales must be returned to participating communities, or ES providers, with the remainder available to project coordinators for management, coordination and monitoring costs (PV, 2013). In the case of PCCA, the agreed benefit sharing mechanism allocates 70% of funds to participating communities (PDD, 2015).

Biophysical and socio-economic conditions vary across the three sites, with these being deliberately selected by PCCA developers to encompass diverse local ecologies and livelihood conditions. Key commonalities are the predominance of extensive grassland areas and of (to some degree) mobile livestock herding as a central livelihood strategy. Ongoing grassland degradation, variously linked to climate change and variability, stocking rates and increasing sedentarisation also constitute commonalities between sites (PDD, 2015). Prior to the inception of PCCA, poverty levels and inequality were also recorded as high in a baseline survey at all three sites. Specifically, the majority of households' income fell below monthly averages for rural households, according to government statistics, whilst households' own participatory evaluation of wealth status indicated the predominance of average or below average livelihoods (ibid).

Pastureland tenure in Mongolia continues to preclude outright private ownership of grazing land. The 2002 Land Law remains a key piece of legislation under which pastureland remains officially in state

ownership, albeit operating to some degree as a de facto commons. Within the pastoral landscape, households derive rights to different seasonal pastures on the basis of a range of complex and intersecting claims, typically based on possession of particular winter and spring campsites and inferred rights to surrounding pastures, traditional use of other seasonal pastures, and membership of particular administrative divisions, supported by the provisions of the Land Law. This Law also makes provision for allocation of particular seasonal grazing areas to herder groups, such as the three participating in PCCA, through agreements with local administrations. However, these remain use rights, rather than outright ownership (Upton, 2020; PDD, 2015).

The majority of households at all PCCA case study sites have allocated winter and/or spring campsites, either individually, or as small kinship-based groups (*khot ail*). Grazing of other seasonal pastures typically follows established temporal and geographical patterns, grounded in custom, but also reflecting annual pasture use planning by the group and by local administrations, as well as households' own capacity and need for mobility. Flexibility, for example linked to extreme weather events, also remains a key feature of Mongolian pastoralism, with the practice of *otor* (periodic long distance migration in search of grazing) still widespread. This poses challenges for PES schemes, in relation to non-exclusivity of tenure and prospects for leakage.

As highlighted by Addison et al (2020), Mongolian steppe/ rangelands may be considered a 'non colonial context', albeit with legacies of the Soviet-era *nedgel* (collective) period still arguably resonating to some extent in particular areas and in relation to issues of herders' status and wealth. These legacies are not explored in any detail, or highlighted as pertinent factors, in available literature for the PCCA case study.

As highlighted above, the 2002 Land Law remains a key piece of legislation shaping pasture governance, with key provisions around annual pasture management and planning, and allocation of campsites enacted through devolved *bag* (sub district) and *soum* (district) administrative structures (Upton, 2020). Herder groups, such as those at the core of PCCA are relatively recent institutional and organisational innovations, reflecting some two decades of largely donor-led attempts to implement various forms of community-based rangeland management and/or conservation, often allied with a sustainable livelihoods agenda (ibid). Resultant groups typically constitute some 10-40 herding households, who are geographically proximate and share pastures in at least some seasons, and to varying degrees reflect preceding traditional, informal kinship-based and geographical groupings (ibid, PDD). The three PCCA groups were established between 2003 and 2007 by MSRM or GTZ (Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit - German Technical Cooperation Agency) and thus long predate the emergence of PCCA. A number of herder groups, including these three, have agreed pasture use contracts with local *soum* administrations, which ostensibly recognize their group rights to local pasture areas.

Problematization and framing

PCCA arose directly from a preceding Darwin Initiative funded research project, 'Values and Valuation: New Approaches to Conservation in Mongolia', (2012-2015) (hereafter referred to as the 'Darwin project'). Available sources indicate that key aims of supporting and enhancing herders' livelihoods and well-being, whilst contributing to the protection of a globally important biodiversity heritage, were

established as part of this Darwin project and subsequently fed into PCCA (Upton, 2020, PDD, 2015). Planning for PES/ Plan Vivo activities also featured in the latter stages of the Darwin project (PDD, 2015). Sources also highlight a wider Mongolian context in which degradation of rangelands, loss of biodiversity, climate change and rural poverty constituted key national concerns (PDD, 2015). Upton (2020:230) furthermore maps out a national policy context in which *'ES-based planning and 'appropriate' valuation of biodiversity and ES [have] become a recent priority for the Mongolian government'*, but wherein monetary valuation of provisioning services have tended to predominate to date. The development of PCCA is thus presented as an enactment of *'radical pragmatism'* (after Kallis et al., 2013, cited in Upton, 2020), through seeking to ensure that local agency and (non- economic) values are recognised and reflected in any resultant ES-based interventions (ibid). In terms of specific problem definition in participating sites, local administration data and statistics are used to identify recent increases in livestock numbers, trends in pasture degradation and *'overgrazing'* and herders' livelihood status, with Darwin project baseline data also used to assess the latter (PDD, 2015). This includes herders' own participatory wealth status evaluations (ibid). PCCA activities, as developed during the Darwin project and linked to herders' own problem evaluations and priorities, are described as being derived from a lengthy participatory planning process, facilitated by MSRM (ibid). As stated by Upton (2020:239). *'these did not identify radically new areas of activity, but in the main highlighted a range of established challenges for which herders were seeking new ideas and forms of support in their resolution...[e.g.] greater mobility between seasonal pastures and better coordination of pasture use; development of hayfields; maintenance and repair of key infrastructure ... and support in processing and marketing of livestock products'*. Thus, in the case of PCCA, environmental problems were initially defined through attention to the wider, national context, but supported with available local government data and statistics for case study sites. The specifics of problems and activities were then co-developed by herders in the participating herder groups, with support from MSRM (ibid). The focus on herder groups inevitably excludes herders outwith the selected groups from direct involvement in planning and value articulation as part of the Darwin/ PCCA process, and reflects Plan Vivo (PV) requirements, as the PCCA accrediting agency, for local community groups and institutions to be at the core of all PV projects (PV, 2013). It is worth noting in this context that this proviso challenges the predominance of private property rights as a basis for inclusion/ exclusion in many PES schemes, the subject of much criticism (Upton, 2020). It is also notable that PCCA makes provision for non-participating households to raise any issues or grievances through established local meetings and channels for discussion and decision-making, with these to be reported back to MSRM and PV, should they arise (PDD, 2015). No such grievances have been reported to date (Upton, 2020).

The decision to develop a PES scheme as a way of tackling some of the interlinked challenges identified was made at a number of levels. The ambition to develop a community-based PES was articulated as part of the underpinning Darwin project, and within the wider context of ES-based planning and emergent PES approaches in Mongolia (Upton, 2020; PDD, 2015). However, the specific nature of and decision to move forward with a PES scheme was derived from a lengthy series of meetings between MSRM and local herder groups during the Darwin project (Upton, 2020). Sources indicate these herder groups and their members had an established track record of strategic engagement with donor/ research projects and schemes, with the potential PES scheme constituting another potential *'surface of engagement'*, albeit without crowding out other approaches to tackling environmental and livelihood challenges (ibid). Carbon

sequestration and related PES were an unfamiliar concept to most members, yet herder groups self-selected to become part of the PCCA, based on the scope to develop a range of potentially beneficial activities under this PES umbrella (ibid). At the core of the PCCA scheme was the serendipitous alignment between carbon sequestration, largely valued by external actors and by the PV Standard itself, and the herders' own desire to enhance herd management and mobility (Addison et al., 2020; Upton, 2020). Deployment of the CENTURY model enabled links to be identified between these diverse values and priorities, with changes in livestock mobility and stocking rates linked to changes in soil carbon (ibid). According to Addison et al (2020:8) this enabled '*exploit(ation) of an alignment between pastoralist livelihood aspirations unrelated to carbon, and the carbon related values of the international community*'. As highlighted above, the initial PCCA design thus focused on carbon sequestration and aspects of biodiversity conservation, linked to a range of livelihood and pasture management activities, as identified by participating herder groups. The latter were identified as ES providers by the very nature of the PV process, wherein the focus is on community groups developing their own Plan Vivo and receiving compensation through the voluntary carbon market (PV Standard, 2013). Although not specifically stated in available sources, beneficiaries may thus be considered as encompassing the purchasers of these certificates (e.g. travel companies, resellers, private individuals), those deriving aesthetic and economic benefit from these grassland landscapes (e.g. tourists, travel companies, as well as livestock producers) and globally from carbon sequestration, non-human natures through species and habitat conservation, and of course the herders themselves, for whom well-managed and cherished landscapes underpin livelihoods and well-being.

Values and value articulation

As highlighted above, initial planning for PCCA proceeded through a series of workshops with participating herder groups, facilitated by MSRM and as part of the underpinning Darwin project (PDD, 2015). This latter source makes little reference to specific methods for value articulation, but rather focuses on herders' agency in identifying preferred activities and in working with MSRM to agree appropriate phasing of and indicators for these activities over the duration of PCCA (ibid). These preferred activities, expressive of herders' underpinning values and priorities, ranged from pasture management (e.g. improved mobility and/or stocking rates; linked as highlighted above to carbon sequestration in soils), to biodiversity conservation (including habitat/ species protection and herders' enhanced participation in governance) and livelihood/ risk management issues (e.g. repair of infrastructure such as wells and shelters; processing of livestock products) (ibid). Addison et al (2020) also suggest a distinction between herders' visions and values in Mongolia, albeit with the latter underpinning the former and shaping perceptions of locally meaningful livelihoods and futures. This understanding is reflected in the participatory wellbeing indicator developed with herders in Darwin/ PCCA, whereby not only socio- economic considerations, but local landscapes, biodiversity and pasture management informed herders' notions of wellbeing. Upton (2020) provides further exposition of links between herders' values and preferred activities and of the techniques deployed for elucidating the former. Specifically, the initial design process under the Darwin project, from 2012-2015, incorporated household surveys and in-depth interviews, social values mapping and choice modelling, as determined by the UK/ Mongolian research team. Through the latter two methods in particular, '*Mongolian researchers worked with herders to explore the latter's perceptions and*

values around the local environment and non-human nature, deploying terms and categories such as baigal (nature), baigal orchnoo hairlan hamgaalah (protecting the environment) and exploring the ways in which they valued and related to nature' (Upton, 2020:234). It is notable that non-emic categories and concepts such as 'ES' and 'biodiversity' were not used directly in these encounters, but only applied later in data analysis and in relation to a wider ES framework (ibid). One gap here is the absence of more detailed published accounts of the application of these social values mapping and choice modelling methods within participating herder groups, of negotiations, tensions and discussions therein, and of how these factors then resulted in specific value articulations. It appears, however, that the design of the PCCA scheme sought to prioritise values and worldviews of the herding communities, albeit inevitably shaped and constrained to some degree by non-local values underpinning aspects of the PV Standard, and the demands of buyers in the voluntary carbon market. Specifically, as previously noted, concerns with carbon sequestration, at the core of the PV Standard and many purchasers' requirements, had little interest for herders. Rather, their values revolved around preferences and principles incorporating utilitarian values (e.g. for provisioning ES: grassland, clean water etc.), but also extending beyond these to highlight the importance of conservation care and stewardship and their own roles and responsibilities therein (ibid). According to Upton (2020: 240) during the lengthy planning process *'herders seized the opportunity to effectively foreground diverse ontologies, through further incorporating their own values and conservation care labour as the 'valued stock''*. Notions of reciprocity, responsibility to non-human natures and affective socio-ecological relations in turn underpinned these values, and formed the starting point for development of a locally co-constituted manifestation of PES (ibid). As acknowledged therein, these considerations co-existed in some tension with herders' pragmatic concerns with securing their livelihoods. The activities developed and agreed by herders under PCCA thus reflect a balance of endogenous values and livelihood priorities, anchored to external values primarily through the alignment of enhanced pastoral mobility and reduced grazing pressure with carbon sequestration in soils. The requirements of the PV Standard (2013) also inevitably shaped the final form of PCCA, although this emphasises recognition of local priorities and values, as did Darwin Initiative's requirements around admissible, conservation-sensitive activities (PDD, 2015).

To date, there is no published evidence of contestation around the process, values or resultant trade-offs.

Distribution of costs and benefits

Benefits and compensation

As highlighted in the PCCA Project Design Document (PDD, 2015), compensation is through monetary payments to participating herding communities, based on sales of PV certificates (each equivalent to 1 tonne sequestered carbon/ avoided carbon emissions) and representing Verified Emissions Reductions (VERs) to purchasers in the voluntary carbon market. The Plan Vivo Standard (PV, 2013) sets a basic requirement by which at least 60% of the income from such sales must be returned to participating communities, with the remainder available to in-country project managers/ coordinators (in this case MSRM) for administration and monitoring of the scheme. In the case of PCCA, 70% of the value of sales are returned to herders, in excess of the 60% minimum, with MSRM retaining 30% to cover management,

monitoring and reporting. According to Upton (2020) and PDD (2015), each of the participating herder groups, all of which pre-dated PCCA, had established structures and procedures, for example elected leaders and agreed mechanisms for electing new ones, and group bank accounts. The existence of such established community organisations with clear governance and operational procedures is a pre-requisite for PV accreditation (PV, 2013). As determined in initial PES agreements for PCCA and based on the groups' own stated preferences, funds were distributed by MSRM to the groups' accounts with these then shared equally between participating households, rather than being allocated on needs-based or other criteria (Upton, 2020; PDD, 2015). Available published sources do not present specific details of the intra-group decision-making processes around this issue of benefit distribution, but only the outcome of this process. This may be seen as a gap, although Annex 7 of the PDD does present records and images of a number of participatory workshops with herder groups in which the details of PCCA were developed and discussed (PDD, 2015). Sources indicate that at the end of Phase 1 of PCCA (2015-2019), distribution and compensation were perceived as just, at least in that herders reflected positively on the contributions of the scheme and with all groups wishing to continue into a second commitment period (Phase 2), with no recorded complaints or challenges (Upton, 2020). It is also evident that for herders, benefits exceeded merely financial compensation. Indeed, slow early sales of certificates meant that financial compensation was slow to arrive, and quite modest when it did so (ibid). Nonetheless, herders continued to discharge planned activities as far as possible, reflecting the basis of these in endogenous values and priorities and a lengthy participatory planning process (Addison et al., 2020; ibid). Upton (2020:240/244) asserts *'It is... notable that in this case non-monetary incentives, for example, participation in governance, coordination of labour and land rights, were at least as important to many herding participants as additional financial incentives. Thus, the prospect of future small payments through PCCA certificate sales may be seen as supporting rather than transfiguring herders' existing practices and socio-ecological relations'*.

Costs

For PCCA, it is primarily the participating herders whose conduct is impacted by the programme. As highlighted above, PCCA activities were developed through a lengthy series of participatory planning meetings from 2012-2015, when the programme was officially launched. The stated desire by participating herders to enhance/ restore aspects of seasonal mobility between pastures reflects traditional practices and organisation in Mongolia's pastoral sector, wherein mobility has long formed a central and ecologically rational strategy, and shaped by a wider context of pasture degradation and growing sedentarisation (Addison et al., 2020; Upton, 2020; PDD, 2015). PCCA documents highlight pasture degradation as one of the commonalities across study sites, linked to a range of factors such as changing climates, but also trends towards sedentarisation and growing numbers of livestock (PDD, 2015). The latter is thus highlighted as problematic, with issues of 'overstocking' further complicated by the fact that large livestock herds have traditionally been associated with wealth (ibid). Nonetheless, as documented in the PCCA Project Design Document (PDD, 2015), activities developed and agreed by participating herders included reductions in overall grazing pressure in key seasonal pastures, realised through enhanced mobility and also some modest reductions in livestock numbers in these pastures. For herders, the desire for better grazing, environmental and livestock quality, which in turn supported livelihoods, underpinned these commitments. Thus, PCCA did not require land use changes as such, but

rather improvements in existing land use and management practices, which providentially translated into enhanced carbon sequestration in soils, as modelled using the CENTURY model (ibid). Herder groups thus developed annual pasture management plans that reflected these agreed changes and targets. Participating herder groups also developed a range of other activities around conservation (e.g. habitat/species protection; enhanced involvement in governance) and livelihoods/risk management (e.g. processing and marketing livestock products, collective action to repair or construct key infrastructure). Annual and biannual targets and indicators were developed and agreed for all these activities, as set out in the site-specific management plans in Annex 5 of the PDD (2015). Sources indicate that monitoring was then undertaken through a combination of herder groups' reporting to the project managers, MSRM, supported by evidence such as group accounts and meeting minutes, and local administration records and statistics, in conjunction with verification visits by MSRM. In compliance with the PV Standard, Annual Reports, with supporting evidence were then submitted to PV throughout the project, for their scrutiny and approval. Issuance of certificates was dependent on receipt of this approval, with provision for adjustments where any targets were not met (PDD, 2015, PV, 2013). The issue of leakage appears to have posed a cultural challenge, given that pastures are not privately owned and that flexibility and reciprocity are core tenets of Mongolian pastoralism. In practice, this means that herders from other areas may come into and graze herder group pastures. This occurs both as a regular, informal practice particularly in some summer pasture areas, and also in times of natural disaster (*dzud*), wherein herders may migrate long distances to other areas in search of grazing (PDD, 2015). Key seasonal pastures wherein this was a significant annual phenomenon were omitted from grazing pressure and pasture management commitments under PCCA, as it was deemed inappropriate to seek to change such behaviour, as well as being beyond local herders' capacity to do so (ibid). The PDD (2015) and Upton (2020) suggest that PCCA is also sensitive to prospects for leakage and displacement from outmigration by participating herders under locally challenging conditions, with provisions for receiving areas to negotiate a proportion of PV benefits as compensation for pasture use. This provision does not appear to have been put into practice to date.

Available sources do not provide detailed accounts of costs of participation, although for the reasons set out in the analysis above, it seems reasonable to conclude that these may be limited, at least in terms of social and cultural impacts. Contra some critiques of PES as a concept and as enacted in other geographical spaces, Upton (2020) further argues that PCCA has not imposed new cognitive frames or transformed participating herders into 'PES postulates', motivated solely by economic values, but rather has built from endogenous values and priorities.

Outcomes

Social outcomes

PCCA has a range of social impact goals, in addition to carbon sequestration, pasture management and conservation. These appear to take two forms. As documented in the Project Design Document (PDD, 2015), herder groups worked with MSRM to develop a range of socio-economic and risk management related activities, with accompanying indicators and annual/ biannual targets. As previously highlighted,

these activities ranged from collective action to repair and maintain key herding infrastructure (e.g. wells and shelters), to activities with a direct impact on household income, such as enhanced processing and marketing of livestock products. For these latter types of activities, annual targets typically comprised percentage changes in household income against the pre PCCA baseline, established during the Darwin project (PDD, 2015). The PDD (2015: 38/39) also sets out 6 socio-economic indicators based on those used in national poverty/ wellbeing assessments and prioritised by herders, including factors such as income and income availability, existence of savings and herders' own life evaluation, as well as pasture management related goals, specifically changes in annual mobility. The PDD provides 2015 baseline figures and estimated figures for 2019, the end of Phase 1 of PCCA. Progress against annual targets, as set out in site specific management plans (Annex 5, PDD, 2015) are documented in Annual Reports, as required by the Plan Vivo Standard, and based on herders' self-reporting, evidence provided and MSRM's monitoring and verification activities (PV, 2013; Dorlignsuren et al., 2019; Dorlignsuren et al., 2018; Dorlignsuren et al., 2016). The Year 4 Annual Report (Dorlignsuren et al., 2019), marked the end of PCCA Phase 1 and thus also provides more detail of progress over this phase of the project as a whole, including against the 6 socio-economic indicators, and compares these with the targets set in the PDD. Data for these six indicators in 2019 was derived from a repeat of key aspects of the original baseline household survey, thus providing a longitudinal household-based dataset for herder group members (ibid). As reported therein, these indicators showed a positive direction of change on the whole: *'...targets have been met or even exceeded for the majority of criteria, with livelihood diversification as the only exception. Of course income changes also reflect wider contexts such as market prices for livestock products and state subsidies, which are outwith the control of PCCA. Nonetheless, herders' narrative accounts highlight the importance of economies of scale and collective action under PCCA, as well as income and loans from sale of PCCA certificates in improving livelihoods'* (ibid: 20).

Ecological impacts

Ecological impacts are also documented in these same annual reports. Again, annual targets are set in the PDD (2015) as part of the site-specific management plans, developed by herders with MSRM's facilitation. These include activities such as protection of habitats and key species, as well as herders' own enhanced participation in local environmental governance, assessed as for social impacts by self reporting, provision of data (e.g. habitat/ species surveys; agreements with local administrations), and MSRM monitoring and evaluation. Enhancement of rangelands at wider landscape scale, through reduction of grazing pressure may also be considered an ecological as well as a pasture management and carbon-related impact. The Year 4 Annual Report (Dorlignsuren et al., 2019) cites evidence of success across a number of these indicators, albeit with funding constraints precluding annual repeats of camera trap surveys, for monitoring of changes in wildlife populations. Targets for reduction in livestock numbers were not met in full at all sites, but reduced grazing pressure was nonetheless realised through increased mobility, with associated positive impacts on environmental conditions and on carbon sequestration. Available sources do not record how herders who were not part of the participating groups perceived the scheme, although Upton (2020) and PDD (2015) both outline provisions for such herders to be informed and to voice any concerns. Upstream participants, in other words the herder group members themselves, are cited in Dorlignsuren et al. (2019: 21) as taking an increasingly active role in wildlife monitoring and protection,

with this offering *‘important benefits for conservation of key wildlife species, as do herders’ activities to protect wildlife from illegal hunting and poaching. The latter are typically undertaken in agreement with local environmental officers and highlight the increased participation and leadership of herders in aspects of environmental governance under PCCA’*. Herders also credited PCCA with improvements in pasture management and collective action (ibid).

Participation

Participation levels are assessed through the annual reports, with each giving information on the number of participating households and the reasons for any changes, as supplied by MSRM. The reports show some reduction in the overall number of households over the duration of Phase 1 PCCA, but this is ascribed to some 24 households’ leaving the project areas altogether for unrelated reasons, rather than their remaining in situ but deciding to leave PCCA. Evidence for the main factors influencing participation comes primarily from Upton (2020) as cited above. According to this source herders, who have long been exposed to a variety of development projects and initiatives in the Mongolian countryside, initially viewed PCCA as another ‘surface of engagement’, but also as one in which they were particularly able to express their own (including non monetary) values and priorities, due to the co-produced nature of the scheme. According to Upton (2020), this supported herders’ continuing commitment in Phase 1, even when certificate sales and hence financial benefits, were initially slow to materialise, and is reflected in their uptake of Phase 2. Barriers to participation appear to have mainly revolved around membership/ non-membership of the pre-existing herder groups. It appears that PCCA Phase 1 was deliberately kept as a small pilot, due to the novelty of the scheme in Mongolia, albeit with opportunities for further upscaling in the future (Dorligsuren et al, 2019). Factors which have acted as barriers to access in PES schemes elsewhere, such as individual land title or wealth, have largely been avoided in PCCA, due to PV recognition of community rights and tenure and the deliberate inclusion of poorer/ marginalised households (Upton, 2020; PV, 2013).

Other outcomes

Issues around land tenure and leakage are summarised above. Available sources do not provide details of any indirect social, cultural or environmental impacts. They do, however suggest that there may have been ‘crowding in’ rather than ‘crowding out’ of diverse values and motives for conservation, due to the locally led, participatory nature of the scheme (Addison et al, 2020; Upton, 2020).

Methodology and literature

This case study relies on both systematic literature searches and expert judgement. Specifically, a structured search of the databases Web of Science, Science Direct, Scopus and Google Scholar was conducted using the following search terms: ("payment* for ecosystem services" OR "payment* for environmental services" OR "investment* in environmental services" OR "investment* in ecosystem services" OR "investment* in ecological services" OR "payment* for ecological services" or “PES”) AND (“Mongolia*” OR “Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action” OR “PCCA” OR “Plan Vivo Mongolia” OR “Values and Valuation” OR “Upton” OR “MSRM” OR “Mongolian Society for Range Management”) NOT

("Inner Mongolia"). Searches were also conducted using Science Direct with the following slightly amended research terms to accommodate system limits on Boolean operators and absence of 'wildcard' (*) function: "payment for ecosystem services" OR "payment for environmental services" OR "payment for ecological services") AND ("Mongolia" OR "Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action" OR "PCCA" OR "Plan Vivo Mongolia) NOT ("Inner Mongolia"). The selection of databases was designed to encompass scientific, social scientific and policy-oriented sources which may contain reference specifically to the case study, in line with IPBES guidance and goals. More general sources on ecosystem services, values and conservation in Mongolia or the wider region were not targeted in searches. Searches were limited to 2012 onwards, when the PCCA programme and the underpinning 'Values and Valuation' research project first emerged. These searches only yielded two relevant academic studies (Addison et al., 2020 and Upton, 2020), due to the paucity of published academic work on PES in Mongolia and on this PCCA project in particular. It was therefore supplemented by searches drawing on expert knowledge and judgement, and including those focused on non-academic sources and grey literature. Specifically, the Plan Vivo website (<https://www.planvivo.org/project-network/pastures-conservation-climate-action-mongolia/>) hosts the Project Design Document and Annual Reports for PCCA, as it does for all accredited projects. These provide detailed insights into the project's context, design and impacts, reviewed and approved for publication on the website by PV. A further five yearly independent validation report prepared by external auditors is currently in preparation.

References

- Addison, J., Brown, C., Pavey, C., Lkhagvadorj, EO, Bukhbat, D., and Dorjburedgaa, L. 2020. Understanding alignments and mis-alignments of values to better craft institutions in the pastoral drylands. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, Vol 4, Article 116: 1-10.
- Dorligsuren, D. and Dulmaa, D. 2016. '*Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action, Mongolia- Year 1 Annual Report*'. Available online at https://www.planvivo.org/docs/Annual-Report-2015-2016_PCCA-Mongolia-1.pdf.
- Dorligsuren, D. and Uilst, D. 2019. '*Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action, Mongolia- Year 4 Annual Report*'. Available online at https://www.planvivo.org/docs/PCCA-Mongolia-Yr-4-Annual-Report_public.pdf.
- Dorligsuren, D. and Uilst, D. 2018. '*Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action, Mongolia- Years 2 and 3 Annual Report*'. Available online at https://www.planvivo.org/docs/PCCA-Mongolia-Yrs-2-3-Annual-Report_public.pdf.
- Plan Vivo. 2013. '*Plan Vivo Standard for Community Payments for Ecosystem Services Programmes*'. Available online at <https://www.planvivo.org/docs/Plan-Vivo-Standard.pdf>.
- Plan Vivo Project Design Document (PDD). 2015. '*Pastures, Conservation and Climate Action, Mongolia*'. Submitted by C. Upton, D. Dorligsuren, D. Dulmaa, G. Gantsogt. Available online at

<https://www.planvivo.org/docs/Pastures-Conservation-and-Climate-Action-Mongolia-PDD-2016.pdf>.

Upton, C. 2020. Conserving natures? Co-producing Payments for Ecosystem Services in Mongolian Rangelands. *Development and Change*, 51(1):224-252.

REDD+ in Cross River State, Nigeria

Adeniyi Asiyambi and Usman Isyaku

1. Background and Context

REDD+, (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation, forest carbon stock conservation, the sustainable management of forests, and the enhancement of forest carbon stocks) described by some as the “world’s largest experiment in Payment for Ecosystem Services” has generated interest across the climate, conservation and development circles (Corbera, 2012 p612). Nigeria formally commenced the REDD+ programme in October 2011 with the approval of its National Programme Document by the UN-REDD – a culmination of groundwork going back to 2008. The country adopted a nested approach in which national policy processes were pursued concurrently with demonstration activities at the subnational level in Cross River State, one of the country’s 37 states. Cross River, 21,787 km² in area (or about the size of Slovenia) is an area of local and national importance, covering a significant portion of the country’s remaining stretch of biodiversity-rich rainforest including a national park, a wildlife sanctuary, 14 forest reserves and hundreds of community forests (Caldecott and Morakinyo, 1996; Ite, 2001). Moreover, Cross River is also internationally recognised as part of the Guinean rainforest global diversity hotspot, an area of significant ecological and socio-cultural diversity with a long history of international biodiversity conservation and development programmes (Abua et al., 2013; Oates, 1999; Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund, 2020). Nigeria’s mangrove forest, a significant part of which is in Cross River, is the third largest globally, accounting for 7% of the world’s total and exceeded only by Indonesia (19%) and Brazil (9%) (FAO & UNEP, 2020 p.22).

Jointly supported by a number of international REDD+ platforms including the World Bank’s Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF), United Nations REDD+ programme (UN-REDD) and the California-based Governors’ Climate and Forests Task Force (GCF), the goal of Nigeria’s REDD+ as specified in the National Programme Document was “to contribute to climate change mitigation through improved forest conservation and enhance sustainable community livelihoods.” (NPD, 2011 p.11). The readiness phase, the first of the three-phased scheme sought to improve institutional and technical capacity at the national level and in Cross River State and create a framework for REDD+ expansion across Nigeria. The readiness programme also sought to demonstrate elements of readiness in Cross River, including mobilizing a participatory base for REDD+, determining the drivers of deforestation, establishing an emission reference level and baseline, developing benefit sharing arrangements, and deploying social and environmental safeguards (NDP, 2011; R-RP, 2013; Asiyambi, 2015; Isyaku, 2017; Nuesiri, 2016). The programme thus sought to protect what was described as “Nigeria’s last rainforest”, amidst high rates (3.7%) of deforestation in Nigeria (NPD, 2011 p.16).

But REDD+ in Nigeria and specifically in Cross River also builds on a long history of regional and national forest management and biodiversity conservation efforts that go back to colonial origins in the 1900s

through postcolonial era beginning in 1960 when Nigeria gained political independence from Britain (von Hellerman, 2013; Oates, 1999). These colonial and postcolonial contexts set the background for forest and land policy in Nigeria, one remarkable element of which is the contested co-existence of a weakened customary land tenure subsumed to the formal statutory land tenure. The Land Use Act (LUA) of 1990 (formerly Land Use Decree of 1978) vested all land comprised in the territory of each state in the governor of that state. Though recognized in the LUA, customary land rights are subsumed under the control of the state governors. This essentially gives the state governors total control of land (including forested land, except for National Parks which are under federal jurisdiction) within each state. The National Forest Policy (2006) also defers to the Land Use Act in the determination of forest rights and ownership. Meanwhile, at the state level, Cross River State Forest Laws, which were promulgated in 1958 under the colonial rule largely continued to apply, until the laws were repealed and approved by the state government in 2010 as part of the institutional preparation for REDD+.

While the colonial legacy of forest management reflects in the enduring powers of Cross River forest department to appropriate lands for the state and regulate forest resources, it is the LUA which has been the most significant in enabling the government to exercise a more encompassing control over lands and forests in postcolonial times. For instance, the constitution of the Cross River National Park between 1989 and early 1990s which saw the displacement of several local communities was made possible through an uneasy combination of LUA-sanctioned sub-national control of land and the administrative superiority of the federal military government of Nigeria at the time (Ite, 1998). More recently, as Schoneveld (2014) notes, the vulnerability of community land and forest tenure under the LUA has been most evident in the state appropriation of community and private lands for large scale industrial agriculture by international investors and national elites, under the pretext of greater public good. Meanwhile, efforts to promote a decentralised forest governance structure in Cross River beginning with the integrated conservation and development programme of the Cross River National Park in the early 1990s culminated in the emergence and flourishing of the NGO sector in Cross River state (Oates, 1999; Abua et al., 2013). But only little changed in terms of recognition for community rights and devolution of real control to communities (Ite, 2001). This longer history has greatly conditioned and shaped REDD+ in Cross River, even as REDD+ came to transform this wider forest governance landscape in important ways.

2. Problematization and Framing of Payment of Ecosystem Services Project (REDD+) in Cross River State, Nigeria

If REDD+ was framed as a solution to a combined financial and ecological crises in Cross River, its local grounding rested on problematizing local livelihood activities of forest communities as drivers of deforestation. The economy of Cross River State suffered a significant reduction in oil revenues following a 2012 Supreme Court ruling, which upheld the transfer of much of the state's oil wells to the neighbouring state, Akwa-Ibom. This followed a separate International Court of Justice judgement, which transferred the oil-rich, long-contested area of Bakassi Peninsular from the federal government of Nigeria to the government of Cameroon, thereby riding Cross River of its littoral claims. While federal allocations from oil revenues accounted for as much as 80% of Cross River's total state revenue annually, the loss of its oil wells combined with mounting public debt (total debt grew from Naira 94 billion in 2008 to Naira 137

billion in 2015, making Cross River the 3rd most indebted state of Nigeria's 37 states in 2015) drove the state government to actively seek other lucrative sources of state finance. The state thus identified REDD+ as one important source of green finance, with both the 2011 and 2012 budget speeches of the state governor noting that "We expect to access substantial financial and technical resources from the UN-REDD" (Imoke, 2010; 2011).

At the same time, a crisis narrative of deforestation linked to protecting what was widely described in programme documents as "Nigeria's last rainforest" galvanized interest around REDD+ in Cross River. An international environment summit jointly hosted by the government and civil society organisations in Calabar, the capital city in June 2008 concluded that rates of forest and biodiversity loss were assuming a 'catastrophic' proportion. The summit, was declared opened by the state governor, Liyel Imoke, and had in attendance representatives of the United National Development Programme (UNDP), Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA) and the British Council. The top three recommendations of the summit communiqué asked the state to "halt revenue target based on timber exploitation and focus on forest conservation and regeneration for possible carbon finance", "declare a two year moratorium on logging" and "initiate action to take advantage of the carbon credit market" (Summit Communiqué, 2008 p.3). The state governor implemented these resolutions: forestry revenue targets were stopped, a ban on logging was declared indefinitely with a fully militarized anti-deforestation task force to enforce it and steps to implement REDD+ were initiated. The summit had been partly organized by civil society actors with interest in and international collaborations on carbon forestry; these were influential in setting the agenda for the summit as the pre-summit documents revealed. Indeed, some of these civil society actors were later appointed to the Board of the Cross River State Forestry Commission and the Anti-deforestation Task Force – two important government institutions for the development and implementation of REDD+. As such, it was this convergence of the fiscal and the ecological problematization, which is central to understanding the rise of REDD+ in Nigeria and in Cross River in particular.

Yet, the problematization of local livelihood activities (including farming, fuelwood use) as the main drivers of deforestation was important to ground REDD+ in local communities. REDD+ proposals and project idea notes were developed mainly by international consultants working with local NGOs, government actors and consultants, and ratified in a series of stakeholder workshops (Nuesiri, 2015). These proposals clearly identified what was considered to be the main drivers of deforestation in the three designated REDD+ forest clusters: the livelihood activities of local communities, particularly farming (Oyebo et al., 2010, See also MTPR, 2017). The proposals also pointed to new farms created by "outsiders". It also highlights the recent popularity of cash crops such as cocoa and oil palm (Oyebo et al., 2010). About 70% of the nearly three million residents of Cross River state who were regarded as "absolute poor" by the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (2012) rely heavily on agriculture and forest-based livelihoods. The REDD+ proposals (Oyebo et al., 2010) designated three forest clusters for the programme in Cross River as follows:

1. The Ekuri-Iko Esai cluster, which brings together 94,000ha of forests claimed by 12 communities and a forest reserve across three local government areas. REDD+ intervention in this cluster is

expected to lead to the sequestration of an estimated 21,341,760 tons of CO₂eq emissions over a 20-year period.

2. The Mbe Mountain – Afi River Forest Reserve cluster. This project brings together 50,000 ha of forests claimed by 18 communities in the Boki local government area. It is estimated that the cluster would similarly sequester an equivalent of 11,352,000 tons of CO₂eq in emissions over the same period.
3. The mangrove forest cluster, which brings together close to 100 communities around the mangrove forest areas of Cross River. The delays ratifying the inclusion of mangroves in REDD+ at the international level meant that a detailed project idea note was not prepared for the mangrove cluster.

REDD+ clusters were designated and mapped out by the consultants solely on the basis of forest contiguity; some communities were not even aware that their forests had been mapped out for REDD+ long after REDD+ readiness had begun. Yet, REDD+ proponents pursued clustering as a condition for financialization. One of the programme documents justified clustering: “the project is viable and attractive to carbon finance only if the project area includes the multiple community forests and forest reserves. A project considering only one of these areas would not be viable on its own’ (Oyebo et al., 2010 p.89). These clusters would become the basis for community representation in REDD+ and wider community engagement in various REDD+ activities. Yet, clustering precipitated new tensions and exacerbated old conflicts among communities (Isyaku et al., 2017).

Yet, partly through the promise of better livelihoods linked directly to carbon offset payments (often called ‘carbon credit’ among communities), communities were summoned into REDD+ in order to bring local forest uses under state control. This raised expectations among many forest communities within the clusters. Proponents presented REDD+ as a new carbon economy in which local forest communities are presented as service providers, who can restructure their forest use to generate third party-verified carbon emission reduction units for which payments would be made either through donor-driven results-based payments or through private REDD+ finance and carbon offset trading. While REDD+ proponents continue to claim that carbon rights are yet to be determined, the board of the Forestry Commission went ahead to quietly include a carbon sharing code into the appendices of the new “Forestry Regulation and Tariffs for market and transportation of forest products and other forestry prescribed fees” dated August 2012. The carbon sharing code allocated 10% of carbon benefits in all forest types to communities, while government and private entities will receive 20% and 70% of benefits respectively. This document, which was formulated without the knowledge of forest communities was challenged by some community leaders who later got hold of the schedule.

Though REDD+ proponents focused on the pilot clusters, engagement through meetings, workshops, and field demonstration was limited to even fewer communities within the clusters, the so-called “model” REDD+ communities (see Asiyani et al., 2019). Yet efforts to incentivise communities sit uneasily with the anti-deforestation task force’s unpopular campaign of strict forest surveillance, timber seizures and restrictions on community forest access (Asiyani, 2016). Throughout the REDD+ process, the problem of

stakeholder participation and representation also remained a recurrent challenge. Indeed, Nuesiri (2016; 2017) found that the REDD+ process in Nigeria did not consider the democratic rights of key local government authorities, community conservationists, and other relevant groups at consultation and implementation stages. As such not only is the process of obtaining free, prior and informed consent of communities ineffective, the process also followed a 'carrot and stick' approach where dissenting community voices were suppressed by state sponsored agents who claimed to provide consent on behalf of others (Isyaku, 2017).

3. Values and Values Articulation in Cross River State REDD+ Project

In REDD+ and other PES arrangements generally, values are usually conceived and articulated through the rational actor paradigm that expects stakeholders to give preferences to aspects of the environment that provide the most economic benefits (see Angelsen, 2009; Angelsen, 2014). In Cross River, discussions of values and valuations of forest ecosystem services are predominantly based on this economic paradigm, focused primarily on carbon. To be clear, there is a rhetorical commitment to generating co-benefits through Cross River's REDD+ and a number of REDD+ reports have tried to map carbon stock distribution unto areas of ecological and social values in order to advance priority co-benefits activities (Ravilious et al., 2010; Maukonen et al., 2017). In reality however, too little attention has been paid to other co-benefits (e.g. how to generate, measure, monitor and equitably share them). Rather what is more evident are the trade-offs, for instance, between local access to the forest and forest protection for REDD+. As such, co-benefit claims notwithstanding, in practice forest values are focused away from biodiversity conservation, food security, timber and non-timber forest products to prioritize global climate change mitigation benefits. Prior to the logging moratorium (itself an instance of carbon value articulation) in preparation for REDD+, timber resources were valued for their significant contributions to government budgets and community livelihoods through royalty payments – values that were largely displaced by REDD+ (Agbor, 2011; Amalu et al., 2016; Asiyambi, 2016; Asiyambi et al., 2017).

As such REDD+ proponents sought to entrench values aligned with the promotion of a carbon commodity regime. This was pursued, for instance, through a national carbon estimation and map-making exercise by consultants from the UNEP-WCMC. This exercise, which made use of satellite imagery and standard soil charts to render visible biomass carbon aboveground and belowground estimated Nigeria's biomass and soils carbon as totaling 7.5gigaton (Ravilious et al., 2010). The clustering of community forests as noted above also reflects a specific scalar targeting underpinned by the pursuit of an economics of scale that renders community forests legible and attractive to carbon finance. REDD+ proponents further articulated these values through series of consultative meetings with stakeholders, workshops, field demonstration of tree volume measurement, and community engagement meetings. Nonetheless, there are accounts that show that these value articulation processes deliberately excluded some relevant stakeholders who are perceived to hold alternative viewpoints to that of the project proponents.

Consequently, there are concerns that intrinsic, non-instrumental and non-carbon values that underpin local forest conservation were not considered in the design and implementation of REDD+ in Cross River State. Abua et al., (2013) reported that international donors focus on carbon sequestration value of

forests is alien to the local communities. They also observed a mismatch between complex dynamics of local peoples intrinsic and extrinsic value structures and strictly utilitarian value of forests championed by international donors as seen in REDD+. Cultural values of forests for healing, spirituality, celebrations and cultural traditions have been central to the survival of forest communities in Cross River State for centuries. Yet, the logic of carbon valuation has actively and unwittingly ignored these indigenous knowledges and cultural values (Odok, 2019). Similarly, pro-natural and pro-social intrinsic values linked to aesthetic beauty of forestlands and forest products, connectedness to nature, place attachment and identities are excluded from the REDD+ design and implementation (Isyaku, 2017; Isyaku, forthcoming). The assumption was that incentive payments could easily change or compromise communities' deeply held cultural values relating to forests.

This incongruence between proponents values and those of local communities has often generated local resistance and contestations both by forest communities and civil society organisations, including non-governmental organisations such as Friends of the Earth Nigeria

(FoEN) and Green Concern for Development (GREENCODE), who decry the effects of proponents' values on communities and forests in Cross River (Osarogiagbon, 2011). Local communities have organized protests, pursued litigations, rejected benefit sharing proposal and have some times been forced to counter the violence of the anti-deforestation task force. Even in some of the communities which are regarded as model REDD+ communities, communities have used protest letters to challenge attempts to undermine community development efforts by REDD+ proponents who seek forest protection for REDD+ even when this is counter productive – for instance in a case where communities are being prevented from salvaging trees already felled in the process of rural road construction on community lands (Asiyambi et al., 2019).

4. Distribution of Cost and Benefit

In Nigeria's REDD+, tentative benefits to communities were both monetary and in-kind, with the former being the dominant form. First, the state, through the Cross River Forestry Commission, had converted the previous timber royalty regime into a 'loyalty payment' regime to serve as an important strategy for incentivizing support for REDD+. Timber royalty, which continued to be paid to communities until 2008 when a total ban on logging was imposed, was calculated as a fraction of total timber revenue collected by the state. Being the major benefit to communities from timber extraction, royalties were a critical part of many communities' collective livelihood and development fund. In principle, communities – government share of timber royalties was in the ratio 70% / 30% for timber extracted from community forests and 50% / 50% of timber from state forest reserves. Royalties were paid to 'landlord communities', that is, communities on whose current community land or ancestral lands (in case of state forest reserves) timber had been extracted. Communities received as much as Naira 1 million (US\$ 2,590) per annum in timber royalty.

However, 'loyalty payment', which was first paid to communities in 2012/2013 was a flat rate payment from a special state budget for REDD+. Loyalty payment was made to communities who have purportedly demonstrated commitment to REDD+ by being generally cooperative. Cooperation was defined as

communities keeping their forests intact, or offering community land for reforestation, or simply not expressing dissenting views (at least in public) towards REDD+. The loyalty payment was also supposed to elicit and test a potential benefit sharing system among REDD+ communities, being payment for “not cutting the forest”. Specifically, a cheque of an arbitrary sum of Naira 0.5 million (US\$1,295) was issued to each REDD+ cluster with the instruction to share the fund among themselves. Cheques were handed to representatives of each cluster who were mostly community chiefs or managers of the community based associations of the dominant communities in the clusters.

While the total ban on logging and the embargo on royalty payment were state wide, only the communities that made up the clusters were entitled to loyalty payments. The value of the flat rate loyalty amount was much lower compared to what many communities received as royalty payment under the timber regime. Moreover the loyalty payment generated tensions between communities and the Forestry Commission partly for its arbitrary value. Some struggled to decide how to share the loyalty payment, with one cluster particularly rejecting the burden of developing a cluster-level carbon benefit sharing formula which was considered as pitting communities against each other. In cluster one where the loyalty payment was intensely contested, the payment was at first declined altogether, with community representatives refusing to collect the first state-issued cheque for several months. When the cheque was finally picked up, the communities ultimately agreed to share the loyalty fund equally, a decision which did not go down well with some of the communities who believed that equal payment was inequitable, given that it did not reflect the different historical commitment to forest conservation within the cluster and significant differences in individual community’s forest area.

Loyalty payments were not only substantive payments to communities in replacement of royalty payments, they were also indicative payments to demonstrate what communities could expect under the future results-based payment in which even greater level of monetary benefits were to be expected. It is worth noting that much of this promised future benefit did not materialize in Cross River. Besides loyalty payments, other monetary benefits of REDD+ to communities include per diem payments to individual representatives of clustered communities at REDD+ meetings and workshops. In-kind benefits include the involvement of some of the communities in awareness raising events, field demonstration of carbon estimation, and other training workshops. A report of the community-based REDD+ sub-programme of Nigeria’s REDD+ claimed that “more than 300 households across 21 communities have benefitted” from the sub-programme which supported communities to develop management plans, carry out reforestation, improve cassava processing and undertake sustainable cocoa cultivation.

While these benefits from REDD+ and policy process associated with it were limited to the communities within the pilot cluster sites (and even fewer beneficiaries in the case of the community-based sub-programme), some of the major costs and burdens of REDD+ in Cross River took a state-wide dimension. For instance, the programme in Cross River had problematized local forest and land uses across the entire state as the ‘driver of deforestation’. It was in direct response to this scale of problematization that the logging ban was imposed across the entire state’s landscape. The militarised anti-deforestation task force operated in part through a dispersed network of informants so that the task force was able to intercept logging operations, confiscate wood products in transit and suppressed timber sale across the state. The

entire forest economy was virtually criminalised. Arrested ‘forest offenders’ piled up so quickly that the anti-deforestation task force requested the establishment of a special mobile court to try the teeming populations of offenders more rapidly. As a result, not only were livelihoods lost in the timber value chain, the price of timber in Cross River rose by up to 300% at its peak. In this sense, the burden of REDD+ was, to a large extent, state wide, although forest clearing for industrial farms owned by national and international elites was allowed to continue largely unhindered (Asiyanbi, 2016; Schoneveld, 2014).

There were barely any systematic efforts within Nigeria’s REDD+ programme to account for the various cost of participating in REDD+. At least not for local communities, where some community members have only expressed in private conversations their disappointment and frustration at the failure of the REDD+ remuneration to materialize. As a result, some communities expressed regret about community-driven efforts to limit forest use in anticipation of REDD+ compensation. Across several communities, among timber seller and wood artisans, and across the general public, the impacts of REDD+ on the availability and price of timber and other forest products and the wider impacts of these on public well being were widely decried (Agbakwuru, 2012; Ekott, 2016, Una, 2017). And with respect to costs to the state government, Cross River state, like many of the subnational governments’ surveyed in a recent study by Lutterel et al. (2018), has expended far more (resource, forgone opportunities and manpower hours) on REDD+ than it has received in REDD+ funding. For instance, the former state governor lamented the failure of REDD+ to yield returns on investment at the end of his tenure in 2015.

5. Outcomes

The June 2017 Mid-Term Progress Report (MTPR) for Nigeria submitted to the World Bank’s FCPF presents a self assessment of the REDD+ readiness process in Nigeria. Though a major goal of Nigeria’s REDD+ was to contribute “to climate change mitigation through improved forest conservation and enhancing sustainable community livelihoods” (NPD, 2011 p.11), the mid-term report accounted for social and environmental impacts not by enumerating specific indices of social and environmental impacts per se but by detailing efforts to develop and apply tools for integrating “social and environmental considerations into the REDD+ policy-making process” (MRTP, 2017 p. 31). These tools, particularly the World Bank-sanctioned Strategic Environmental and Social Assessment and the Participatory Governance Assessment process are central to an understanding of outcomes in Cross River in terms of safeguarding against negative impacts (MRTP, 2017). This is also in consonance with wider requirement for safeguard mechanisms at the international level (see UNFCCC, 2011).

Nevertheless, the community-based strand of the REDD+ programme, sought specifically to simultaneously pursue forest conservation and social development objectives of reducing rural poverty. In reporting its achievements under the UNREDD, the CBR+ notes that “more than 300 households across 21 communities have benefited from the Programme... [which] promotes forest management and biodiversity conservation, rural livelihoods improvement with focus on climate smart approaches, capacity building for participation in climate change programmes including REDD+, and sustainable energy alternatives” (UNREDD, 2018). In one of the CBR+ pilot communities, Iko-Esai, it was claimed that “significant outcomes” were recorded in terms of alternative livelihood improvements and increase in

average household income (Griet, 2019). For instance, community women were given food processing machines and men were trained in strategies to improve cocoa production value chain to divert their dependence on forest products (Griet, 2019). The CBR+ also served as a common dialogue platform where various community groups and state officials discussed progress and concerns, which fed into the fine-tuning of REDD+ policy implementation strategies (UNREDD, 2011; UNREDD 2018). In some communities, there was evidence that members were selected and trained on how to perform preliminary carbon measurement estimations as part of the capacity building program of REDD+. There has been a greater and more widespread awareness of carbon forestry in Cross River, even if this has not necessarily led to better understanding of what is a complex idea. Notably, CBR+ accesses social impacts at the level of communities and community clusters. And these social impacts focused on the time-scope of the various livelihood intervention projects designed and implemented by CBR+ official.

However, in some communities, CBR+ was largely unsuccessful due to community resentment from lack of formal consent and tokenistic participation. Some of these claims are refuted by some community members who were either sidelined in the scheme or were involved to fulfilled donors' requirements without achieving any measurable positive impact. For example, Isyaku (2017) documented that the Ekuri community have rejected the planned social safeguard program which was to introduce different forms of alternative agricultural practices that can improve their livelihoods. A member of that community noted that "we need skills acquisition because we don't value snail farming here. Who will come and buy snails from us? We know our problems better than anybody. They cannot handle it for us. All we need is to be guided as we take our own decisions". Indeed, beyond the REDD+ cluster communities some of whom have been the target of the CBR+ interventions, the social impacts of REDD+ was perceived and experienced as negative. For instance, many residents of Cross River including government officials, NGO actors, timber merchants, wood artisans and farmers all decried the ways in which REDD+ and the logging ban have sent the price of timber through the roof, destabilised local forest economies and local livelihoods, and the failure of REDD+ to deliver the promised carbon benefit to communities (see also Asiyanbi, 2016). These undesirable social impacts, though widely reported in national newspapers as directly resulting from REDD+ readiness in Cross River (e.g. Agbakwuru, 2012; Ekott, 2016, Una, 2017), were neither monitored nor reported in official REDD+ reports. A recent study of socio-economic indicators in Cross River found that a major impact of REDD+ in the sampled communities was the inability of resident farmers to build new houses of their own (Adeniran, 2018).

Ecological outcomes

International REDD+ partners such as the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) working with national agencies including the National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) and other local actors continue to monitor both historical and current forest cover change in Cross River. Pre-REDD+ monitoring was used in part to justify the need for REDD+ in Nigeria (Oyebo et al., 2010; NPD, 2011; R-PP, 2013; Maukonen et al., 2017). However, more recent REDD+ reports have documented an increase in deforestation rates in Cross River over the period of the deforestation ban and REDD+ readiness. For instance, while deforestation rates in Cross River was estimated to be 2.7% between 1990 and 2000, the rate had increased to 2.95% between 2007-2014, a period that almost fully overlaps with the period of

the logging ban which began in 2008 and REDD+ readiness period which gained approval from the UNREDD in 2012 (Maukonen et al., 2017). This is consistent with increased deforestation rates in Cross River reported by the global observatory, Global Forest Watch (GFW). Primary forest loss stood at 619ha in 2008, dropping to 358ha in 2009 (a year after the ban on logging was declared) before starting to rise to reach 1430 ha in 2013 and a staggering 3980 ha in 2014 before hitting a new peak of 4820 ha in 2017 (GFW, 2020). Evidence of increased deforestation was also supported by interviews with government officials and some community actors (see Asiyanbi, 2016). However, proponents were refrained from associating the increased rate of deforestation in Cross River to REDD+. Rather, the transitioning of Nigeria's REDD+ from the 'readiness' to the more advanced phases of REDD+ has afforded proponents the opportunity to use evidence of surging deforestation under REDD+ readiness to justify the continuity of REDD+ and renewed support from international REDD+ partners (Maukonen et al., 2017).

REDD+ documents continue to make claims about broad-based participation of stakeholders in the Nigerian REDD+ process. These claims are often based on attendance at key stakeholder meetings (Nuesiri, 2015). In fact, attendance lists have become one key avenue through which proponents of REDD+ demonstrate participation to international partners. Analysing evidence of representation of forest communities in Nigeria's REDD+ processes, Nuesiri (2015) argues that forest communities have not been adequately represented, since NGOs and community based association rather than the democratically-elected local government representatives of the people were formally recognised as representatives in REDD+.

Local participation in REDD+ is partly linked to the principle of free, prior and informed consent (FPIC), which is a mandatory requirement under the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (see UNDRIP, 2007). In Cross River State, the FPIC process was largely symbolic and was carried out as a set of activities in the course of the readiness programme and not as an initial requirement, which should have determine whether or not the readiness program could be implemented. FPIC was assumed to be given by the communities through participation in community engagement meetings in which attendance registers were taken as evidence of consent rather than pursue an elaborate processes of negotiation with communities using standard procedures of the UNDRIP. For some communities, FPIC was no more than informing the communities of the proposed REDD+ programme. Participation in REDD+ workshops, as noted above, was mainly through the REDD+ clusters, and even within these clusters, through few model REDD+ communities in each cluster. Reports of community livelihood activities under REDD+ and particularly, the involvement of communities in the community-based REDD+ is also taken to reflect community participation in REDD+. Here too, about a score of communities are engaged. However, sustainability of participation in such livelihood enhancement projects is typically time limited, linked to the duration of funding.

Though proponents of REDD+ continue to frame the REDD+ readiness process in terms of the narrow programme objectives, the wider impacts of the process in Nigeria have been variously documented by analysts. For instance, the intensification of state control over forests and land evident in the enforcement of an indefinite logging ban across the state, including in community forests is also a reflection of the precarious condition of community tenure. While the logging ban lasted, state-sanctioned industrial

plantation (of palm oil, rubber and fruits such as pineapple) surged in Cross River, accounting for a significant part of the increases in deforestation in the state under REDD+ (Schoneveld, 2014). There were also reports that the destabilization of the timber and non-timber forest economy has led to many traders, artisans and labourers in the sector to turn to farming for sustenance. As part of the enforcement of the ban on logging, timber merchants were allowed to import timber from neighbouring states and the State Forestry Commission also held talks with government of Cameroon on plans to import timber into Cross River. As such, these are indication of displacement of deforestation, that is, leakage.

There has been no experimental analysis of values and motivation crowding effects of REDD+ based on pre- and post-programme evidence in Cross River State. However, in a recent perception study, Isyaku (2017; forthcoming) documented that community members within the REDD+ forest clusters can be broadly classified into 3 categories: (a) conservatives (b) no pay, no care (c) we care but pay us. The 'conservatives' are those community members who hold traditional values that are biospheric and altruistic because they consider aesthetic values of forests, the rights of future generations, and the rights of the biosphere to exist. These value holders have no problems accepting REDD+, have attended conservation meetings, reported violation of conservation laws to authorities, and have made donations to conservation organisations. These values are not likely to be crowded negatively. The 'no pay, no care' category holds mostly egoistic values which indicates that their conservation behaviour is determined by the amount of incentive they receive and the benefits they derived from the forests. These community members are willing to connive with logging companies whenever they feel their rights of forest use are restricted without commensurate monetary compensation. Some of them are involved in REDD+ discussions only because of expectations of payments. Here, there is a possibility for the existence of negative value crowding because these community members have complained about past experiences with government and conservation NGOs that failed to fulfill their promises. The 'we care but pay us' category have a combination of biospheric, altruistic and egoistic value orientations. These community members conserve the forests because of the benefits they derive, consideration for future generations as well as the function of forests as home for biodiversity. They are aware of the impact of their activities on the forest but they are unwilling to participate in REDD+ before receiving any incentives in advance. These community members show tendencies for both positive and negative crowding effects on their values.

6. Methods

For this case study, two sets of literature were used. One is academic literature, which was sourced in part using Scopus. On Scopus, we searched for "Nigeria" OR "Cross River" and "REDD+" or "UNREDD" within Title, Abstract and Keywords. We limited the results to publications years 2008 to 2020. The result generated twenty-two (22) documents, which were then reviewed for relevance. These resulting relevant articles were supplemented with few other academic resources, particularly those relating to the history of conservation in Nigeria and Cross River. The second set of literature used here are project documents and media reports. We searched programme document databases of FCPF and UNREDD for all reports on Nigeria and Cross River. We then reviewed resulting reports for their relevance, paying attention to the major programme proposals and progress reports. These resources were complemented by authors' in-

depth knowledge of the case study based on a combination of 12 years of research on Nigeria's REDD+, and intensive fieldwork totalling two years between 2013 and 2015.

References

- Abua, S., Spencer, R., & Spencer, D. (2013). Design and outcomes of community forest conservation initiatives in Cross River State of Nigeria: a foundation for REDD+. *Conservation biology: voices from the tropics*, 51-58.
- Akanni, A. (2006). An Assessment of Social and Economic Indicators in Pilot REDD+ Communities of Afi/Mbe in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Protection and Policy* 6(3), 63-70.
- Agbakwuru, J. (2012) *Cross River Assembly indicts Task Force on Anti-deforestation*. Vanguard Newspaper, 11 May, 2012. Available at: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2012/05/c-river-assembly-indicts-task-force-on-anti-deforestation/> Accessed 9 September, 2020.
- Agbor, C. O. (2011). The role of forest products in sustaining rural livelihood. *Natural resource use and conservation systems for sustainable development*, 42-53.
- Akanni, A. (2006). An Assessment of Social and Economic Indicators in Pilot REDD+ Communities of Afi/Mbe in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Protection and Policy* 6(3), 63-70.
- Amalu, T. E., Ajake, A. O., & Obi, P. O. (2016). Impact of royalties from forest resources on community development in Boki Local Government in Cross River state, Nigeria. *GeoJournal*, 81(3), 475-487.
- Angelsen, A. (2014). The economics of REDD+. *Handbook of Forest Resource Economics*, 290-316.
- Angelsen, A. (Ed.). (2009). *Realising REDD+: National strategy and policy options*. Cifor.
- Asiyanbi, A. (2015). Mind the gap: global truths, local complexities in emergent green initiatives. In *The international handbook of political ecology*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Asiyanbi, A. P. (2016). A political ecology of REDD+: property rights, militarised protectionism, and carbonised exclusion in Cross River. *Geoforum*, 77, 146-156.
- Asiyanbi, A. P. (2018). Financialisation in the green economy: Material connections, markets-in-the-making and Foucauldian organising actions. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 50(3), 531-548.
- Asiyanbi, A. P., Arhin, A. A., & Isyaku, U. (2017). REDD+ in West Africa: politics of design and implementation in Ghana and Nigeria. *Forests*, 8(3), 78.

- Bose, A., Garcia, C., & Vira, B. (2019). Mottled motivations and narrow incentives: Exploring limitations of direct incentive policies in the Western Ghats, India. *Ecological Economics*, 156, 511-518.
- Caldecott, J.O. and Morakinyo A.B. (1996). Nigeria. In: Lutz, E. and Caldecott, J. (Eds.). *Decentralization and Biodiversity Conservation*, World Bank, Washington, DC, USA (1996).
- Corbera, E. (2012). Problematizing REDD+ as an experiment in payments for ecosystem services. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 4(6): 612-619.
- Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund (2020). Explore the Biodiversity Hotspots. Guinean Forests of West Africa. Available: <https://www.cepf.net/our-work/biodiversity-hotspots> [Accessed 17 October 2013].
- Dietz, T., Fitzgerald, A., & Shwom, R. (2005). Environmental values. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, 30, 335-372.
- Ekott, I., (2016) Investigation: How a \$4 million UN climate programme impoverished Nigerian communities. Premium Time Newspaper. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/202150-investigation-4-million-un-climate-programme-impoverished-tortured-nigerian-communities.html> Accessed 9 September 2020.
- FAO and UNEP. 2020. *The State of the World's Forests 2020*. Forests, biodiversity and people. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca8642en>
- Friant, S. R., Ayambem, W. A., Obaji, A. A., Ifebueme, N. M., Okoi, O. M., Ogar, D. A., ... & Rothman, J. M. (2019). Life on the rainforest edge is associated with improved food security in the agriculture-forest frontier of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 3, 113.
- Global Forest Watch, (2020) Primary Forest Loss in Cross River, Nigeria. Available at: <https://tinyurl.com/yym4dqmo> Accessed 9 September, 2020.
- Griet I. D. (2019) Community-based REDD+ projects in Iko-Esai, Nigeria. Accessed at <https://www.un-redd.org/post/2019/05/28/community-based-redd-projects-in-iko-esai-nigeria>
- Grillos, T., Bottazzi, P., Crespo, D., Asquith, N., & Jones, J. P. (2019). In-kind conservation payments crowd in environmental values and increase support for government intervention: A randomized trial in Bolivia. *Ecological Economics*, 166, 106404.
- Imoke, L. (2010). Cross River State 2011 Budget Speech, delivered on the 22 December, 2010. Cross River State Secretariat, Calabar.

- Imoke, L. (2011). Cross River State 2012 Budget Speech, delivered on the 21 December, 2011. Cross River State Secretariat, Calabar.
- Isyaku, U. (2017). *Beyond policy design: REDD+ implementation and institutional complexities of environmental governance in Cross River state, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Leicester).
- Isyaku, U. (forthcoming). How REDD+ interferes with intrinsic motivations for forest conservation in Cross River State, Nigeria: A Q Methodology Study, *Ecosystem Services*.
- Isyaku, U., Arhin, A. A., & Asiyambi, A. P. (2017). Framing justice in REDD+ governance: Centring transparency, equity and legitimacy in readiness implementation in West Africa. *Environmental Conservation*, 44(3), 212.
- Ite, U.E., (1998). New wine in an old skin: The reality of tropical moist forest conservation in Nigeria. *Land Use Policy*, 15(2): 135-147.
- Ite, U.E. (2001). *Global Thinking and Local Action*, Farnham, UK, Ashgate.
- Luttrell, C., Sills, E., Aryani, R., Ekaputri, A. D., & Evinke, M. F. (2018). Beyond opportunity costs: who bears the implementation costs of reducing emissions from deforestation and degradation?. *Mitigation and adaptation strategies for global change*, 23(2), 291-310.
- Maukonen, P., Nkor, B., Ama, M., Guth, M., Williamson, A., Okeke, F., Hicks, C., Effiom, E., Adekola, R., and Ekwu, A. (2017) Using spatial analysis to explore multiple benefits from REDD+ actions in Cross River State, Nigeria. Prepared by the Nigeria REDD+ Programme, Cross River State Forestry Commission (CRSFC) and UN Environment's World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC). Nigeria National REDD+ Programme, Federal Ministry of Environment, Abuja.
- Mid-term Progress Report (2017) National REDD+ Process and R-PP Implementation Mid-Term Progress Report for Nigeria and Request for Additional Funding from FCPF. June 2017.
- Moros, L., Vélez, M. A., & Corbera, E. (2019). Payments for ecosystem services and motivational crowding in Colombia's Amazon Piedmont. *Ecological Economics*, 156, 468-488.
- National Forest Policy (2006). National Forest Policy, The federal ministry of environment Abuja. Available: <http://www.fao.org/forestry/15148-0c4acebeb8e7e45af360ec63fcc4c1678.pdf>
- NPD. 2011. National Programme Document: Nigeria. Retrieved from UNREDD website: <https://www.unredd.net/documents/policy-board-86/seventh-policy-board-1257/session-iv-national-programmes-1283/nigeria-1287/5955-unredd-pb7-national-programme-document-nigeria-5955.html>

- Nuesiri, E. O. (2017). Feigning democracy: performing representation in the UN-REDD funded Nigeria-REDD programme. *Conservation and Society*, 15(4), 384-399.
- Oates, J.F. (1999). *Myth and reality in the rain forest: how conservation strategies are failing in West Africa*. Berkeley, University of California Press.
- Odok, G. E. (2019). Commodification of forestlands and assault on indigenous knowledge within forest-dependent communities of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa*, 74(2), 126-131.
- Osarogiagbon, R. (2011). REDD & Its Implication on Community People. A presentation made at Cross River State stakeholders forum on Climate change, REDD & Forest Dependent Community Rights. 01-March-11. Available: <http://www.redd-monitor.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/04/Appendix-21.pdf> [Accessed 22 March 2016].
- Oyebo, M., F. Bisong and T. Morakinyo (2010). 'A preliminary assessment of the context for REDD in Nigeria' Available: <http://www.unredd.org/AboutUNREDDProgramme/NationalProgrammes/Nigeria/tabid/992/Default.aspx>
- Participatory Governance Assessment for REDD+: The pilot process in Nigeria Oslo Governance Forum 3-5 October, 2011 By Salisu Dahiru National Coordinator. Accessed at <https://slideplayer.com/slide/5732538/>
- Ravilious, C., V. Kapos, M. Osti, M. Bertzky, J.L. Bayliss, S. Dahiru and B. Dickson (2010). Carbon, biodiversity and ecosystem services: Exploring co-benefits. Nigeria: Preliminary Results', available at <http://www.unepwcmc.org/medialibrary/2010/11/03/668576ca/Nigeria%20Summary%20Report%202010.pdf>
- Reser, J. P., & Bentrupperbäumer, J. M. (2005). What and where are environmental values? Assessing the impacts of current diversity of use of 'environmental' and 'World Heritage' values. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 25(2), 125-146.
- R-PP. 2013. REDD+ readiness preparation proposal of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.forestcarbonpartnership.org/nigeria>
- Schoneveld, G. C. (2014). The politics of the forest frontier: Negotiating between conservation, development, and indigenous rights in Cross River State, Nigeria Land Use Policy. 38: 147-62
- Summit Communiqué (2008). *Communiqué of the Stakeholders' Summit on the Environment 25th-28th June, 2008*. Ministry of Environment, Calabar.

Una, E., (2017) 7 injured as task force clashes with timber dealers in Calabar. Vanguard Newspaper, 8 February 2017. Available at: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2017/02/7-injured-task-force-clashes-timber-dealers-calabar/> Accessed 9 September, 2020.

UNDRIP (2007) United Nations Declaration of the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. Accessed at <https://www.un.org/development/desa/indigenouspeoples/declaration-on-the-rights-of-indigenous-peoples.html>

UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) (2011) Report of the conference of the parties on its sixteenth session, held in Cancun from 29 November to 10 December 2010— Addendum: part Two: action taken by the Conference of the Parties at its sixteenth session: decision 1/CP.16 – The Cancun Agreements: Outcome of the work of the Ad Hoc Working Group on Long-term Cooperative Action under the Convention

UNREDD+ (2011) Nigeria REDD+ Readiness Programme: Participatory Governance Assessment for REDD+. Accessed at https://www.unredd.net/index.php?option=com_docman%26task=doc_download%26gid%3D5679%26Itemid%3D53+&cd=1&hl=en&ct=clnk&gl=no

UNREDD+ (2018) Community Based REDD+ Program in Nigeria: A Success Story. Accessed at <https://www.un-redd.org/post/2018/06/21/community-based-redd-programme-in-nigeria-a-success-story>

Von Hellermann, P. (2013). *Things fall apart?: the political ecology of forest governance in southern Nigeria*, Berghahn Books, New York.

Fondo para la protección del agua (FONAG), Quito, Ecuador

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Background and context

FONAG, “Fondo para la protección del agua” or “fund for water protection” was established in 2000 by The Nature Conservancy and Quito’s water utility, EPMAPS (Empresa Pública Metropolitana de Agua Potable y Saneamiento de Quito). Established as a trust fund, the main purpose of FONAG was to generate interest income to finance conservation activities in biodiverse Andean ecosystems important for Quito’s water supply (Echavarría 2002; Echavarría et al. 2015; Joslin 2020a). In particular, FONAG focuses on protecting and restoring biodiverse, highland Andean grasslands or páramos—which are important ecosystems for water regulation and dry season water availability—in the Guayllabamba watershed. Since establishment, FONAG has grown beyond a financial mechanism, and currently has four primary focal areas: 1) water management (including hydrological, biodiversity, and return on investment monitoring and studies); 2) sustainable water conservation areas (including a park guard program where “guarda páramos” work to surveil and protect hydrologically important areas, land purchases, and community conservation and development agreements); 3) restoration and recuperation of vegetation and soils in areas of hydrologic importance; and 4) environmental education (<http://www.fonag.org.ec/web/programas/gestion-del-agua/>). FONAG has served as a model for many water funds across Ecuador, the Andes, and beyond (Kauffman 2014; Bremer et al. 2016a).

FONAG both manages land owned by the water company and also utilizes PES-like agreements to protect and restore additional areas. The specific programs within FONAG that are most relevant for PES are the guarda páramo (páramo park guard) program and the community conservation and development agreements. In the guarda páramo program, 22 páramo guards, all from rural communities in FONAG focal regions, are employed by FONAG to surveil and monitor páramos in protected areas and in areas part of community conservation agreements or owned by the water company (Joslin 2020b). The goal of this program is primarily to reduce grazing and burning in protected páramo grasslands. Guarda páramos also work as liaisons between FONAG and their rural, mainly indigenous communities to establish community conservation and development agreements. In these agreements, communities propose productive projects (e.g. household gardens, lower-elevation pastures, guinea pig, medicinal plant cultivation, and ecotourism), for which FONAG provides materials as an in-kind payment in exchange for conservation activities in high priority páramo areas (e.g. reducing livestock, planting native vegetation, controlling fires) (Joslin 2019b). According to FONAG, 18 conservation agreements have been signed with rural communities to date (<http://www.fonag.org.ec/web/programas/areas-de-conservacion-hidricas-sostenibles/>).

Much of the area where FONAG works falls within the Condor Bioserve, a bioregional vision which includes three national protected areas established starting in the 1990s. While land within the reserves

is technically controlled by the Ecuadorian government, in many cases the original landowners (many times communities and small farmers) were never compensated for their loss of certain uses of the land (whether ever formalized or not) (Echavarría 2002). There are 80+ rural, mostly indigenous communities, with a population >10,000 in the regions where FONAG works. In 2001, when FONAG began approximately 66% of the population living in this area was considered below the Ecuadorian poverty line (Leisher et al. 2012).

A key enabling legal condition for FONAG was a change in a law governing public financing in 1999, which allowed government organizations to manage funds in private organizations (Echavarría 2002). This allowed for the establishment of FONAG as an endowment that receives money from government, private, and NGO organizations and can accrue interest over time. Decisions on how to spend funds are carried out by a board of directors, made up of entities who sign the trust contract. Voting power is tied directly to the amount of financial contribution. TNC and EPMAPS were the founding constituents, but over time membership expanded to include Quito's Electric Company, two beverage companies, and an agricultural consortium (Joslin and Jepson 2018). Through a percentage (2%) of the sales of water and sewage, EPMAPS provides 90% of funding and thus has the dominant decision-making power (Bremer et al. 2016a). While EPMAPS was somewhat passive in the decision making in the beginning (on its own accord), in 2012 EPMAPS raised concerns about the efficiency of the fund in its capacity to deliver hydrological benefits and facilitated a targeting of hydrologic areas, and program leadership and focus has shifted in response (Joslin 2019). While community members, in their role as guarda páramos, are important intermediaries with the fund, they do not currently have any decision making role on the FONAG board (Bremer et al. 2016a).

Páramo grasslands

Páramo grasslands, the focal ecosystem of FONAG, are sites of high cultural, ecological, hydrological, and economic importance. Ecuadorian páramos occupy less than 2% of the land area in Ecuador, yet support tremendous amounts of endemic biodiversity, including 2,000 species of vascular plants (León-Yanez 2011) and are vital to key note species like the Andean Condor and Spectacled Bear. The livelihoods of many communities and individuals who live in or below páramos are based on varying degrees of use and management of these highland systems (Buytaert et al. 2006; Farley and Bremer 2017), and many of the most marginalized communities and smallholders rely at least partially on the páramo for grazing (Keating 2007). People have utilized páramos for at least 7000-8000 years, with activities likely focused mainly on low-frequency burning and grazing prior to Spanish colonization (White 2013). Sheep, cattle, and horse grazing began in the 1500s, and large and small landowners burned large extensions of páramos to improve the land for grazing (Hofstede 2001). Cultivation and grazing pressure intensified in many areas in the 1970s with agrarian reforms, with livestock grazing (primarily sheep and cattle) coupled with burning on 2-5 year cycles the most common current páramo land use in Ecuador. However, many communal and other landholders have worked to protect páramos for water, biodiversity, and other values, either through removing grazing or through transitioning to camelid (alpaca and llama) grazing, which requires less frequent burning (Farley and Bremer 2017).

These high elevation (normally ~3200 m to the snowline), biodiverse grasslands have become a regional hotspot for PES programs due to their critical role for water supply for Andean cities, irrigation and hydropower as well as their high biodiversity and elevated levels of soil carbon storage (Farley et al. 2011). Páramo soils are primarily Andisols, which are characterized by extremely high levels of soil carbon and related high water retention capacities (Buytaert et al. 2006; Farley et al. 2013; Bremer et al. 2016b). While most PES programs, including FONAG targeted páramo grasslands, have promoted alteration or elimination of burning and grazing practices with the goal of enhancing hydrological services and carbon sequestration, relationships between incentivized land management and ecosystem services remain poorly understood. While intensive and frequent burning has been shown to degrade páramo soils and associated hydrologic services (Hofstede and Arnout 1995; Poulenard et al. 2003), infrequent burning and less intensive grazing regimes (including with alpacas) have been shown to have little impact on soil properties and even to increase landscape species richness and diversity (Bremer et al. 2016b, 2019). The iMHEA Andean monitoring network, which includes a site in FONAG, is working to increase data on the hydrologic outcomes of páramo land management (Ochoa-Tocachi et al. 2016).

Problematization and Framing

FONAG originated primarily through efforts by the The Nature Conservancy, Fundación Antisana, and USAID to increase funding to protect biodiversity in severely under-resourced protected areas making up the informal Condor Bioserve surrounding Quito (Joslin and Jepson 2018). While there had been a major push to establish protected areas in Ecuador, the majority remained paper parks, with little funding or resources to achieve stated goals. TNC with support from USAID, presented the idea to EPMAPS as a way to protect the watersheds that supplied water to the city. A number of environmental problems were identified, including water diversion projects, development projects (e.g. oil pipelines, irrigation, hydroelectric plants), though the “inadequate” agricultural, livestock and forestry practices of rural communities became the focus of FONAG’s efforts (Echavarria 2002; Joslin 2019). FONAG framed the problem in terms of a need to generate economic alternatives to address poverty assumed to be the major factor driving overgrazing and burning in the páramo and other land uses deemed harmful to biodiversity and hydrologic services. This was based primarily on input from TNC, EPMAPS, and Fundación Antisana, with limited involvement of indigenous and other rural communities in the problem framing (Joslin 2020a).

FONAG emerged in a context of ineffective protected areas and a perceived need to increase funding through a user pays model. By broadening from biodiversity to include water, TNC shifted the discourse to ecosystem services and framed the problem in terms of water security for Quito (Joslin and Jepson 2018). At the same time, the use of the term and concept of payments for ecosystem services had been rejected by Andean indigenous communities who viewed these initiatives as attempts to privatize water sources and usurp traditional values and rights (Kauffman 2014; Joslin 2019a). Payments and even the term “incentives” are generally avoided by FONAG, due to their association with privatization and commodification of nature (Kauffman 2014). Yet, Joslin (2020a) argues that FONAG still employs much of the characteristics of PES and even self-identified as such in the 2009 strategic plan, defined as: “a mechanism of payments for ecosystem services directed towards protecting and regenerating water

sources” (FONAG 2009: 1). More recently, FONAG has adopted language of reciprocity, describing productive projects as “co-mechanisms of reciprocity for the protection of conservation of the zones of hydrologic interest” (Dominguez 2014:1 in Joslin 2020a).

In 1997 when the design and negotiation of FONAG began, a specific hydrologic service was not identified in a highly technical way; rather there was a general idea of generating financing for protecting biodiverse watersheds where EPMAPS supplied water. This was likely both for water quality as well as water regulation (maintaining dry season flow), though it was not explicitly expressed as such. Biodiversity was also a major initial goal given that biodiversity conservation was a major impetus for the establishment of the fund.

Values and value articulation

At the start of the program, there was no value-articulation methods used per se, rather a focus on hydrologic services came from a need to finance under-resourced protected areas (Joslin and Jepson 2018). EPMAPS was by far the largest contributor to the fund, and as such, FONAG focused on areas considered important for the water company. Guarda Páramos, which are hired by FONAG from rural communities identify potential productive projects with communities, which are presented to FONAG. Accordingly, rural communities play an important role in designing interventions. FONAG’s original strategic plan included a multi-actor platform designed by the NGO Fundación Futuro Latinoamericano, which would create micro-watershed committees with representation from rural communities to collaboratively design and implement watershed management plans financed through FONAG, but the idea was put on hold in 2012 (Kauffman 2014; Joslin and Jepson 2018).

EPMAPS goals and priority areas are central to FONAG because they are by far the most important funder of the fund. Joslin (2020b) describes how guarda páramos often “translate” FONAG into a value system that resonates with local communities, focusing on community benefits and protecting areas for future generations, rather than a focus on serving Quito which was rejected or ignored by guarda páramos (Joslin and Jepson 2018). However, Joslin (2020b: 12) argues that the work of guarda páramos still “serves to reorder and compartmentalize the landscape and reinforce ideological positions regarding human relations and the environment.” Specifically Joslin (2020b:) argues that FONAG facilitated a transition away from the páramo as a site of “uncultivated production that is integrated into indigenous Andean livelihoods” to conservation spaces. However, it is important to note that FONAG is one of many conservation organizations working in the area (Leisher et al. 2012), so this process would be complex and not just have to do with FONAG, and may indeed have been on the volition of communities themselves.

There is little evidence of direct protest or contestation by rural communities, though Joslin (2019) suggests that some of FONAG’s initial attempts to enroll communities failed based on rejection of the program as a financial, neoliberal mechanism. The indigenous community of El Hato, for example, was reported to have declined a very early FONAG proposal because it did not adequately recognize the community’s long-standing work in the absence of incentives (Diehn 2005). TNC’s study of the social impacts of FONAG (which was rife with analytical problems), tells an account of working with the

indigenous community Oyacachi from the perspective of the previous FONAG manager, Pablo Lloret (Leisher et al. 2012: 10):

“After a little more than a year working with the community, Lloret reports that locals brought the cows down from the local páramo grasslands that provide water for Quito, fenced off the area, and ceased burning the grasslands. ‘We were singing our praises and declaring victory,’ says Lloret. But it wasn’t long before the bad news filtered back to Quito: the people had brought the cows back to the Páramo. Local people perceived that the benefits they received from the water fund were not sufficient to offset the costs of not grazing the Páramo... Rather than insist that locals remove their cows and cease burning the grasslands, they decided to work harder to win local trust and confidence, and provide local residents with tangible, reasonable alternatives. This time, they asked the people of the community what projects most interested them. The town’s artisans made simple wooden spoons that Lloret reports sold for 50 cents apiece in markets in neighboring towns. Yet they were talented woodworkers and carving came easy to them. With training, they began to make sculptures of osos de anteojos, the celebrated spectacled bear of the Andean mountains, which sold for \$500 dollars or more in upscale markets in Quito. Lloret now had his leverage. With viable alternatives, the people could bring their cattle down from the mountains and still make a living. And they did.”

This approach emphasizing community empowerment and capacity building, is now implemented across FONAG partner communities and has served to become part of their engagement model. More critical research is needed in this area, particularly as FONAG has evolved to include more social scientists on their team and to incorporate a more active water justice approach, including supporting WASH initiatives (Meza Prado 2019).

Distribution of costs and benefits

FONAG does not use direct payments, but rather provides compensation in the form of productive projects (e.g. guinea pig husbandry, household gardens, lower-elevation pasture, household hardens, medicinal plant cultivation, and ecohusbandry) (Joslin 2020a). FONAG provides material, and in exchange, communities are required to carry out conservation activities (e.g. reducing livestock, planting native vegetation, controlling fires in the páramo). While agreements are made with the community as a whole, in a review of 13 FONAG reports between 2008-2013, Joslin (2019) found that direct benefits are received by just 15% of total households. Likewise, in an in-depth study of three communities where FONAG works Joslin (2019) found that 6-13% of community members can be considered direct beneficiaries. Communities are selected based on their location and management of páramos important for Quito’s water supply; there is no targeting based on poverty criteria or other social metrics, but the majority of communities are indigenous and 60% below the Ecuadorian poverty line (Leisher et al. 2012). Another form of compensation is through hiring guarda páramos, who are paid by FONAG to monitor and surveil FONAG conservation areas and community protected areas as well to serve as a liason with rural communities. Finally, a more recent form of compensation, and part of FONAG’s move towards a more active social justice approach is to support communities who have been excluded from receiving municipal water supplies to secure safe and secure water supplies (Meza Prado 2019)

There is little evidence on whether communities or guarda páramos view various compensations as just. Leisher et al. (2012; as referenced above), provide a vignette from the perspective of the former FONAG technical secretary who described how they learned from the experience of a community not being satisfied with the compensation and so rebelled by bringing cows back up to the páramo. According to the former secretary, based on this experience, FONAG improved its compensation efforts to better meet community goals, and recent projects have taken this a step forward towards addressing real environmental injustice including a lack of access to safe drinking water (Meza Prado 2019). Taking a deeper and critical approach, Joslin (2019) examined three communities working with FONAG. In one case (the community of Paquiestancia), she concluded that while FONAG motivated direct beneficiaries of a productive project, the community rejected the project because they did not see benefits as fairly distributed. In another case (Oyacachi), the community agreed to a FONAG contract despite the fact that it benefitted a select portion of the population because this was a community with a suite of development projects from many NGOs and other organizations. In this case, the subset of community members participating in a guinea pig project were not satisfied with the economic benefits provided by the project and stopped the enterprise.

Limited research suggests that communities and park guards carry out FONAG-related conservation activities for multiple reasons, including their desire to protect the páramo for current and future generations. Joslin (2019)'s ethnographic study of three FONAG communities finds that most of the communities were already undergoing the conservation activities that FONAG incentivized, and many saw FONAG as rewarding good stewardship which they carried out for cultural, ecological, and hydrologic benefits. Based on interviews with guarda páramos, Joslin and Jeplin (2018) found that many guarda páramos work many more hours than compensated for, largely because they see their work as protecting resources for their community.

FONAG conservation agreements primarily impact community members who utilize the páramo for grazing. There are no studies (that we know of) which analyze which community members or what percentage of community members utilize the páramo for grazing, though in other parts of Ecuador it is often community members with the least access to land who utilize the communal páramo the most (Bremer et al. 2014). However, Joslin (2019) also found no evidence that FONAG actually caused any of the reductions in grazing; rather such reductions were already occurring on the community's initiative and FONAG was viewed as a reward or as perceived compensation owed. Joslin (2019) evaluated the case of the first FONAG project where FONAG worked directly with a small (23 people) women's group, Flor Andina, in the community of Paquiestancia from 2007-2011. This case was considered an important success by FONAG and USAID, though Joslin (2019) contests this. During this time three agreements were made with FONAG where the compensation included, household gardens, guinea pig production, and a pasture improvement project, and the conservation agreement required the community to contribute labor to a litter clean up, native vegetation planting, and removing livestock from the páramo. Joslin (2019) suggests that, while the contracts were with Flor Andina, FONAG expected the entire community of Paquiestancia to support the conservation agreements. While the community supported the litter clean-up which was proposed by Flor Andina, the community rejected the outplanting project proposed by FONAG as there was a previously unsuccessful planting effort in the area. The livestock removal was

found to have begun prior to the arrival of FONAG both to support ecotourism and water quality, so not attributable to FONAG (Joslin 2019).

There is little evidence on how FONAG agreements are enforced beyond the guarda páramo program. A TNC-led study cautioned against conditionality in water funds given that productive projects cannot be returned (Goldman-Benner et al. 2012), and in general, productive activities are viewed as practices which facilitate moving livestock away from the páramo.

Outcomes

FONAG does not have explicit “upstream” social goals, but sees productive projects as focusing on alternative agricultural production as a more equitable way to take pressure off of páramo lands (Farley et al. 2011). In terms of downstream goals, FONAG does seek to reduce operational and financial risks related to water availability during the dry season (Bremer et al. 2016a). FONAG’s website reports the following social monitoring statistics: 46,725 people who have participated in environmental education projects and 18 conservation agreements signed. FONAG’s *Agua a Fondo* newsletter also frequently highlights success stories of community agreements and guarda páramos, including a recent feature on five guarda páramos, with a quote from one from the community of Oyacachi: “we should unite to leave our children a large inheritance, a planet to live,” also providing evidence of the relational motivations for participation (Morales 2019).

The Nature Conservancy set out to monitor the upstream social outcomes of FONAG, but had a number of challenges including: 1) participants were not able to distinguish FONAG projects from other development projects; 2) widespread interview fatigue among participant communities; and 3) issues with a consultant who did not provide access to the full data set, including interview transcripts (Leisher et al. 2012). The TNC report provides two vignettes, including the one about Oyacachi to demonstrate social benefits. Leisher et al. (2012) also provide a case study from the community of Cuyuja, concluding that 40 families benefit from organic gardens and that FONAG has also provided medicinal plants, fruit trees, guinea pigs and chickens. They suggest the benefits perceived by the community are: healthier diets and reduced use of chemicals; improved farming practices for soil and water conservation; and reduced expenses. It is unclear where the data came from for this case study, but likely from an interview with the community leader, Ricardo Urcuando.

The most substantial work on the social and institutional dimensions of FONAG comes from an ethnographic PhD geography thesis (Joslin and Jepson 2018; Joslin 2019, 2020a, b). This work includes archival analysis of FONAG and other reports, interviews with guarda páramos, and ethnographic research and interviews in three communities where FONAG works. As reported earlier, Joslin (2019) found that 6-13% of community members in the communities she focused on can be considered direct beneficiaries. This is slightly below the 15% found from a review of 13 FONAG reports between 2008 and 2013. Joslin (2020b) suggests that FONAG’s guarda páramo program compartmentalizes the landscapes and changes the páramo from a site historically used for uncultivated production and central indigenous livelihoods and culture to one where the páramo is a conservation space. There are many different interpretations of this transition, and this statement conflicts with her previous account that communities were already

shifting livestock down on their own accord in efforts to protect water supplies and due to shifting economic opportunities and constraints. Joslin (2019), also reported that one FONAG agreement in Paquiestancia created tensions between the community organization that FONAG contracted with and the larger community over a planting project.

No studies were found on gender impacts or on impacts on different socio-economic groups beyond what is explained earlier. However, many of FONAG's staff are women (<http://www.fonag.org.ec/web/conocenos-2/equipo-fonag/>) and the guarda páramo program has evolved to include women. Thus, it would be interesting to explore the gender impacts of these programs.

In terms of current ecological objectives, hydrological outcomes (dry season flow and water quality) are considered primary goals and biodiversity goals are considered secondary (Farley et al. 2011). In a survey in 2015, program managers also identified carbon as a potential co-benefit (Bremer et al. 2016a). In 2012, EPMAPS became a more active member of the board and began to criticize FONAG's lack of focus on water outcomes. Given EPMAP's voting power, they facilitated a re-organization that replaced the technical secretary and redefined areas for intervention, focusing more heavily on areas deemed critical for their intakes (Joslin and Jepson 2018). FONAG reports a number of land-cover change-based statistics on its webpage: 19,870 hectares owned, 6,593 hectares under formal conservation agreements, and 15,374.51 hectares recuperated and restored.

Several studies have measured ecological impact, with loose links to hydrologic services through measures of vegetation cover. A diagnostic plot-level study of aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems Encalada et al. (2017) found no difference between aquatic systems in and out of FONAG managed areas, but that FONAG managed areas had significantly lower amounts of bare ground and higher coverage and representation of shrubs which characterize "healthy" páramo systems. They conclude that the vegetation in FONAG sites is starting to recover after significant reduction in grazing and burning pressure (Encalada et al. 2016). They further hypothesize that recovery of aquatic systems will follow. A TNC study (Leisher et al. 2012) also found ecological improvements in FONAG managed sites, including that the conservation sites had higher plant species richness, higher aquatic invertebrate species richness and number of rare species, than the control sites. The researchers caution however, that without time series data is challenging to infer causality of the water fund. The same study found slightly higher water quality in conservation sites, but few significant differences; however, they also found that even within the water funds sites, water quality exceeded national standards for total coliforms, fecal coliform, and *Escherichia coli* indicating fecal contamination of water. FONAG also reported benefits of their conservation activities in restoring the food chain for the endangered Andean condor (*Vultur gryphus*) which was seen consuming a deer in the Hydrologic Conservation Area of Antisana (owned by EPMAPS and managed by FONAG), for the first time (Kohn 2020).

FONAG, along with EPMAPS, and the Instituto Nacional de Meteorología e Hidrología (INAMHI), administers the Red Integrada de Monitoreo Hidrometeorológico (RIMH; integrated network of hydrometeorological data), which includes 29 meteorological stations, 68 flow stations, and 33 hydrologic stations distributed throughout Quito's main watersheds (Agua a Fondo, date?). In 2014, 2-years prior to the commencement

of restoration activities (in order to have a 2-year baseline), FONAG also established a water quantity monitoring program to assess the impacts of their restoration activities in the Jatunhuaycu watershed, which is part of the Antisana property (Fuentes, 2013). The water monitoring system design follows the iMHEA protocol measuring water level every 15 minutes (Ochoa-Tocachi et al. 2016). As part of the regional network to monitor Andean ecosystems, the specific focus is on understanding the impacts of vegetation cover (through active and passive páramo restoration) on soil hydrology and the supply and regulation of water flow. FONAG collaborated with EPMAPS on a return on investment study based on water quality and quantity, which suggested that FONAG has had a positive return on investment for EPMAPS; final results of this study are in preparation for review (Ochoa-Tocachi 2019).

Finally, FONAG's newsletter *Agua a Fondo* reports that the water fund is helping the city adapt to climate change, including through developing fire response networks. As temperatures rise and urban development continues, dry brush and eucalyptus forests near the city can catch fire easily. The fire department was not prepared to face peri-urban and rural fires so FONAG developed a partnership with the fire department, training guarda páramos and staff in fire prevention, management and control (Falconí 2019).

References

- Bremer LL, Auerbach DA, Goldstein JH, et al (2016a) One size does not fit all: Natural infrastructure investments within the Latin American Water Funds Partnership. *Ecosyst Serv* 17:. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.12.006>
- Bremer LL, Farley KA, Chadwick OA, Harden CP (2016b) Changes in carbon storage with land management promoted by payment for ecosystem services. *Environ Conserv* 43:397–406. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892916000199>
- Bremer LL, Farley KA, Demaagd N, et al (2019) Biodiversity outcomes of payment for ecosystem services : lessons from páramo grasslands. *Biodivers Conserv*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-019-01700-3>
- Bremer LL, Farley KA, Lopez-Carr D (2014) What factors influence participation in payment for ecosystem services programs? An evaluation of Ecuador's SocioPáramo program. *Land use policy* 36:. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2013.08.002>
- Buytaert W, Célleri R, De Bièvre B, et al (2006) Human impact on the hydrology of the Andean páramos. *Earth-Science Rev* 79:53–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2006.06.002>
- Diehn SA (2005) Rival modesl for land management in Ecuador. *Cult Surv Q* 29:
- Echavarría M (2002) Financing watershed conservation: The FONAG water fund in Quito, Ecuador. In: *Selling Forest Environmental Services: Market-Based Mechanisms for Conservation and Development*. pp 91–101

- Echavarría M, Zavala P, Coronel L (2015) Infraestructura Verde en el Sector de Agua Potable en América Latina y el Caribe : Tendencias , Retos y Oportunidades. Inf Tec para Entes Reguladores Agua Potable y Saneam las Américas
- Encalada A, Suárez E, Schrekinger J, et al (2016) Case Study 2: FONAG. In: Bremer L, Vogl AL, Bievre B de, Petry P (eds) Bridging Theory and Practice for Monitoring in Water Funds. The Latin American Water Funds Partnership and the Nautral Capital Project, pp 20–31
- Falconí D (2019) Juntos por el agua contra el fuego. Agua a Fondo, #43 7
- Farley K a., Bremer LL, Harden CP, Hartsig J (2013) Changes in carbon storage under alternative land uses in biodiverse Andean grasslands: Implications for payment for ecosystem services. *Conserv Lett* 6:21–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2012.00267.x>
- Farley KA, Anderson WG, Bremer LL, Harden CP (2011) Compensation for ecosystem services: An evaluation of efforts to achieve conservation and development in Ecuadorian paramo grasslands. *Environ Conserv* 38:393–405. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S037689291100049X>
- Farley KA, Bremer LL (2017) “Water Is Life”: Local Perceptions of Páramo Grasslands and Land Management Strategies Associated with Payment for Ecosystem Services. *Ann Am Assoc Geogr* 107:371–381
- FONAG (2009) Plan Estratégico 2009-2013 [Strategic Plan 2009-2013]. Quito, Ecuador
- Goldman-Benner RL, Benitez S, Boucher T, et al (2012) Water funds and payments for ecosystem services: practice learns from theory and theory can learn from practice. *Oryx* 46:55–63. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605311001050>
- Hofstede R (2001) El impacto de las actividades humanas sobre el páramo. In: Proyecto Páramo (ed) Los Páramos del Ecuador: particularidades, problemas, y perspectivas. Quito
- Hofstede RGM, Arnout JGA (1995) P mo Graands , Colombia . Biomass of Grazed , and Burned , Root and Ratio Aboveground : Belowground
- Joslin A (2020a) Translating Water Fund Payments for Ecosystem Services in the Ecuadorian Andes. *Dev Change* 51:94–116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12542>
- Joslin A (2020b) Dividing “Above” and “Below”: Constructing Territory for Ecosystem Service Conservation in the Ecuadorian Highlands. *Ann Am Assoc Geogr* 0:1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2020.1735988>
- Joslin A (2019a) Translating Water Fund Payments for Ecosystem Services in the Ecuadorian Andes. *Dev Change* 0:1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12542>

- Joslin AJ (2019b) Unpacking 'Success': Applying Local Perceptions to Interpret Influences of Water Fund Payments for Ecosystem Services in the Ecuadorian Andes. *Soc Nat Resour* 32:617–637. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2018.1559379>
- Joslin AJ, Jepson WE (2018) Territory and authority of water fund payments for ecosystem services in Ecuador's Andes. *Geoforum* 91:10–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2018.02.016>
- Kauffman CM (2014) Financing watershed conservation: Lessons from Ecuador's evolving water trust funds. *Agric Water Manag* 145:39–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2013.09.013>
- Keating PL (2007) Fire Ecology and Conservation in the High Tropical Andes: Observations from Northern Ecuador. *J Lat Am Geogr* 6:43–62. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lag.2007.0003>
- Kohn S (2020) El cóndor andino recuperó su dieta en Antisana. *Agua a Fondo*, #40 5
- Leisher C, Hess S, Sherwood D, Boucher T (2012) Report on the Ecological and Socioeconomic Assessments of the Quito Water Fund. *Nat Conserv*
- León-Yanez S (2011) La Flora de los Páramos Ecuatorianos. In: Mena P, Castillo A, Flores S, et al. (eds) *Páramo: Paisaje estudiado, habitado, manejado institucionalizado. Selección de textos de las Serie Páramo, órgano de difusión del Grupo de Trabajo en Páramos del Ecuador (GTP)*. Abya Yala, Quito
- Meza Prado K (2019) Create in Quito, Ecuador: Fire stories at the center of water and equity. In: *Creat. Initiat.* <https://create.umn.edu/tag/quito/>
- Morales A (2019) Cuidar los páramos con la vida. *Agua a Fondo*, #39 10
- Ochoa-tocachi BF (2019) Participatory Hydrological Monitoring to Support Sustainable Water Resources Management. 207
- Ochoa-Tocachi BF, Buytaert W, De Bièvre B, et al (2016) Impacts of land use on the hydrological response of tropical Andean catchments. *Hydrol Process* 30:4074–4089. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10980>
- Poulenard J, Podwojewski P, Herbillon AJ (2003) Characteristics of non-allophanic Andisols with hydric properties from the Ecuadorian páramos. *Geoderma* 117:267–281. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(03\)00128-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(03)00128-9)
- White S (2013) Grass páramo as hunter-gatherer landscape. *The Holocene* 23:898–915

***Watershared* program, Bolivia**

Nigel Asquith

How are values articulated through PES programs, and how do these shape social and environmental outcomes? How do decision-makers make 'trade-offs' among multiple values, and whose values come to matter, and how?

1. Background and context:

Brief description of the program (for introductory purposes):

Geographical extent, ecosystem services (ES) rewarded, approximate level of participation, type of compensation.

Watershared Agreements (Acuerdos Recíprocos por Agua in Spanish) are based on the logic that protecting upstream forests helps maintain water supplies, and that sustainable conservation requires the financial participation of water users. *Watershared* programs provide upstream landowners with economic alternatives, such as fruit trees, irrigation pipes and beehives, in exchange for forest conservation. Upstream landowners thus move away from drought susceptible annual agriculture, and at the same time improve hydrological functioning, ensuring water quality and quantity for human consumption and agricultural production downstream, thus helping all the watershed communities simultaneously develop and mitigate and adapt to climate change.

The first *Watershared* Program was initiated in 2003 between the villagers in the upstream town of Santa Rosa and irrigators in the downstream town of Los Negros, in the Santa Cruz valleys of eastern Bolivia (Asquith et al 2008). Six downstream irrigators negotiated a ground-breaking deal with their upstream counterparts. The program's crucial innovation is that it provides development inputs – beehives and fruit tree seedlings – as “seed capital” that kick starts a process by which, over time, downstream water users can build the required local institutions and ultimately pay for the costs of upstream conservation.

To date, the *Watershared* model has been adopted in 58 municipalities of Bolivia, where 367,148 hectares of forests are being protected, benefiting 6,871 indigenous and rural families through environmentally friendly water access and productive incentives (Asquith, 2016). As one example, the Comarapa Local Water Fund was set up in 2007 (Vargas et al. 2010), and now disburses ~ \$15,000 worth of development projects to upstream families every year, in exchange for the conservation of 12,106 ha, with 6% annual growth. In 2018, the Comarapa Local Fund graduated away from donor support to become a standalone 100% self-financed institution.

Contextual factors

Biophysical conditions

Watershared has proven to be a robust “PES” model: rapid self-replication in five countries across a range of ecosystems and socio-economic realities. From indigenous Guarani communities earning water tanks in return for protecting the dry Chaco forest on Bolivia’s border with Argentina; to intensive cattle farmers above Bogota getting premium milk prices in exchange for conserving their riverbanks; to small maize producers receiving bee hives to help them prevent pesticide pollution of the Tekit cenote source in Mexico’s Yucatan peninsula, the *Watershared* model has been replicated across Latin America (Martinez et al., 2013, Asquith 2016, Bauchet et al., 2020). In most *Watershared* areas, forests are perceived as contributing to providing high-quality water for human consumption and irrigation. Gastrointestinal illnesses are endemic across the region when water intakes are not protected. For example, the health centre of Moro Moro, a Bolivian community of approximately 800 people, treated 236 cases of diarrhoea in 2015 (Pynegar et al. 2019, Abell et al., 2017). Traditional farming systems involve cattle grazing freely within the forests from where communities take their water, so fecal contamination from cattle is an important contributor to the high diarrhoea prevalence. Some communities have rudimentary sedimentation and filtration systems, but these are of limited effectiveness and often become clogged with sediment after each rainfall event. Chlorination or other chemical treatment is rare.

Land inequities

A range of land ownership and tenure types are present in regions with *Watershared* programs. The first program was initiated in the mid-altitude valleys of Bolivia’s Santa Cruz Department, where land is owned individually, and most landowners now have official government approved title. At other *Watershared* sites, land is owned communally by indigenous groups, with title held by the group over a much wider area. The crucial determinant of whether someone can join a *Watershared* program is that local authorities confirm that they are legally responsible for land use and land use change on that parcel. Compensations can thus be given to de jure and de facto owners of the land, but not to users of the land working as daily labourers or renting lands. Compensations can be given to individuals, families, or other groups, or to communities, depending who is the de facto, or ideally de jure landowner (Bétrisey and Mager, 2014).

Political conditions

Governance context (relevant institutional framework and policy context, including related policy and legislation)

Watershared schemes function in indigenous and non-indigenous municipalities alike, with five different types of national governance frameworks (Bolivia, Peru, Ecuador, Colombia and Mexico). It thus appears that *Watershared* has a robust institutional design that works at many levels. This is primarily because the model decentralizes all design, decision-making and financing to the most basic level: local governments and water users associations. The basic intervention is always refined and adapted by participants, but the philosophy underlying *Watershared* is always the same: “people who provide water share it, people who benefit from water share the benefits”. If upstream water “providers” and downstream water users can agree on this statement, then the rest of *Watershared* creation is simply ironing out the details.

Power relations and political influence among stakeholders

Local institutions have usually played an intermediary role between upstream and downstream stakeholders to help set up *Watershared* programs. Such entities are frequently NGOs (such as Natura in Bolivia, Instituto Bien Comun, Oxapampa, Peru, and Naturaleza y Cultura, Loja, Ecuador) but have also comprised regional governments (CORPOGUAVIO and CVC in Colombia), municipal governments (Pasorapa, Bolivia) or water companies (ETAPA, Cuenca, Ecuador). Such intermediaries tend to have more political, financial and human resources than other actors. They have wielded these resources in different ways, sometimes primarily supporting poverty reduction for water providers, but more usually focusing on water quality improvements for users. Municipal governments and water users (or their representatives) tend to finance the vast majority of *Watershared* compensations and so these actors wield the most power, deciding exactly where programs are focused, and what value and types of compensation are offered. Nevertheless, all *Watershared* programs are designed and negotiated amongst the local stakeholders, so the actual influence of each actor is entirely dependent on the local situation.

Problematization and framing (defining the problem)

How was the environmental problem defined? Who was empowered in/excluded from this decision?

The first *Watershared* program was initiated as a response to perceived water shortages, caused by invasions of migrant farmers into forests bordering Bolivia's Amboró National Park. Although downstream water users blamed upstream deforestation, this growing scarcity was probably a combined result of factors reducing water supply (such as land-use changes), higher water off-take from irrigators upstream (due to increased population and more intense cropping), and losses during water distribution. Nevertheless a clear local perception of forest–water links existed: with clouds almost permanently present above the upstream forests, downstream farmers had a strong belief that forest protection and the maintenance of water supplies were linked.

Local upstream farmers blamed recent illegal colonists for land-grabbing and deforestation, and so were able to form an alliance with downstream users to solve their joint problem. The new migrants, the supposed cause of the problem, were excluded from discussions and decision-making, as their recent arrival provided them with no standing in the community. Nor did they own land, so had no de jure or long term de facto role in landuse decision-making. Notwithstanding this initial focus on water, few local funds were available to initiate watershed protection, so an external donor funded the start-up of the first *Watershared* program to help protect habitat for eleven species of neotropical migratory birds (Asquith et al., 2008).

How was PES chosen as the solution? Who was empowered in/excluded from this decision?

What ecosystem services (ES) were prioritized in the initial design? Who was identified as beneficiaries and potential providers of ES, and how?

An intermediary NGO, Natura provided the first motivation and impetus for the program, based on a locally observed problem of increasing water scarcity. An external donor provided funds to catalyze conservation until local counterpart funding could be found (Asquith et al. 2008). During the project negotiation phase, farmers from upstream Santa Rosa and downstream Los Negros met and after some iterations agreed on the annual payment of one beehive for every 10 ha of forest protected for a year—a cash equivalent of ~US\$3/ha/year, plus the value of accompanying apicultural training. The alternatives discussed were road improvements, and marketplace or bridge construction in Santa Rosa.

Upstream farmers specifically rejected the option of payments in cash. As one enrolled farmer explained: *“If I receive cash, I know I will spend it right away. Instead, I want these payments to create something that lasts”* (Asquith et al. 2008). Negotiations were between volunteers who had self selected as interested in water conservation, and included only downstream irrigators and upstream landowners. Upstream landless farmers were effectively excluded, as they were unable to make landuse decisions, and hence play a direct role in forest conservation.

The *Watershared* logic, from initiation, was that the fewer parties in a negotiation, the easier it is to come to an agreement. Only once a pilot agreement was struck that was acceptable to the key parties – upstream landowners and downstream water users – were other individuals and institutions involved. Now that *Watershared* has spread across almost 80 municipalities across the Andes, and the robustness of the model is well understood, promoters are experimenting with different versions, such as involving all upstream residents in community-based agreements.

3. Values and value articulation:

What value articulation method(s) was/were used in the initial design process (e.g. MCA, ecosystem modeling/targeting, referenda, focus groups, etc.)? How was spatial targeting and prioritization done? How were upstream participants/ES ‘providers’ targeted?

How and by whom were these methods chosen?

Who was involved? What roles did they play?

Two groups of upstream residents rarely participated in the initial *Watershared* programs: recent immigrants and small landowners. Immigrants – often already socially and politically marginalized in community structures – were de jure excluded from the scheme because they do not own land. The size of the land owned also matters; the compensation is proportional to the amount of land that the landowner conserves; so landowners who own very little land—and are already considered poorer—therefore receive only small compensations, which discourages participation (Bétrisey et al. 2016). While the poorest landowners didn’t sign up for the program, land owners who do join tend to be those who are more socially embedded within their community and view environmental protection as important (Grillos 2016, Jack and Recalde 2014).

One of the defining characteristics of *Watershared* is its organic growth, both within and between villages and municipalities. No decisions are made centrally, nor are stakeholders deliberately identified and either included or excluded. Only one criteria is non negotiable for a *Watershared* program, that:

- The alternative landuse to upstream conservation is low value, such as extensive cattle grazing. (*Watershared* will not work, for example, when the alternative is mining or urban development)

However, the program seems to work better in watersheds that:

- Have threatened but reasonably well-conserved vegetation cover the upper watershed.
- Do not depend on glaciers and snowmelt, but rather on vegetation cover.
- Cover 200–2000 sq. km (to ensure a visible upstream–downstream relationship).
- Have an altitudinal gradient of at least 500 metres and an average 5% slope (to enhance the probability that there is an obvious upstream–downstream relationship).
- Support downstream communities who are able to, or may be convinced to contribute
- Can differentiate between upstream and downstream communities, but these are relatively close, preferably with a larger population downstream.
- Have an upstream population with influence over upstream land use decision-making.
- Water use is from surface sources.

These criteria were developed by the NGO (Asquith and Vargas 2007), but were not meant to be definitive or exclusive. Indeed once these basic guidance has been taken into account, *Watershared* expansion into new municipalities has been rather ad-hoc, following funding oportinties and/or calls for help rather than an overarching strategy.

More generally, municipal or community authorities take the decision that they want to set up a *Watershared* program because they share the philosophy of “people who provide water share it, people who benefit from water share the benefits”, and they think it would work in their community. They then organically build their program based on the communities’ own needs, challenges and legal, economic and cultural context, not undertaking many studies or analyses. Indeed the *Watershared* model is based more on the precautionary principle than publishable science.

Within a community, the only spatial targeting decision is that programs focus on conserving land along river banks, especially those upstream of the community water intake pipe, a mapping process that can be undertaken quickly by municipal and NGO staff.

How and why did some values become influential over others in program design and/or implementation?

What values were reflected/excluded in the design process? What forms of knowledge? What worldviews?

Whose values were reflected/excluded? Whose knowledge? Whose worldviews?

Was this process contested? If so how? (E.g. other strategies by which marginalized values might be expressed – protest, counter-organizing, sabotage).

Were trade-offs made among multiple objectives, and if so how and by whom?

Natura developed, refined, improved and adapted the basic *Watershared* model, not in situ at the pilot sites, but by trying out new versions to new municipalities. Each new iteration of the model is viewed as a new pilot, or a hypothesis to be tested. Some things have remained the same everywhere, for example, the focus on reciprocity and solidarity as motivating values for enrolling and complying. Indeed, the *Watershared* version of the PES concept was never about “payments” or “services”. Rather, reciprocity and solidarity was cited by upstream farmers as a key element in their decision to enter. The main motivation landowners mentioned for their participation was not the market value of compensation but the hope that the ARA would contribute to the collective’s wellbeing, and to community cohesion and recognition from downstream actors (Bétrisey and Mager, 2014).

Moreover, simple “recognition” seems to have been a prominent motivation for many upstream farmers. Such recognition was a hope, an expected result of participation in the scheme as well as a more general way of entering and maintaining horizontal relationships with relevant longer term partners. It was expressed as “being taken into account,” “feeling noticeable and noticed,” “being respected,” and being recognized as a municipal “citizen” by municipal authorities (Bétrisey et al. 2018, see also d’Adda 2011).

Other program characteristics have been maintained across Bolivia, but have changed fundamentally in other countries. For over 10 years, almost all Bolivian municipalities used the \$3/ha equivalent as the baseline starting value of a compensation package, although variations were possible based on plot location (nearer to the river was valued more) or how many hectares were being conserved (a landowner’s two hundredth hectare receives less than the first) (Bottazzi et al 2018). Values have been an order of magnitude different in Colombia for example, and even in Bolivia, Natura has piloted a version in which compensation varies with both the number of hectares enrolled, and also with the number of residents in the upstream communities (i.e. for two communities both conserving 1000 hectares, the community with more residents will receive higher levels of compensation). Given the decentralized local nature of each *Watershared* program such variations provide a series of experiments to assess which model works best.

In order to quantify these experimental assessments of *Watershared* effectiveness, Natura has undertaken a series of Randomized Control trials (Asquith 2020, Wiik et al 2019, Wiik et al 2020). Experimentation has required standardization, and a greater stress on more quantifiable values, but baseline and endline socioeconomic surveys of participating and non-participating households allowed Natura to maintain a focus on the values important to upstream landowners (Grillos 2016, Grillos et al 2019, Bottazzi et al 2018). For example, while most community members, pre intervention, agreed

with the statements “If a person works more than others, it is fair that they earn more money” and “It's the responsibility of the government to reduce inequality of income between people with a lot of money and people with a little money”, such beliefs were stronger after someone had participated in the program (Grillos et al 2019)

4. Distribution of costs and benefits:

Benefits:

Compensation/payments:

What kind of compensation is used (in-kind vs. monetary)?

How and to whom are benefits distributed (e.g. individual landholders/households, community organizations, etc.)? Based on what criteria (equity, need, etc.)?

Compensations consist of beehives, coffee or fruit tree plants, water tanks and tubes and so forth as well as capacity building related to the use of these new items (Bétrisey et al. 2018). In general, the amount of compensation depends on the amount of land conserved as well as on the distance between the plot and the river catchments, but is not designed to cover economic opportunity costs. Compensations are given to de jure and de facto owners of the land but not to users of the land working as daily labourers or renting lands (Bétrisey and Mager, 2014). Agreements have been signed with individuals, families, or other groups, and with entire communities.

How were distribution decisions made (who was involved, what was the nature of their participation)? This may reference material above.

Do participants perceive distribution and compensation as just? Why or why not? Were distribution decisions contested, and if so how?

In the initial pilot, all upper watershed landowners were invited to voluntarily enter the program at the established rates. They decided what plot to enroll, and the time period of their contract. Building trust and confidence in the concept has been a slow but positive process. After a contract runs out the participant can then chose whether or not to re-enroll. Some service providers have thus been part of the program for over 15 years, with other, new providers joining every year. Five farmers initially participated in the Los Negros program in 2003, protecting 592 ha. They were joined in 2004 by seven more who protected an additional 252 ha (Asquith et al 2008). By 2020, 41 families were conserving 2400 ha in a self sustaining program, annually funded by \$7,000 from 1,300 water users and the municipal government for. The Los Negros Fund has now “graduated” from needing NGO support.

Some landowners have expressed discontent at the compensation levels, suggesting that least some actors view the program as unjust. *Watershared* promoters have responded that their role is as a catalyst helping to start the program, and that implementation details are decided by local actors: concerns should thus be directed to the municipal governments and the water users who are implementing and financing

the program. Whether the scheme is “just” or not, however, is perhaps the wrong question. Most important is that participants give their free prior and informed consent to be part of the program, they co-invest heavily in it, they usually renew their contract after expiration, and many of their neighbors have subsequently joined the program. Not one municipality where Natura has tried to initiate a Watershared program has rejected the idea, and no Bolivian *Watershared* programs have failed or been abandoned.

Watershared has always promoted a “learning-by-doing” PES strategy: Natura has found that learning main lessons when money is already changing hands, rather than trying to architect all the details in advance is far more socially acceptable to local actors (Asquith et al 2008). The program philosophy is that it is better to spend, for example, \$10,000 on studies to develop a “good-enough” program that delivers \$50,000 of benefits to more or less the correct upstream service providers, rather than spend \$50,000 on designing a perfect program that delivers \$10,000 in local benefits to the “right” landowners. While the former better fits the interests, vision and worldview of many governments bureaucrats, Natura has found that the latter more closely fits the interests of local actors.

What do participants perceive as benefits of the program (i.e. other motivations that might not be represented in compensation; this may include ecological benefits)?

In a Watershared program Cuenca, Ecuador, the city water provider, Empresa de Telecomunicaciones, Agua Potable, Alcantarillado y saneamiento de Cuenca (ETAPA), had for decades been working to protect the upper Yanuncay watershed. However, in upstream Soldados, villagers were viscerally opposed to ETAPA, going as far as to kidnap company staff. Downstream, demand was exceeding supply in the dry season but city users were wasting water. A two-pronged public awareness campaign called Pride for *Watershared* Agreements was able to calm tensions upstream and promote a ‘shorter showers’ initiative downstream, thereby resolving both of ETAPA’s major problems in one go. With the conflicts resolved, and a clear local mechanism of cooperation visible to all, ETAPA was then able to contract 22 *Watershared* agreements in the middle watershed, putting 1,341 ha under conservation. Because it is a cooperative community-based process, *Watershared* can help resolve conflicts. Indeed, the *Watershared* message – that everyone in a watershed is part of the same problem and so can be part of the same solution – is in itself a low-cost, local mechanism for conflict resolution (Asquith 2016).

In most Watershared programs, the economic value of the compensation is low and only marginally related to the (potential) opportunity costs of maintaining the forests (Bottazzi et al 2018). Rather, *Watershared* creates new institutions for conservation, avoiding command and control schemes, while also rejecting the ideal of market mediation, in particular by trying to harness traditional norms of collective and reciprocal action. The program does not aim to solve poverty, but it explicitly addresses the social component of conservation, by trying to create fairer institutions (Bétrisey et al. 2018)

Upstream landowners thus consider the compensation more as an indemnity or a reward for good behavior than as a payment proportional to the total economic value of the services they provide. Given that the expected benefits from new productive activities (honey, coffee, fruit production, etc.) are difficult to estimate in advance, beneficiaries see the program more in the light of traditional norms (enhancing social ties) than of market logic (individual profit) (Bétrisey and Mager, 2014).

More generally, upstream contract signers often see themselves as the first beneficiaries of conservation: For this reason they they invest heavily in co-financing compensation inputs such as barbed wire and irrigation pipes. Indeed, Bottazzi et al (2018) show that for every \$100 worth of the “fencing compensation package” the barbed wire provided to a landowner by donors, was worth \$7, the wire provided by the municipal government was worth \$15, and the landowner himself contributed more than \$75 worth of posts, staples and labor. *Watershared* can thus be best seen not as a PES, but rather as scheme that “nudges” landowners into providing themselves with an environmental “self-service.”

In the pioneer Los Negros *Watershared* program the quality of relationships between participants and the trust among them are said to have improved in the Palma Sola community, now, “people are inspired and are starting to have faith in each other” (Bétrisey et al. 2016). The program was seen to bring personal recognition from downstream actors during public events— through applause, photo sessions etc.—and increased the reputation and esteem of participants. Upstream participants are seen as “deserving respect and admiration” (Bétrisey, 2016) for their work in conservation.

This “recognition” benefit is highlighted through the dramatization of compensation events. These celebrations are ritualized and occur in the community’s main space, in front of everyone, in the presence of representatives of municipal authorities and/or downstream water cooperatives. People making conservation commitment are applauded and pictures are taken, sometimes accompanied with musical bands and dancing. *Watershared* promoters have cultivated the emotional dimension of these events, producing a “different approach” for the conservation of nature (and a “new relationship between community actors and official actors downstream (cooperatives, municipal authorities)” (Bétrisey et al. 2018). *Watershared* thus appears to both provide personal recognition in its own realm but also to contribute to a wider recognition of the upstream communities by downstream municipal authorities. With this in mind, the program can be considered to alleviate not only material but also relational poverty (Bétrisey et al. 2016).

Distribution of costs

Whose conduct is impacted by the program? Whose conduct is defined as problematic?

What land-use or other changes were required of participants? How are these changes enforced (conditionality)?

How are the costs of participation measured/accounted for (e.g. monetary opportunity costs, social and cultural impacts of livelihood change, etc.)?

What did participants perceive as costs of participation (might show mismatch between compensation and motivations)?

In early iterations of *Watershared*, upstream participants signed agreements simply to not deforest. In more recent versions, there have been three levels of contract which vary in terms of what land is eligible and what restrictions are placed on land owners. For a level 1 contract (which covers only forested land,

within 100m of a river), no cultivation is permitted within the contracted area and cattle must be excluded. Level two contracts apply on similar land to level 1 and also require no clearance but farmers can phase out cattle removal. Level 3 contracts apply to forested and shrub land not along the banks of rivers. While clearance for cultivation is forbidden, cattle rearing is acceptable. Natura conduct annual monitoring of each parcel under level 1 or level 2 and record signs of the presence of cows or clearance to verify farmers' compliance. Level 3 contracts are monitored using remote sensing. Extreme cases of non-compliance have resulted in the incentives being taken back and redistributed to the community (Bottazzi et al, 2018), but such cases are few and far between (less than 10 out of 800 contracts in the study area).

5. Outcomes

Social outcomes (based on program monitoring, where available, and subsequent studies)

Does the program have specific social impact goals? Is there monitoring for these, and how?

What social impacts have been documented (through program monitoring and in wider literature)?

What methods/proxies were used, and at what spatial and temporal scales?

What was the direction or magnitude of change?

Although individual programs may have local specific goals *Watershared* as a whole has no specific social impact goals. However, Natura has consistently quantified progress in Bolivia using three Key Performance Indicators (KPI): 1) the number of hectares conserved, 2) the number of beneficiary upstream families and 3) the proportion of program funding that comes directly or indirectly from water users. KPI 1 measures conservation impact, the other two measure social impact in terms of how many upstream families are benefitting from the alternative development projects (KPI 2), and how many users are benefitting from better water supplies and are recognizing that improvement through a willingness-to- pay for it (KPI 3).

Nevertheless the *Watershared* theory of change predicts that the incentives and conservation education provided to landowners, will lead to six social impact outcomes:

- Awareness changes relationship with forest
- Barbed wire makes it possible to manage grazing
- Cement and irrigation tubing make it possible to irrigate
- Provision of fruit tree seedlings encourages sustainable production
- Provision of barbed wire and irrigation tubing makes it possible to protect water sources
- Awareness motivates environmental engagement in community

In 2010, Natura and five municipal governments initiated a Randomized Control Trial of their *Watershared* program (Pynegar et al., 2018). A total of 129 communities were randomly allocated to treatment or control (offered agreements or not). After the program, and as predicted by the *Watershared* theory of change, treated households and treatment households had significantly more small fruit trees and more fruit trees in production than their counterfactuals. Participants also appeared to have increased the area of their land under improved grazing, and treatment households were more likely to have used barbed wire to protect their water intakes and to have done this more recently. The intervention is clearly having a positive impact on some intermediate social outcomes, but it is perhaps still too early to detect ultimate impacts (Wiik et al, 2020).

What are participants' perceptions of the program's social impacts?

In comparison to controls, participants in *Watershared* programs were more likely to perceive positive trends over the last five years in water quantity and forest condition, and more likely to perceive that the wider community cared more about the forest (Wiik et al., 2020). Moreover, in comparison to landowners who had not participated in the program in the last five years, *Watershared* participants had more positive perceptions about the economic benefits of forests and perceived that water quality was improving (Grillos et al 2019).

Ecological impacts (based on program monitoring, where available, and subsequent studies)

What ecological outcomes are prioritized, for what beneficiaries, and how are these monitored?

What changes in ES or other impacts have been documented (in program monitoring and wider literature)? What monitoring protocols were implemented?

What methods/proxies were used, and at what spatial and temporal scales?

How do upstream participants and/or downstream stakeholders perceive ecological impacts? (Might show disconnect between ES monitored and impacts of interest to participants or other stakeholders).

Water quality and water quantity have always been the primary environmental outcomes of *Watershared*. A hydrological modeling exercise, using data available at the national level, found a likely link between deforestation in the Los Negros headwaters and decreased dry-season water flows in Los Negros. It predicted that an annual upper watershed deforestation rate of 0.8% would decrease dry-season stream flow in Los Negros by 75% over 10 years (Asquith et al., 2008). Following these modelling predictions, Le Tellier et al (2009) attempted to better quantify stream flow in this pilot *Watershared* program. Stream depth and flow were regularly measured at four points of the main Los Negros River, and in eight of its tributaries. Four of these tributaries were heavily forested, while the other four had been significantly disturbed (Le Tellier et al., 2009).

Trying to develop a "quick and dirty" data collection protocol unfortunately did not work though and results were inconclusive. Natura then decided to invest in a more thorough assessments of water quality. A five-year, six-paired watershed doctoral research project supervised by Dr Conrado Tobon of the

National University of Colombia (Medellin) concluded that conservation of a hectare of forest in the Santa Cruz valleys can lead to a net increase of 700 cubic meters of dry season baseflow (Y. Manco and C. Tobon, unpublished data).

Given the complexities of quantifying trends in water quantity, most *Watershed* programs have focused on measuring water quality. Pynegar et al (2018) undertook an evaluation to see if forest conservation through *Watershed* contracts could improve water quality. The principal parameter of water quality was *Escherichia coli* colony forming unit concentration (CFUs) in water samples. *E. coli* concentration, along with that of other non-*E. coli* bacteria belonging to the coliform group, was quantified using the Coliscan Easygel method (Micrology Labs, Goshen, IN, USA). Coliscan Easygel allows enumeration of coliforms as after incubation *E. coli* colonies appear purple, blue-purple or dark blue. Pynegar et al (2018) found that the presence of cattle feces in water or on the stream banks results in higher *E. coli* contamination at individual sites. Moreover, with cattle removed from upstream forests through *Watershed* agreements, the probability of having *E. coli* in the water system decreases 66-93% and the concentration of *E. coli* decreases 3 times.

In terms of the impact of *Watershed* on forest cover, it must be recognized that not all land put under conservation agreements is in areas that are apt for other land uses, and even if it is, some landowners would not have converted them in the absence of the *Watershed* project. Moreover, landowners do not always fully comply with their conservation commitments. Bottazzi et al (2018) discovered that 14% of conserved parcels were apt for agriculture (and 30% for cattle grazing), would have been converted if the project had not happened, the landowner complied with the agreement but s/he plans to convert these lands after the project finishes. This estimate (14-30%) of how much forest would have been degraded in the no-project scenario (i.e. the additionality of the program), is self reported (Bottazzi et al 2018).

As an alternative way to quantify impact and additionality, as part of the Randomized Control Trial described above, Wiik et al. (2019) investigated the effectiveness and efficacy of the program at reducing deforestation, over 5 years, by applying generalized additive models (GAMs) to global forest change (GFC) data. The researchers undertook a standard ITT evaluation to explore effectiveness at the level of randomization regardless of uptake of *Watershed* agreements in individual communities, and further quantified efficacy by evaluating the effect of uptake on deforestation (c.f. “as-treated” analysis). They controlled for factors that can relate to both uptake and deforestation, including propensity to enroll (endogeneity), and considered the potential influence of unobserved confounding factors. Because the program was voluntary, and the “price” offered in this iteration of *Watershed* was low, relatively small amounts of land were put under protection overall. There was therefore not a large difference between the % of a community's forests actually under conservation in the “program-offered” treatment vs. in the “program NOT-offered” treatment. While forest loss over five years in the treated communities was less, the difference was minimal (Wiik et al. 2019). Thus small landscape affect – which can be explained as a function of low program uptake – contrasts with the 10-39% self-reported additionality of deforestation reductions on individual conservation parcels (Bottazzi et al., 2018)

Participation

(How) have participation levels and longevity been assessed? What is the extent of participation in the areas covered by the program?

Watershared agreements vary greatly in their length, ranging from one year to twenty, with a few beneficiaries even having donated their land to the program to be conserved in perpetuity. In villages where the program was offered and sign up is by individuals, household participation varied between 0 and 100%, with a mean of 47% (Wiik et al 2020). In other municipalities, where decision-making is communal, the entire village has to decide to enter or not. Of the 70 communities offered the program in eastern Tarija, Bolivia, only one declined.

What evidence exists in the literature regarding the main factors influencing participation (e.g. non-monetary motivations, barriers, availability of alternative labor markets or livelihood options, etc.)? This may overlap with material above.

Watershared uses in-kind compensations rather than monetary payments and makes extensive efforts to engage with norms of reciprocity and cooperation. While material factors play a large role in motivating participation in the program, such factors seem to reflect barriers to entry rather than the draw of actual financial incentives. Participants are more likely to have formal land title, have larger homes and to own cattle. Lack of formal land title thus represents a clear barrier to entry to the program. Owning a larger home is a proxy for wealth, the lack of which represents another barrier to entry. Because the compensation program requires removal of cattle from associated land, cattle ownership increases the costs of compliance with the contracts and is therefore related to the size of the financial motivation to participate, but it could also represent a barrier to entry, as it is another important proxy for wealth in this setting. Such barriers may preclude households from participating in the program even if they do have a desire to enroll (Grillos 2017).

On the other hand, social embeddedness is a strong determinant of participation. Measures of embeddedness include: whether a household reports that they participate in community work, whether they participate in the pre-existing decision-making institution in the community, and the number of generations the family has resided in the village. Those who choose to participate in the program are more socially embedded than those who do not participate, suggesting that social motivations may indeed play a role in the decision to participate (Grillos 2017). Framing the program in ways that engage with pre-existing social norms thus may promote participation. In contrast, there is no evidence that participants are motivated by any intrinsic valuation of the environment (Grillos 2017)

In summary, then (i) Material factors, particularly in the form of barriers to entry, play a large role in determining participation in the program. These factors skew participation toward wealthier community members, with potential implications for longterm equity of the program. (ii) Intrinsic valuation of the environment does not appear to play a large role in the decision to participate in the compensation program, though this may be due to the difficulty of measuring internal beliefs. (iii) Social embeddedness is a strong predictor of participation, more so in communities where pre-existing norms surrounding

reciprocity are still salient (Grillos 2017). Other important determinants of participation are individual motivations (d'Adda 2011, Bottazzi et al. 2018), and whether or not households were available to attend the meetings in which the program was presented (Wiik et al. 2019).

Other outcomes and research gaps

Effects on land tenure?

Land tenure arrangements are highly informal in much of the Andes. Few landowners have government-approved titles, but rather rely on signed purchase contracts, some of which are generations old, as proof of possession. *Watershared* can sidestep this tenure problem, because the locally defined *Watershared* agreements do not require formal land titles but instead rely on locally accepted definitions of who owns and controls, or grants access to, watershed forests. In Bolivia, tenure is confirmed and agreements are signed on the basis of simple assurances from neighbours and the village chief that a piece of land belongs to an individual. *Watershared* ownership decisions are thus based on local consensus, and although such tenure does not necessarily have *de jure* recognition, the *de facto* definition of boundaries used by participants in the *Watershared* scheme is often stronger (Asquith 2016)

In the early days of *Watershared*, 15 years ago, Bolivian land titling process was far less advanced than today. This was a major problem as landless immigrants viewed forested areas not delimited by barbed wire as unused and available for colonization. Many new immigrants cleared land illegally or 'informally', i.e. on land owned by other farmers or within the national park, and establish possession without any supporting documentation (Asquith et al., 2008).

It thus appears that some *Watershared* programs provide pronounced additionality simply by controlling colonization by landless people. In upstream Los Negros, for example, a clear perception existed that formalized *Watershared* contracts with maps and demarcations helped institutionalize *de facto* land-tenure security, thus reinforcing intra-village acceptance of tenure claims, and raising the probability of successfully resisting invasions. No successful migrant invasion has occurred on *Watershared*-enrolled land. Indicative for the strategy of *Watershared* as tenure consolidation is also the increasing number of landowners that have requested to be paid by barbed wire as an in-kind compensation, which they utilized to fence off their land (Asquith et al., 2008)

Off-site impacts/leakage?

Is there evidence of off-site or indirect social or environmental impacts, including e.g. impacts on other labor markets, social cohesion, cultural practices, or broader environmental impacts due to intensification of agriculture or land conversion elsewhere?

Is there evidence of 'value crowding,' positive or negative?

Data post *Watershared* implementation shows that the program increased prioritization of environmental values (evidence of crowding-in as opposed to crowding out) and altered social beliefs related to inequality and the role of government. *Watershared* thus had a positive impact on promoting

environmental values and increased the belief that government involvement in helping landowners invest in conservation is appropriate (Grillos et al. 2019)

6. Methodology and literature:

Literature was identified by consulting with researchers and practitioners that have been involved with the *Watershared*/ARA model. I am confident that I have included most, if not all peer-reviewed published articles that discuss the program. I have also included a few gray literature articles written by researchers known to program implementers.

References

- Abell, R., N.M. Asquith, et al. (2017). [*Beyond the Source: The Environmental, Economic and Community Benefits of Source Water Protection*](#). The Nature Conservancy, Arlington, VA, USA.
- Asquith, N.M., (2016). [*Watershared: Adaptation, Mitigation, Watershed Protection and Economic Development in Latin America*](#), Climate and Development Knowledge Network.
- Asquith N.M. (2011). [*Reciprocal Agreements for Water: An Environmental Management Revolution in the Santa Cruz Valleys*](#). *Harvard Review of Latin America*
- Asquith, N.M. (2020). Large-Scale Randomized Control Trials of Incentive-Based Conservation: What Have We Learned? *World Development*
- Asquith N.M., Vargas Ríos M.T., Wunder, S. (2008). Bundling environmental services: Decentralized in-kind payments for bird habitat and watershed protection in Los Negros. *Ecological Economics*.
- Asquith, N.M., Vargas, M.T. (2007). *Fair Deals for Watershed Services in Bolivia*. Natural Resource Issues Series Number 7, IIED, London